

THE SOCIOLOGY OF THE YORUBA NOVEL: A STUDY OF ISAAC THOMAS,
D. O. FAGUNWA, AND OLADEJO OKEDIJI

BY

JAMES ADEBISI OGUNŞINA
B.A. (Hons.), M.Phil (Ibadan)

A thesis in the
Department of Linguistics And African Languages.

Submitted to the Faculty of Arts in partial
Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
of the
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IBADAN, NIGERIA.

APRIL, 1967

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to the cherished memory of my
late Father

MICHAEL ADE OGUNSINA (AMODE-ERIN)

Àmòdé, fòṣṣòrò, Ajílogba

Àmòde òpó, Arígbadáṣà

Amòde ọmọ à ní léde aṣọ

Amòdé ọmọ à ní léde èwù

Amòde ọmọ à ní lede àpótí

Amòde tó bá dọrun ọja ni Jàágún

Olúkálukú a gelete lori ohun ti Baba re,

Aróyèhún Amòdé, m á jẹ wọn ó gelete lórí
ohun ti Babá re

Amòde ọmọ Ṣonibáre eke o wu ni ika ko

wu ọmọ èniyan

Ikà ò fẹ ka rẹrù ká sọ

Ṣonibare ori ẹni ni in sọ ni

Ọmọ à ní jo o lọ lójúde èké, ọmọ

re ní gberin

Èké 'fẹ ka pe lékèé loun

Ikà ò jẹ ra re nikà.

Abstract

Up till now, no systematic and sustained study on the sociology of the Yoruba novel has appeared in print. The sociology of ~~the~~ Yoruba novel belongs to the realm of sociology of literature, a field that is new in Yoruba literary criticism. This study attempts to explore that area. It examines the relationship between selected Yoruba novelists and their society.

The study has two broad divisions - the theoretical and the critical. It is made up of four chapters. The first chapter which constitutes the theoretical base of the study attempts to answer the question, "What is Sociology of Literature? It examines the origins, principles, and methods of literary sociology. Sociology of literature is seen as a fusion of two distinct disciplines - sociology and literature, both serving complementary functions in our understanding of the society. The various approaches - positivistic, Marxist, formalist, structuralist and Goldmann's genetic structuralism are critically examined. However, it is the Marxist literary approach, in a general sense, that is adopted in this work.

Chapter Two discusses the relationship of Isaac Thomas, the first Yoruba novelist, to his changing colonial society. Thomas lived and wrote at a time when the Lagos society began to experience the socio-economic effects of the emerging capitalist economy, a phenomenon which gradually made members of the society individualistic, materialistic and dehumanized. In a society where material loyalty has displaced communal loyalty, what is the novelist's reaction? The study reveals Thomas's first and only novel as a bitter opposition to the materialistic world-view of the nascent bourgeoisie.

In the third Chapter, the first two novels of D.O. Fagunwa are discussed with a view to understanding his relationship to his society. As the study shows, Fagunwa, unlike Thomas, allies with a world view which establishes the status quo of the colonial - missionary ruling class. Not only does Fagunwa accept the world view of moral excellence which he considers a crystalising force for the society, he proclaims and reinforces it.

Chapter four is a detailed study of the first two novels of Oladejo Okediji, to highlight the relationship between the artist and his society. The period of Okediji's writing was one of glaring social ills. The changing socio-economic patterns heightened the zest for material acquisition, leading

to various unscrupulous practices that generated a general sense of insecurity to life and property. The ineptitude and inefficiency of the police force, coupled with the conciliatory and fearful attitude of the public further compound the problem. Okediji's panacea to the brutal wave of criminality in the society is action - positive action, a theme that reverberates in all aspects of the structure of the novels.

The concluding chapter gathers the threads of thought together, evincing the usefulness of sociology of literature as a new dimension in the literary criticism of Yoruba literature. It reveals the theory as a comprehensive one which makes it possible to see a work of art in a wider context, a totality, in which the parts relate to the whole in a particular way, depicting the interrelationship between the novelist, the novel, and the society. It ends with suggestions for further studies in the sociology of literature.

Acknowledgement

No research is ever the work of a single person. It is therefore with deep sense of appreciation that I express my sincere thanks to all who in varying ways, have contributed in no small measure, to the success of this work.

First, I am profoundly grateful to my Supervisor, Professor Olatunde O Olatunji, for his love and co-operation since my undergraduate days. I greatly appreciate his insightful suggestions and constructive criticisms throughout the process of this research. I am grateful to Dr. Femi Osofisan who read through the first draft of this thesis and gave me valuable comments and suggestions. I thank Professor Ayọ Bamgboṣe for his support and encouragement at every stage of this work. To Dr. Ben Elugbe, Acting Head of Department of Linguistics and African Languages, I am immensely grateful for his unflinching support and co-operation to see this work to its successful completion. I am sincerely thankful to Mrs Molarara Ogundipe-Leslie, Dr. Karin Barber and Mr. Olabiyi Yai who made available to me rare books, without which this work could have been difficult, if not impossible.

I express my heart-felt thanks to my many Christian friends for their genuine love and concern. I am particularly grateful to the following: Dr. Kunle Adeniran, Mr. Dokun Fadiran,

Mr. Olu Daramola, Dr. Isaac Madugu, Dr. Akintunde Akinsoyinu, Dr. Dosu Oyewole, Dr. Omoniyi Adewoye, Dr. Bunmi Ogun, Prof. Wale Odutuga, Mich. Filani, Dr. Yiwola Awoyale, Prof. Beban Chumbow, Lt. Col. Makanjuola, Engr. Yemi Tanisowo, Bro. Olu. Ologun, Bro. Bode Ojo, Mrs. J.O. Ogunranti, Bro. Isaac Ogunola and Pastor Olu AriJesudade for their invigorating prayers and spiritual support, at all times. I am grateful to Professor Oladele Awobuluyi and Professor Oludare Olatubu for their encouragement.

My thanks are due to the staff of the Universities of Ibadan and Ilorin Libraries for their assistance and co-operation. I am greatly indebted to the University of Ilorin for funding the research that produced this work. I also thank Mr. E. Ediale who typed this work.

To my dear brother Adesoye Ogunfina and his wife Bolatito, I express sincere appreciation for hosting me while writing the final draft of this thesis. To my beloved Lasun and Yinka, is special thanks for their sincere brotherly love and fervent prayers.

I am profoundly grateful to 'my darling Becky' for holding the fort during my many journeys on this research. And finally, and most importantly, to my Almighty God, whose promises are yea and amen, be all laud, honour, and glory for ever. Amen.

CERTIFICATION BY SUPERVISOR

I certify that this work was carried out by
Mr. J. A. Ogunsina in the Department of Linguistics
and African Languages, University of Ibadan.

S U P E R V I S O R

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April, 1987

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CHAPTER ONE

The Novelist and Society

No critical work on Yoruba written literature has attempted an indepth study of the relationship between literature and society. Critical studies on Yoruba novel have so far been based largely, on the examination of literary texts alone. Such studies give us an inadequate knowledge about the role of the Yoruba novelist in his society. Lack of knowledge about a novelist's society, as well as his relationship to that society, results in a partial and superficial understanding of his work.

The question of the relationship between literature and society, as well as the role of the literary artist and his society, has occupied the minds of many writers and literary critics for quite some time. Some critics hold the view that all literature is ideological. They contend that most writers express some kind of ideology, either implicitly through their imaginative writings, or in explicit pronouncements on social and/or political issues. They claim that almost all artists have some concept of what their role in society should be.

The relationship between literature and society is a very complex one. This is why there are divergent views on what

should be the role of the novelist in the society. There is no consensus as to whether the novel should simply instruct, or indeed attempt a combination of both at the same time. Moreover, there are those who assert that the novel should not perform either of these functions, but that it should be considered an autonomous work of art in its own right. On what the role of the novelist in the society should be, Samuel Richardson, one of the earliest English novelists, states simply: "Instruction, Madame, is the pill; amusement is the gilding."¹ Thus, Richardson is of the opinion that the principal function of the novelist is to instruct and enlighten, the matter of amusement is a secondary role. The same didactic enthusiasm was expressed by Trollope, the nineteenth century novelist. He says:

I have ever thought of myself as a preacher of sermons and my pulpit as one which I could make both salutary and agreeable to my audience.²

The mid-nineteenth century witnessed divergent views on the issue of the novelist's role in the society. On the one hand, were those novelists who felt it was their task simply to

1. Richardson, Samuel, letter to Lady Elching quoted in Allot, M: n1965 Novelists on the Novel, Routledge and Kegan Paul, p.90.

2. Ibid., p.87

create a work of art and that this should not be a vehicle for political and/or social comment. On the other hand, were those novelists who felt it their duty to be socially committed and to point out the evils of society. Flaubert, one member of the former school of thought declared in 1868:

I do not recognize my right to accuse anyone. I do not even think that the novelist should express his own opinion of the things of the world. He may communicate it, but I do not want him to state it... And so, I limit myself to revealing things as they appear to me to explaining that which seems to me, to be the truth.³

Flaubert seems to disagree with committed literature. But it is the very nature of art, particularly the novel, to communicate the artist's view of his society. The communication contains some form of comment. Thus, it is not perfectly true to claim that a particular artist is not committed. George Orwell points out this quite bluntly. He asserts:

No book is genuinely free from political bias. The opinion that art should have nothing to do with politics is in itself a political attitude.⁴

3. Ibid., pp. 94-95

4. Quoted in Bald, S.R. 1982, Novelists and Political Consciousness. p.xiv

Yinka d'Almeida also takes the point further when she says: Any kind of writing is committed, one way or the other. There can be no neutrality in literature and one could say that not being committed is still being committed to non-commitment. See d'Almeida, Y. 1974 "Political and Social Commitment and the Problem of Audience in African Literature". Seminar paper, Dept of English, University of Ibadan, P.I.

It is the view of novelists like George Eliot that the novelist cannot avoid influencing the society. Eliot maintains that a novelist is inevitably a teacher or influencer of the public mind, and sees the novelist's role in the society as akin to that of a setter of fashions in furniture and dress who fills his shops with designs and leaves the public to express their opinion.⁵

Eliot's opinion is a pointer to the subtle difference between writers who inevitably influence the public mind and those who deliberately set out to do so. For there are novelists who regard it their paramount duty to bring the evils in society to public attention. Zola, who belongs to this latter category put his views quite clearly:

We are looking for the causes of social evil, we study the anatomy of social classes and individuals to explain the derangements which are produced in society and man... Now it remains for the legislators to bring the good and develop it. No work can be more moralizing than ours, because it is upon it that the law should be based. Our virtue does not consist of words but of acts; we are active labourers who examine the building, point out the rotten girders, the interior crevices, the loosened stones, all ravages which are not seen from outside, and which can at any time undermine the entire edifice.⁶

5. Allot, M. op.cit., p.94.

6. Ibid. p.94.

Thus from the point of view of eighteenth and nineteenth century European novelists, a novelist has a definite role to play in the society. Our brief survey of some of their views reveals that didacticism, commitment and reflectionism, are some of the main concerns of the novelist in his society.

From the standpoint of Yoruba novelists whose works began only during this twentieth century, what is the relationship between the novelist and his society? From the critical viewpoint, is reflectionism, didacticism, or commitment the main concern of the novelist? What, for instance, is Akin Isola's role in the society depicted in Ó le kú? Is Ó le kú a mere reflection of a morally perverse university campus life? Is it just a covert attempt to expose condemnable moral practices?⁷ Are Olabimtan's Ayànmó and Baba Rere no more than a depiction of a morally depraved society, a society that is "corrupt through and through"? Are novelists like Ogundele, Odundo and others in their category no more than moralists? A criticism of Ó le kú as merely reflectionist, reveals little about Akin Isola's society. For Ó le kú is not merely reflectionist and covertly

7. See Ogunsina, B. 1981 Akoyawo Alaye lori Ó le kú U.P.L., Ibadan.

didactic. Rather, it is a tragic expression of the novelist's attack on the static and philistine Yoruba traditional ideology on marriage.

But how can the critic understand the novelist's relationship to his society? How can the totality of a novelist's art lead us to an understanding of his society? Of what relevance is the Yoruba novelist's individuality, the literary tradition of his time, the content, form, and language of his work as well as the socio-economic situation of his era to a meaningful knowledge of the society he portrays? The problem of the relationship between the novel and society is a crucial factor in sociology of the novel. The Sociology of the novel is a significant aspect of sociology of literature. Thus any meaningful study of the sociology of the Yoruba novel would require a probing into the sociology of literature. What is sociology of literature?

Sociology of Literature

The term 'sociology of literature' was coined by Taine, the French philosopher and critic (1828-1893).⁸ The desire to develop a completely scientific outlook, to submit literature and art to the same research methods as those employed in the physical and natural sciences, led to the founding of this

8. Laurenson, D. and Swingewood, A; 1971
The Sociology of Literature, MacGibbon and
Kee, London, p.31.

relatively new field of literary study. Sociology of literature is a fairly late arrival when compared for instance, with other well established studies in sociology. For instance, there are well developed sociologies of religion, education, politics, sports, knowledge, language, etc. But it is not until recently that the sociology of literature begins to receive any serious attention.

As its name suggests, sociology of literature is a fusion of two distinct disciplines - sociology and literature. In its very general sense, sociology is the science of social relationships as well as the consequences of those relationships for ongoing social systems and the process of social change.⁹ Sociology concerns itself with all that happens to human beings as a result of their relations to each other. Like all social sciences, sociology deals with the world of man's experience - man's behaviour with regard to his fellows, but its main focus is the group or the larger social entity. To sociology, man's existence is in essence, social; his life is bound up with various groups which encompass the social group called society. Various theories of knowledge may focus on one aspect or another

9. Moore, W.E. 1967 'Sociology' in Encyclopaedia Americana, Vol. 25, pp. 207-215.

of social life, but the sociologist's emphasis is on beliefs, values, moral rules, and symbolic communication, which form the distinctive features of human life. The goal of sociology is to understand the society through scientific means. Thus, it sets itself the task of finding solution to the questions of how society is possible, how it works, why it persists.¹⁰ This is achieved through a rigorous examination of the social institutions, religious, economic, political and filial, which together constitute what is called structure. The result of the examination is usually a picture of the ways in which man adapts to, and is conditioned by, particular societies. Sociology attempts to present a picture of the mechanisms of socialization, the process of cultural learning, whereby individuals are allocated to accept their respective roles in the social structure.

Christopher Caudwell defines sociology rather simply:

At one time men are doing different things and therefore stand in relation to one another. The study of these human relations in a general form is sociology.¹¹

10. Barber, K. 1978 Why do we need a sociology of Literature? University of Ife, Seminar paper, p.1.

11. Caudwell, C. 1977. Illusion and Reality, Lawrence and Wishart, London, p.15.

But sociology is more than the mere study of human relations. It is also concerned with the process of change within the society; that is, how society changes gradually or radically from one type of society to another - and the effects these changes have on the social structure.¹² In the Marxist perspective, sociology is conceived as concerned not only with man's reaction to, but also with his reaction upon, social phenomena.¹³

Literature, on the other hand, is concerned with man and his society. It is an art composed of words in such a way, that it proffers entertainment, enlightenment, and relaxation. It attempts to develop, elevate, expand, and transform the experience of its audience. Literature functions as a continuing symbolic criticism of social values. As a virile vehicle of human expression, literature seeks to investigate man, his behaviour in society, his knowledge of himself and the universe in which he finds himself. Literature is part and product of society. Its nature is essentially social.

12. Berger, P.L. 1980. Invitation to Sociology
Penguin, pp. 11-40.

13. I am grateful to Dr. Femi Osofisan for his
this Marxist view of Sociology.

It has no independence from man, for it is produced by people living together, it is a structure of words, and ideas which are shared and understood by members of a community. As Barber points out, Literature, in the Marxist perspective is more than being a part and product of the society:

It also reacts on society. It plays an important part in shaping or crystallising the views held by the members of the society; views about the world, about man, and about society. And it is in the light of views like this that the social order is both maintained and changed.¹⁴

Furthermore, literature is indicative of the society, thus the novel which is the major literary genre in many literate societies, has been seen as a faithful attempt to re-create man's social world, to produce a fictional universe akin to his social institutions, his aspirations, and tensions. Thus it can be seen that literature treads a common social, economic and political ground as sociology. But as art, literature transcends mere objective and scientific analysis of society. It penetrates the surfaces of social life, revealing in a much deeper sense, the feelings of man in the face of his varying

14. Barber, K. 1978, op. cit., p.1.

experiences within his society.¹⁵

From the fore-going, it can be safely surmised that literature and sociology are not wholly distinct disciplines; rather, they complement each other in our understanding of society. Richard Hoggart, aptly attests to this when he asserts that:

Without the full literary witness, the student of society will be blind to the fullness of a society.¹⁶

Hoggart's assertion then underscores the point that a knowledge of a society's literature is essential for a full and meaningful understanding of that society.

Sociology of literature, therefore, is an attempt to understand the inter-relationship between literature and society. It postulates that a work of art does not exist in isolation and should not be studied as such. This is because works of art are not independent of their society. Literature is language in action. The language with which a work of art is composed is the property of the society. The literary artist is not independent of his society, his personality is

15. Warren, A. 1964. "Literature" in Encyclopaedia Americana Vol. 24. pp. 119-124.

16. Hoggart, R. 1966. "Literature and Society" p.56.

influenced by many socio-political and economic factors. No individual forms his ideas in isolation, he is born into society and learns his concepts from the social environment.

Sociology of literature sees the relation between a work of art, the artist, and the society as one of constant interaction, and that each one affects, and is affected by the other. If we take the novel which is the focus of this study as a reference point, it will be clearly observed that neither the novel nor the novelist can be said to be independent of the society. The sociology of the novel sees the novel, the novelist and the society as inextricably bound together, such that neither the novel, nor the novelist, nor the influence of society on both can be considered in isolation. Rather, to understand one fully, there is need for constant reference to the other two components of the triangle.

Thus if we take the novelist as our starting point, it is clearly observable that his relationship with the society is a two-way one. A social being that he is, his attitudes and ideas will undoubtedly be shaped by the social, cultural,

political, and economic background from which he springs. He expresses a definite world vision in his art; through this, he relates back to the society. For instance, the Yoruba world vision on marriage is the focal point of Akinola's Filà lobinrin.¹⁷ In spite of the various angles from which he views marriage, at the end, we are left in no doubt that this novelist is in perfect agreement with the Yoruba traditional view of marriage, that it is not only love that determines marriage, the elements of destiny and divine injunction play significant roles. Therefore in the creation of his individual work of art, a novelist brings to bear the unique combination of his own personality and environment. The manner in which he creates, is almost certainly influenced by the literary traditions with which he is familiar. This is in fact true of many literary innovators, after all, no invention springs out of nothing, for whatever a man creates is usually the product of accumulated knowledge and experience.

Since the novel is not simply the product of an isolated mind, it follows that it cannot be considered in isolation from the society of which it is a part. As rightly pointed

17. See Akinola, B. 1982. Filà Lobinrin, Evans Ibadan.

out by Watt (1957) and Ghent (1965) the form of the novel as we know it today has been largely determined by a complicated set of factors, again social, cultural, political and economic in nature. Indeed all literary and artistic forms invariably bear close relations to the type of society from which they emerge. If the novel is determined by social conditions, it necessarily follows that the novel is in some way indicative of the society, and as such we can from it learn something about the society. This however, does not suggest that the novel and society have a straightforward one to one relationship. Such a suggestion could lead to the erroneous idea of seeing the novel as a mere reflection of society.

Sociology of literature therefore concerns itself with literature as literature, not solely as the simple or complex reflection of social structure. Socio-economic factors as the major determinant of literary creativity must be analysed in close conjunction with actual literary texts. The texts themselves should never be dissolved into environment.¹⁸

18. Laurenson, D and Swingewood, A. op.cit., p.169.

APPROACHES TO SOCIOLOGY OF LITERATURE

Various approaches have been suggested for the sociology of literature. One of the most popular is the "mirror image approach" which sees literature as documentary, arguing that it provides a mirror to the age. One of the first proponents of this approach was the French philosopher Louis de Bonald (1754-1840). Bonald was one of the first writers to argue that through a careful reading of any nation's literature, 'one could tell what his people had been'. The mirror image approach views literature as a direct reflection of various facets of social structure, family relationships, class conflicts and possibly divorce trends and population composition. It conceives a literary work as an attempt to depict events and happenings in a particular society. The approach aims at transferring the fictional world of literature to specific social meanings. Lowenthal, (1957:19) one of the distinguished writers in the sociology of literature expresses what the approach expects of the literary critic:

It is the task of the sociologist of literature to relate the experience of the writer's imaginary characters and situations to the historical climate from which they derive. He has to transform the private equation of themes and stylistic means into social equations.

Thus from the point of view of the mirror image approach, a literary piece is a veritable mine of information about the society that produces it. A writer's imaginary characters are representations of distinct social situations. Events and situations in a work of art are not just figments of the artist's imagination, they have direct relationship to specific historical periods in a society. The themes of a literary work have to be interpreted in relation to definite social facts of the society where the artefact takes its root. The narrative technique and stylistic devices employed by an artist are not an end in themselves, they all have social implications. It is therefore the duty of the literary sociologist to transform the private world of literature to specific social meanings.

The mirror image approach has its advantages. It affirms the conviction that art's relations to society are vitally important, and that the investigation of these relationships may organize and deepen our knowledge of a work of art. It is furthermore a confirmation of the view that art is not created in a vacuum; it is the work not simply of a person, but of an author fixed in time and setting, answering to a community of which he is an important and articulate part. It therefore stresses that literature reflects various norms of the society that produces it.

The approach has many flaws. First it places greater emphasis on the extrinsic aspect of a literary work. Leavis (1952) argues strongly against the method, he sees it as tending to use literature solely as a quarry of information to be sociologically 'ransacked'; to be turned over from the outside by those lacking the necessary critical apparatus for understanding and evaluation. Furthermore there is the danger that the literary sociologist might not have the sufficient skill to unravel the historical details of particular periods. The approach greatly limits the critical appraisal of a work of art to only a person who has knowledge of the structure of society from other sources than literary, to find out the adequacy or inadequacy of the specific social meanings in a literary work. The approach has a greater concentration on extraneous factors than on the literary text itself. The method ^{de-emphasises} the writer's personality, awareness and intention. For many writers do not set out simply to depict the social world in largely descriptive terms. Works of art do more than mere reflecting of social norms and attitudes. Thus a literary criticism that simply reflects the social and historical incidents in a work of art is a narrow and over-simplified interpretation of the artist's effort. Another weakness of the mirror image approach is that, it ranks the

literary text secondary in the process of literary criticism. A greater problem arises over the question of what literature actually reflects. If the novel, for instance, is the mirror of an age, is it not possible that what is portrayed is a distortion of the age? Is artistic fidelity to social and historical truth the goal of a work of art? When a work of art becomes an accurate record of specific historical period, it tends to be a work of history rather than literature. It is therefore important that the concept of the mirror must be treated with great care in the sociological analysis of literature.

The second approach to a literary sociology shifts emphasis from the work of literature itself and concentrates exclusively on the production, distribution and consumption. Robert Escarpit is a leading advocate of this approach. He argues that patronage and cost of production rather than the literary text should be the focus of critical discussion of a work of art. The approach holds that a literary work should, for example, be studied in relation to the book industry and the production, distribution and consumption of works of literature.¹⁹

19. Escarpit, R. 1971. Sociology of Literature, Frank Cass and Co. Ltd., pp. 1-9.

Escarpit seems to be mainly interested in the problems of how literary production and consumption affect the content and form of particular works of art. He states his view categorically:

The literary phenomenon cannot be the work of art itself, but rather, the meeting and sometimes the clashing of two free acts, one of production and the other of consumption, with all their moral and social relations. There is always another man in literature: a writer for a reader and a reader for a writer.²⁰

The point Escarpit is making is that an understanding of the writer's position in the book industry is essential for a thorough interpretation of his work. This is because book publishing is an industrial venture with a profit making concern. It requires the collaboration of readers, editors, printers, distributors and advertisers for the business to succeed. The artist is often an exploitable material of the publishing business. The technology and relations of production employed in the publication of works of literature can have important effects not only on the relations between the literary work and the audience, but also on the content and form of literature itself.

20. Escarpit, R. 1968: Encyclopaedia of the Social Sciences Vol. 9, pp. 417-425.

A comparison of the traditional Yoruba poet with the literary writer will further illustrate this point. In performing his art, the local oral poet (Akéwi) has a close, direct and informal relationship with his audience. He easily identifies members of the audience. He can be prompted when he is in doubt. The reactions of his audience are immediately known to him and these serve to induce him to introduce variety into his style of performance. He digresses at will, introduces humour, interpolates his utterances with stories, comic expressions and songs. It is this situation that often determines the form and style characteristic of the Yoruba praise poetry (oríki) - their fluidity, variety, humour and sense of endlessness.²¹

This is similarly the case in some other Yoruba oral literary genres. In the performance of Yoruba oracle chant (ìyèrè Ifa) for instance, varieties and interpolations are often introduced depending on situational events during the performance. If for instance, the Iyèrè Ifa chanter suddenly stops as a result of forgetfulness, another chanter can quickly

21. Barber, K. 1978. op.cit. p.5

cut in to break the abrupt silence, by saying:

Ẹ kilọ fámúnimúyè kó má a lọ o

Ẹ kilọ fámúnimúyè kó máa lọ o

Ẹ kilọ fámunimúyè kó máa lọ

Please, warn the faculty paralyzer to depart

Please, warn the faculty paralyzer to depart

Please, warn the faculty paralyzer to depart.

The other members of the group sing the interpolation in unison thus saving the face of the chanter. This song coda, allows for continuity and it dispels the chanter's anxiety, giving him the opportunity to re-adjust.

Furthermore, it may be a situation when the Iyèrè Ifá chanter is performing impressively to the admiration and adulation of the audience, who in turn recompenses him with cash gifts. A member of the chanting group could cut in abruptly:

Asán owó làwé n pa o

Asán owó làwé n pa

Awé ò sùn yèrè

Asán owó làwé n pa

Our friend is merely collecting money
 It is only money our friend is collecting
 Our friend no longer chants iyere
 Our friend is merely collecting money

This song coda is quickly taken up by the other members of the chanting group. The song produces instant humour and the affected chanter quickly resumes chanting with a greater feeling of success and dynamism. At other times, it might be that the members of the chanting group are not responding adequately to the chorus "Hẹn ẹn". The leading chanter can quickly revive them by saying:

Èlé: Ẹni bá gberin mi o
 Á logún ẹrú

Ègbè: Hẹn ẹn

Èlé: Ẹni bá gberin mi o
 A lẹgbọ̀n iwọ̀fà

Ègbè: Hẹn ẹn

Èlé: Ẹni bá gberin mi o
 A lẹgbẹrun ọkẹ nílẹ

Ègbè: Hẹn ẹn

Èlé: Èni tí ò gbè'yèrè
Èè ní r'eyèlé tà lógún-lúgba

Egbè: Lógún-lúgba, eni tí ò gbeyèrè
O níi r'eyèlé tà lógún lúgba o²²

Leader: He who responds to my song will
have twenty slaves.

Chorus: Yes

Leader: He who responds to my song will
have thirty pawns.

Chorus: Yes

Leader: He who responds to my song
Shall own two hundred and fifty pounds
in his house (₦500.00).

Chorus: Yes

Leader: He who does not respond to my Iyèrè
Will not have pigeons to sell in
twenties and two hundreds.

Chorus: In twenties and two hundreds, he
who does not respond to the Iyèrè
will not have pigeons to sell in
twenties and two hundreds.

22. See Areoye, A. 1980. Iyèrè Ifá: Okan nínu Ewi Abalaye Yoruba Long Essay. University of Ilorin, p.21.

Such an interpolation by the leading chanter instantly brings animation into the performance of the chanting group and facilitates effective participation, team spirit and co-ordination of effort. Such ingenious and innovative interpolations produce variety and often lengthens the period of performance.

Even in Yoruba folktales (Aló Apagbè) the narrator can creatively introduce digressions and repetitions, if his audience demonstrates appreciation and admiration of his narrative ability. The narrator playing upon the interest and attention of his audience can exaggerate characters and incidents for the enjoyment of his audience. He could prolong the song aspect of the tale if he observes that his audience admires it. Thus depending on the narrator's competence and the audience's cooperation, a Yoruba folktale which should normally last five minutes may be prolonged for a much longer period.

This is not the case with the novelist. He is writing for a vast audience, virtually unknown to him. He tries to write in a way that would be acceptable not only to the audience but also to his publishers. He attempts to create his own world, endeavours to give it an air of complete authenticity. He tries as much as possible to make his

narrative description a faithful portrayal of reality. These varying efforts account for the tradition of novel writing - lengthy, leisurely, lucid, and detailed in construction and peopled with large number of characters akin to life in a particular community.

It was this publisher-author-audience relationship that influenced Ajişafẹ's form and style in Enia Sòro and Iwé Igbádun Aiyé. The bulk of his literate audience were christians, his publishers would not publish anything unchristian. The situation accounts for the biblicalness, didacticism and parsonical elements in his writing. His form and style were not determined by his intention alone, but also the demand of his publishers and the desire of his audience. This type of situation was largely responsible for the form and style of many Yoruba novelists adopting the Fagunwa tradition.²³

Thus Escarpit's approach is that the market economy is an important factor in the production of literary works and should be taken into consideration in the criticism of a writer's work. The advantages of his approach are not far to

23. For further details on Novelists of the Fagunwa tradition see Ogunsina, J.A. 1976: The Development of the Yoruba Novel M.Phil. Thesis, pp. 123-180.

seek. For instance, it reveals that a work of art is the product of various socio-economic factors. An understanding of such extraneous factors would enrich the meaning of a literary work. Furthermore, it shows that a realisation of the influences of the book industry on writers will throw useful light on the form and content of literary works. But despite its usefulness, Escarpit's approach is not flawless. Its greatest fault lies in the fact that its concentration on the impact of the book industry is overemphasised.

Whatever the importance of the market economy on the writer, it is just one aspect of the artist's experience, concentration on this aspect in the way Escarpit suggests would lead to a narrow and one-sided interpretation of literature. Thus our main objection to the "positivistic approach" (reflecticism) lies in its greater concentration on extraneous factors than on the literary text itself.

The Marxist Sociology of Literature

Marxist literary criticism has a fairly long history. This is because Karl Marx himself made important general statements about culture and society in the 1840s. In spite of this fact, it is not erroneous to think of Marxist criticism as a twentieth century phenomenon.

The Marxist literary approach derives from the ideas and thoughts of Karl Marx and Fredrick Engels, published in 'The Communist Manifesto'. It has further been formalised in the writings of various Marxists like Lenin, Mao, Lukacs, Goldmann, Brecht etc.²⁵ In their writing, Marx and Engels argue that the history of man is the history of class struggle. It is their contention that the main goal of man's struggle is to liberate himself from certain forms of oppression. Terry Eagleton elaborates on this struggle for liberation.

24. Selden, R. 1980. A Reader's Guide to contemporary literary theory. University of Kentwcky press p. 38.

25. See Lenin, V.I. 1977. Karl-Marx and His Teaching Progress Publishers, Moscow.

Marxism is a scientific theory of human societies and of the practice of transforming them; and what that means, rather more concretely, is that the narrative Marxism has to deliver is the story of the struggles of men and women to free themselves from certain forms of exploitation and oppression.²⁶

Thus the main message of Marxism is the struggle for the transformation of the human society, so that man can be liberated from exploitation and oppression in all its forms and ramifications. In furtherance of their scientific theory, Marx and Engels assert that history is made up of discernible stages of human development. These stages are: antiquity, feudalism, and capitalism, with socialism to follow. Each stage is characterized by a particular mode of production and class structure. Capitalism which is the present stage of development is seen as the most advanced stage of social production, based on commodity production and wage labour. Capitalism, they contend, employs extensive division of labour and sophisticated technology. In the sense that it succeeds in breaking static feudal relations and a stagnant system of production, capitalism is seen as representing a progressive

26. Eagleton, T. 1976: Marxism and Literary Criticism. University of California Press, p.vii.

social formation. But in terms of economic factors, capitalism, they claim, creates an unequal and conflict-ridden society which has led to class consciousness, active antagonism and alienation in many capitalist societies.

As far as literature is concerned, in capitalist societies, Marx and Engels contend, every work of art is a part of the society's superstructure. This superstructure which includes politics, law, religion, philosophy, ethics, literature and the arts, is designed to legitimize and establish the power of the ruling class.²⁷ Literature which is an aspect of this superstructure, functions as a means of crystallizing the society, since it is the product of a particular class, the expression of a particular class consciousness. Thus most of the dominant views and ideas expressed in literature are in effect the ideas of the ruling class, designed to legitimize its position in the society. Marxism sees the society as a totality, all of which parts are interrelated and can be explained by the same law.

27. Melotti, U. 1977: Marx and The Third World
The Macmillan Press, pp.2-7.

Marx and Engels did not however provide a systematic and specific theory of literature. It was left to their followers to create a definitive Marxist sociology of literature. Thus, the Marxist approach to sociology of literature is concerned with how to achieve a total conception of literature in society. First, it tries to understand the relations of literature to social structure. It tries to identify the historic forces that determine the form and content of literature. It seeks to find out how literature in turn reacts on society. By this, Marxist sociology of literature aims at arriving at a comprehensive idea of literature as part of society.

In a bid to achieve this literary objective, two schools have emerged. First are the orthodox scholars, who conceive literature as a mere by-product of the infrastructure, that is, the economic base of society. This school holds that literature is completely determined by this economic base and completely explicable in terms of it. It is this conception of literature, that prompts Lunacharsky, the first Soviet Minister of Culture under Lenin, to declare that:

The goal of the Marxist literary critic should be to produce a complete picture of the entire social development of an epoch, since literary works always reflect conscious or unconscious psychology of that class which the given writer expresses.²⁸

Lunacharsky's statement is a pointer to the goal of the orthodox school of Marxist literary criticism, namely, to evince the totality of the meaning of a particular work of art, mainly through the study of the social structure of the society which gives birth to it.

On the other hand, are Marxists like Jean Duvignaud, who base their interpretation on the early works of Karl Marx. They thus see literature as playing an active role in shaping the consciousness and social aspirations of the people. All Marxists however agree that literature is part of the society's superstructure, and see it as standing in some relation to ideology. What this relation is exactly, is conceived differently by different Marxist critics.

For instance, there are Marxists, like Terry Eagleton, who take an extremely reductionist view. They maintain that superstructure determines ideology, therefore, ideology is

28. Quoted in Laurenson, D. and Swingewood, A.
op.cit., p.41.

expressed directly in literature. Thus, in his introductory explanation to the concept of Marxist criticism, Eagleton declares:

Marxist criticism is part of a larger body of theoretical analysis which aims to understand ideologies - the ideas, values, and feelings by which men experience their societies at various times. And certain of those ideas, values and feelings are available to us only in literature. (emphasis mine) To understand ideologies is to understand both the past and the present more deeply; and such understanding contributes to our liberation.²⁹

Marxists of the Eagleton School see literature as a mechanical reflection of the ideology of the prevailing class. Eagleton rejects the view that literature can distance itself from ideology. He believes that literature is a reworking of already existing ideological discourses. Various dialectical conceptions of the relationships between literature and ideology, have been developed. Such conceptions help to show the role of literature both as a product of society and a formative agent in social consciousness.

29. Eagleton, T. op.cit., p. viii.

Thus Ernst Fischer, in The Necessity of Art, says that the ideology of a society may cause its social development to lag behind.³⁰ An ideology can be outworn, inappropriate and deceptive. It is therefore the role of art to pierce through the clichés of ideology and to present a new truth which is in accordance with reality. Fischer's concept of literature then provides a greater understanding of the point and posture of novelists like Akin Işola in Ó le kú. The Yoruba ideology on marriage stipulates that marriage between a couple is possible only when the tripartite forces of love, parental support, and divine sanction are ensured. It is Adeleke's insistence on this ideology that prevents Ajani and Aşake's marriage. The end result is tragic. The point of Akin Işola's Ó le kú, is thus more than mere reflectionism. He is stating that such an ideology in modern Yoruba society, is inappropriate, outworn and dangerously deceptive.

Thus Akin Işola does not just attack that ideology, rather, he transcends it, piercing it through and thereby presenting a new truth which is in accordance with the reality

30. Fischer, E. 1963: The necessity of Art: A Marxist Approach. Penguin Books. p- 107

of modern Yoruba society. It is love, more than anything else that determines the marriage of Ajani and Şade afterwards. All Ernst Fischer is saying is that art should not just reflect ideology, it should challenge, reject, and oppose it if need be.

In his own work, The Sociology of Art, Jean Duvignaud, sees literature as a projection of the aspiration of the people for the future. He maintains that literature can bend people's imaginations to a potential acceptance of what will soon be actual. Through literature, people creatively make up their own future.³¹ Awoniyi's Aiyé kòótó can to a large extent be interpreted within the context of this concept. Aiyé kòótó is not merely a mirror of some of the evils of the post-colonial Yoruba society. It is a pointer to the role of the novelist as projector of the people's aspiration for the future. The future of the Yoruba society lies not in the break-neck pursuit of the white collar job, rather, its salvation abounds in a return to agriculture.

31. Duvignaud, J. 1972: The Sociology of Art.
Paladin. p-57

Christopher Caudwell, in Illusion and Reality, asserts that from the earliest times onward, literature has always set itself two tasks. First, is to keep the collective imagination of a society alive such that its members will be able to channel their energies to communal social construction. Secondly, to create the future of the society in imagination.³² To this end, Elechi Amadi's novel Sunset in Biafra, is a pertinent example of Caudwell's assertion.³³ In the novel, Amadi ensures that at every stage of the story, the attitude of the people of South Eastern State (now Rivers and Cross River States respectively) is unequivocally depicted. They are shown as being coerced into participation in the secessionist rebellion which culminated in the Nigerian Civil War. The Biafran leaders are depicted as employing all strategies and tactics to enforce the participation of all groups of people in the civil war, such that it seems everybody is in favour. As the war drags on, the community's collective imagination is not geared towards victory for the secessionists, rather the community's energies are channelled towards social reconstruction. Thus, immediately the rebellion is quelled,

32. Caudwell, C. op.cit., p.145.

33. Amadi, A. 1973: Sunset in Biafra Heinemann, London

the collective spirit of the people is easily reactivated into positive action for reconstruction and rehabilitation.

Amadi uses the novel to inculcate in the mind of the society, the need for urgency and prompt action. Rather than waste away in acrimonious recriminations and worthless moaning of loss, the society's mind is channelled towards team spirit and collectivism. Amadi's literary effort is thus a clear manifestation of Caudwell's point of view.

Thus it can be seen that Duvignaud, Fischer, and Caudwell, all see literature as a social fact which does more than merely reflect ideology. They see literature as an active force which is capable of challenging, rejecting, and transcending ideology. The main conception of Marxist literary sociology is that: the relationship of literature to society as a whole, can only be understood through its relationship to the ideology which prevails in that society.³⁴

The Marxist view of literary criticism helps the critic to focus on literature in all its totality - social, economic, historical and ideological. Marxist literary criticism has brought significant changes into our understanding of literature.

34. Barber. K. 1979 'Marxist Sociology of Literature', Sociology of Literature seminar, University of Ife, p.9.

Marx's famous statement that 'The philosophers have only interpreted the world in various ways; the point is to change it', has strongly influenced people's thought. To Marx, philosophy has been merely airy contemplation, it is time it engaged with the real world. Thus, many Marxist literary critical writings have provided useful guidelines for radical, vigorous and insightful interpretations of works of art. Marxist critics have been particularly innovative in their studies of the novel. For instance, studies by Lukacs uphold the view that the novel reflects reality, not by rendering its mere surface appearance, but by giving us 'a truer, more complete, more vivid and more dynamic reflection of reality.' To him reflection of reality is the framing of a mental structure transposed into words. It is a consciousness not merely of objects, but of human nature and social relationships. Through Marxist critical studies, we are given a deeper insight into the analysis of the novel. For from Marxist point of view, a novel has the capability of conducting a reader towards a more concrete common-sense apprehension of things. Marxist criticism shows that a literary work reflects not individual phenomena in

isolation, but the full process of life. Marxist literary sociology thus enables us to appreciate that, the writer does not impose an abstract order upon the world, but rather, he presents the reader with an image of the richness and complexity and subtlety of lived experience..

Wilson, E. (1972:2664), among others, has expressed the view that Marxist ideas and thought are often presented in a complex frame, difficult to comprehend, and intricate to apply. A cursory look at Eagleton (1976:6) tends to confirm this view. He says:

To understand King Lear, the Dunciad or Ulysses is therefore to do more than interpret their symbolism, study their literary history and add footnotes about sociological facts which enter into them: It is first of all to understand the complex, indirect relations between those works and the ideological worlds they inhabit... This is not an easy task, since ideology is never a simple reflection of a ruling class's ideas; on the contrary, it is a very complex phenomenon..³⁵

The fact that a task is complex does not mean it is insurmountable. Recent critical writings by various Marxists have dispelled this view, bringing out as stated earlier, innovative deep, and insightful interpretations of literature. Thus

35. Eagleton, T. op. cit. p. 6.

whatever negative comments against Marxist criticism, it is indisputably true that the Marxist literary sociology throws a great deal of light on the origins and social significance of works of art.

Formalism

Formalism which later came to be known as the "New criticism", arose as an attempt to reinstate the literary text as the only visible unit of criticism. According to the formalists, the main task of literary criticism lay not so much in studying literature, as its literariness. A work of art was seen as a self-enclosed system, and if sociological factors exercised any influence they did so only indirectly. Thus formalism aimed at establishing literature as an independent and autonomous cultural object. It rejected reflectionsism in its entirety and made the 'artistic device' the focus of its critical concern. To the formalists, each device existed within an "aesthetic system" where it performed specific functions. They say devices like plot, narrative technique etc. as existing independently of external factors. They placed emphasis on literature as a system, and organized or complex whole. They see a work of art as a totality in

which all the constituent parts added up to a coherent whole. To the formalists, criticism became an educational activity and a commitment to the assessment of distinct and discrete literary values in a work of art. Formalism thus involved an intensive critical activity and enquiry, it meant an elucidation of literary texts themselves, a profound scouring and searching so that no word set on paper went unanalysed, no symbol remained unturned.

The 'new criticism' was thus seen as a search for precision, for relevance and exactness. It was a search for essential body of standards in literature, not to be sought from external sources, but from its inherent nature as literature. The concern of the formalist critic was not the critics personal appreciative sensibility. It was not the writer's biography, his psychological, intellectual, social or historical background. The formalist critic's one primary object of critical attention was the text, the words on the page.

The importance of formalist criticism remains undoubted. Its importance lies in its emphasis on the specific aesthetic qualities of literature as well as its focus on the need to grasp literary works as integrated wholes. It took cognizance of the individual artistic competence of the writer. Perhaps

more importantly, formalism in a remarkable fashion shifts us away from the erroneous assumption that literature holds the mirror up to nature. It singularly disproved the hypothesis that there is a direct equivalence between a work of art and the life it imitates. It asserts that, a work of art is fiction, not fact.

In spite of its importance, its claims are not wholly convincing. Many of its convictions about the primacy of the text and the power of individual artistry within it, as well as the capacity of literature to exist as an autonomous, self-sustaining and a-historical whole, are from the point of view of sociology of literature, questionable. Whatever the artistic quality of a literary work, it is part and product of the society that produced it. The writer as well as the devices he uses are owned and influenced by the society. The work of art must have been produced at a particular stage in the historical process of the society. Where then lies its claim to literary autonomy? Finally the formalist literary criticism by its emphasis on the primacy of the text seems a covert suggestion that any species of creativity should not be criticized or confronted on terms other than those it prescribes itself. Such a suggestion is unacceptable to literary sociology because it is misleading.

Structuralism:

The basic concepts of structural analysis were developed by the Swiss linguist, Ferdinand de Saussure in the early part of this century. His Cours de linguistique generale, a posthumous publication was published in 1915. In this work which was translated into English in 1959 as Course in General Linguistics, Saussure developed a number of concepts that have influenced later structural thought. Among the concepts was his unusual definition of language which distinguishes three level of linguistic activity - "language", "langue" and "parole"³⁶ While "language" represents the entire human potential for speech both mental and physical, "langue" is the language system which we use to generate mutually intelligible discourse. What Saussure calls "parole" is our individual utterances.³⁷

Saussure drew important distinctions between synchronic and diachronic uses of language. He was concerned in developing what he called the science of semiology - the study of the life of signs within society, of which language was one part.³⁸

36. See Scholes, R. 1976: Structuralism in Literature Yale University Press, pp. 1-40

37. Ibid., p.16.

38. Laurensen and Swingewood, op.cit., p.61.

He introduced the need to study the system of communication, two aspects of a code which everyone uses. These he termed the "signifiers" and the signified. He also pointed out the importance of syntagmatic and paradigmatic relations in language use.³⁹ Saussure argued strongly for the synchronic use of language. His concepts have striking implications for literature. In its broadest sense, structuralism is a way of looking for reality not in individual things but in the relationships among them.⁴⁰

In the literary sense, structuralism views literature as a system in which the element under analysis forms numerous dynamic relations with other elements, with the other parts of the system, and every element has a meaning only in relation to the other parts. Wittgenstein's structuralist description of the world clearly illustrates this point. He says:

The world is the totality of facts not of things. And facts are states of affairs. In a state of affairs objects fit into one another like the links of a chain. In a state of affairs objects stand in a determinate way in which objects are connected in a state of affairs is the structure. The structure of a fact consists of the structure of state of affairs. The totality of the existing state of affairs is the world.⁴¹

39. Scholes, R. op.cit. p.25.

40. Ibid., p.4

41. Ibid., p.4

Wittgenstein's postulate is a structural view of the world. It is perfectly in consonance with structuralist thought. From the point of view of structuralism, the world is not an isolated entity, rather, it is made up of various components which link and interrelate in definite ways in such a way that it has a form, a structure, and like the link of a chain, one component is part of the whole, and the whole is referable to the parts.

This study of the interrelationship between the part and the whole is the basis of structuralism. Structuralism is not limited to literature. It is employed in areas of knowledge like philosophy, psychology, history, mathematics and the physical sciences. Thus in physics, the practice is to approach the explanation of a physical process by splitting the process into elements. The complicated processes are regarded as combinations of simple elementary processes; the wholes are seen as the sums of their parts.⁴²

It is on this premise that structuralist criticism is based. Before the literary critic can reach the core meaning of any given work he will have to establish a relationship

42. Ibid., p.5.

between the work and some system of ideas outside it. As Todorov rightly suggests, a structuralist interpretation of literature must justify itself by ^{bringing} / something external to the work, in a way that is at least different from that of the artist.⁴³ Structuralism seeks to establish a model of the system of literature itself as the external reference for the individual works it considers. By moving from the study of language to the study of literature, and seeking to define the principles of structuration that operate not only through the individual works but through the relationships among works over the whole field of literature, structuralism tries to establish for literary studies a basis that is as scientific as possible.

At the heart of structuralism is the idea of a system, a complete, self-regulating entity that adapts to new conditions by transforming its features while retaining its systematic structure. Every literary unit from the individual sentence to the whole order of words can be seen in relation to the concept of system. Thus a critic can look at individual works, literary genres, and the whole of literature as related

43. Ibid. p.8.

systems. The study of this systematic relationship in a work of literature is the pivot on which the structuralist concept gravitates.

But structuralism is not without its own weakness. Among its greatest weakness is its assumption of a systematic completeness. There is often the danger of regarding literary works as complete, closed and finished objects which can be studied without reference to other factors. Another problem is what Scholes has called "formalistic fallacy".⁴⁴ Formalistic fallacy is a lack of concern for the "meaning" or content of literary works. It is a charge which is often brought against any critical method which refuses to acknowledge the presence of a cultural world beyond the literary work and a cultural system beyond the literary system. The fallacy ascribed to structuralism does not lie in the fact that it concentrates on certain aspects of the materials being studied, it lies in the refusal to acknowledge that the materials being studied are not the only ingredients with which the literary work is composed. The fallacy further lies in its insistence that the materials in the text function

⁴⁴ Ibid., p.9.

in an entirely closed system without influence from the world beyond literature.

The emphasis on the synchronic aspect of the system is perhaps one of its greatest weaknesses. This emphasis often leads structuralist studies to concentration on minute detail at the expense of the system's development outside itself. Formalists have been accused of excessive one sidedness. Structuralism is similarly guilty of this flaw, for it ignores the importance of sociological environment of a literary work; an environment which is pre-eminently human and therefore historical. Its disregard for the diachronic aspect of language makes it a-historical. From the point of view of literary sociology, structuralism views a literary work as a basic material for research. It sees a work of art as a layered system of meanings which add up to an integrated whole and which is closely related, but not wholly determined by external factors. Such a stance is rather presumptuous and will only result in a half-baked interpretation of literature.

Genetic Structuralism

Marxist literary critics like Georg Lukács and Lucien Goldmann have written extensively on the structuralist approach. Indeed, it was the works of Lukács that gave Goldmann the inspiration to produce what can be called a 'revised version' of the structuralist concept. Goldmann has called his method "genetic structuralism".

By "genetic" he means historically-based, that is, literature as a social fact is to be understood in terms of its origin and development, in terms of its "genesis". By structuralism he means a holistic approach which sees social reality as a totality.⁴⁵ A work of art is composed of parts in a particular relationship to each other; at the same time, each work of art is itself a part of a larger whole. The parts can only be understood by referring to the whole, while to understand the whole, the parts have to be examined. This is because, knowledge does not advance in a straight line. Rather, it is a perpetual to and fro movement, from the whole to the parts and from the parts back to the whole again. In the course of this movement, the whole and the parts throw

⁴⁵ Barber, K. 1979: op.cit., p.10.

light upon one another. Thus to understand a work of literature, we have to put it in a wider context as part of a larger whole. Let us examine this excerpt for instance.

Èyin ará Ekó, àtèkun rẹ
 Mo yọ fún yin, mo sì yọ fara mi
 Ní ti p'Ájagunmólú tàjò bọ
 Aní Makólì Olore ilẹ wa⁴⁶

You people of Lagos and its environs
 I rejoice with you, I also rejoice with
 myself
 In that the conqueror has returned home
 Yea, Macaulay, the benefactor of our land.

This poem is made up of two phrases and two simple sentences. The first and last lines are phrases, while the second and third lines are simple sentences. The first line directly focuses attention on a particular audience. The repetition of yọ (rejoice) in the second line is a strong indication of triumph and exultation. The noun "Ajagunmólú" (conqueror) in the third line creates suspense in that the person referred to is unnamed, until the next line. Thus based on the text, the poem is a joyful expression of the triumphant and glorious return to Lagos of Macaulay the conqueror. This interpretation based purely on textual analysis is inadequate.

46. See Eko Akete November 15, 1925, p.10.

The assessment raises more questions. What, for instance is the rationale for the phrase-sentence-sentence-phrase structure of the poem? Why is Macaulay a conqueror? What war does he fight? Why does the poet call him benefactor of 'our land' rather than of Lagos? When was the poem written? What socio-economic and political factors influenced the poet? No study of the text alone, however detailed, can provide all the answers to these questions. At best, the grammatical rules and constructions serve as signals to probe into the critic's analytical thinking. To understand the poem much more fully, we have to put it in a wider context as part of a larger whole.

The poem was published on November 15, 1925, in commemoration of Herbert Macaulay's victory in the Apapa land case involving Chief Tijani Oluwa and the colonial administration in Lagos. Macaulay, Chief Oluwa's Secretary and spokesman, appealed to the Privy Council in London, in May 1920. As a result of his victory over the Privy Council appeal, Macaulay was given an unprecedented reception by the Lagos community. Thus to the poet, Macaulay's success is not a personal one. It was the victory of nationalism over the exploitative forces of foreign domination. Thus, when the poet refers to Macaulay as benefactor of 'our land' rather than of Lagos, it becomes

clearer that he is not being hyperbolic, rather, he is demonstrating the growing spirit of nationalism in the society. The poem then, is not just a joyous expression of socio-economic victory, it is a signification of the move towards political emancipation.

The phrase-sentence-sentence-phrase structure of the poem is purposive. The grammatical construction has a goal, as the poem is composed to be sung in a definite tune. It is composed in accordance with the christian hymn, "Abide with me, fast falls the evening tide". Thus the structure of the sentences and phrases, the choice of words, are intentionally designed to fulfil this purpose. The deliberate composition of the poem in conformity with a particular christian tune, does not only depict the religious background of the poet, it is indeed a convincing manifestation of the strong influence of christianity in the poet's society. This then confirms that an understanding of the 'genesis' of a work of art, a knowledge of the socio-economic and political history at the time of composition and an awareness of the author's life as a member of the society; and the relationship between all these and the structure of his work, would evince a profound and deeply meaningful interpretation of his work.

Thus from the point of view of genetic structuralism, the study of a work of literature, should not be limited to a mere analysis of text alone. A literary piece must be seen as part of the life of the man who wrote it and this life must be seen as part of the life of a whole community. Goldmann explains further:

An idea which he expresses or a book which he writes can acquire for their real meaning for us, and can be fully understood, only when they are seen as integral parts of his life and mode of behaviour. Moreover, it often happens that the mode of behaviour which enables us to understand a particular work is not that of the author himself but that of a whole social group; and, when the work with which we are concerned is of particular importance, this behaviour is that of a whole social class.⁴⁷

Goldmann's claim here is that the ideas and work of an author cannot be fully understood, if the critic remains on the level of what the artist wrote or what influenced him. Ideas are only a partial aspect of the man, the man in turn, is only an element in a 'whole', that is, the social group to which he belongs. This approach, Goldmann believes, will enable the critic to see the core of the meaning of a writer's work. He will be able to separate the essential aspects of a work

⁴⁷. Goldmann, L. 1964: The Hidden God Routledge and Kegan Paul, London, p.16.

of art from the inessential ones, since it is not every thing that the author writes that is equally important for an understanding of his work.

An important factor that is central to Goldmann's structuralism is the concept of "World Vision". Goldmann argues that every individual in society is a member of a number of different social groups. These may be the family occupational group, social class, and even an all-inclusive national group. Each of these groups tends towards a definite collective outlook, a collection of assumptions, beliefs, and attitudes, relating to the group's position in society. He divides the social groups into two main types. The first category, like families and occupational groups are often concerned with maintaining and improving particular positions within a specific social structure. To this category, the collective interests do not extend beyond the immediate concerns of their members - the maintenance of their group solidarity and achievement of their rights. The collective consciousness of this group, Goldmann calls "ideological consciousness", because "it has a restricted character specific to the groups, and because material interests, in more or less narrow sense of the term, often play by far, the preponderant

role in it.⁴⁸

The second category ^{is represented by} the social groups whose collective ideas are concerned with much more general issues. Such issues include ideas about human relationships, about nature, and society, ideals of humanity, and man's relations with God and ^{the} universe. It is the collective consciousness of this group that Goldmann gives the term "World Vision". To Goldmann the World Vision is far more important than the ideologies of the other social groups. Thus it appears that Goldmann differentiates between World Vision and ideology. World Vision is much more general and ambitious in its philosophical scope than "ideology" which is narrow and tied to specific group interests. World vision also tends to promote the solidarity of the class that holds it. Defining World vision, Goldmann says:

What I have called World Vision is a convenient term for the whole complex of ideas, aspirations, and feelings which link together the members of a social group (a group which in most cases assumes the existence of a social class) and which opposes them to members of other social groups.⁴⁹

⁴⁸. Barber, K. 1979. op.cit., p.13.

⁴⁹. Goldmann, L. 1964. op.cit., p.18.

sees World vision as transcending immediate class interests the struggle to formulate a view of man, nature, God and society. It is a binding force which gives a group of people awareness of their social identity. It is thus on the world vision that Goldman bases his interpretation of literature. This is because, while it is true that every individual belongs to many groups, the social class is by far the most important. World vision, the "collective consciousness" of the social class, has the most far-reaching applications.

Relating literature to the concept of World vision, Goldman believes that it is possible for 'great writers' to express the world vision of his social class in their works. Such expressions may be implicit. It is through the structure of the work of art that the world vision is revealed. To Goldman, the merit of a work of literature depends on the degree of coherence the writer achieves in his expression of the world vision. Goldman's use of the structuralist approach in the interpretation of The Hidden God, is detailed, analytical and brilliant. It is in many respects a useful contribution to Marxist theory of literature. Goldman's genetic structuralism clearly shows that sociology of literature is not simply a study of writers and their social

background, life style and norms. It is the linking of the literary text with particular socio-economic conditions in a coherent and meaningful way. Goldmann's method lays emphasis on the internal unity of a literary work. It attempts to identify certain structures within particular texts and relate them to concrete historical social conditions and structures. The emphasis through, is on the text as a whole and on history as a process. His method does not dissolve literature into a merely simple or complex study of the author and his surrounding environment.

Approach in this Study

Our brief survey of approaches to the study of sociology of literature, clearly indicates that no single approach provides a full and final clue to literary sociology. Each of the approaches has its strong and weak points. For instance, the positivistic approach which conceives literature merely as symptomatic, as mirrors of conditions within the society, and the artist as mere reflector of societal norms, is an inaccurate interpretation of the artist's literary endeavour. We believe that a work of art does not just reflect, its goal is to create a definite awareness in man, to make him recognize and change the world.

The literary artist recognises man's sense of incompleteness, thus literature attempts to fulfil man's striving towards a fullness of life, to a more comprehensible and just world, a world that makes sense.

The formalistic approach with its emphasis on the primacy of the literary text and the power of individual technique in it, aids our understanding of the internal structure of a work of literature. Yet, it tells us little about the society. It is thus a partial interpretation of the relevance of literature and society. The Marxist approach is a very useful one particularly in illuminating our knowledge about the social significance of art. Even Goldmann's Structuralist approach which takes cognizance of the internal analysis of text and the general analysis of social structure, in its interpretation of literature, is a progression of the Marxist literary approach. Thus it is the Marxist literary approach in its general sense that we shall adopt in this study. It is our belief that the approach will lead to a fuller and deeper understanding of the structure of the Yoruba novels under analysis. It will also enrich our knowledge of the Yoruba society that produced the novels. The approach will most probably be another contribution to the criticism of Yoruba Literature.

For the purpose of this study, three novelists have been selected. They are I.B. Thomas, D.O. Fagunwa and O. Okediji. The need for selection and choice becomes necessary when one realises that as at now (1987) sixty Yoruba novels by twenty-six novelists (past and present) have been identified.⁵⁰ A sociology of all the novels in a single work, is difficult, if not downright impossible.

The choice of the three novelists and the five novels in this study is based on the fact that they are significant in many respects. First, all the three novelists were born during a significant period of Yoruba history - the colonial era.⁵¹ But perhaps of greater significance is the fact that, the society in which they lived and grew up symbolizes three separate and distinct periods of Yoruba history - the traditional, the colonial and the post-independence.⁵² Whereas, Thomas, the oldest of them all lived and grew up in the colonial Lagos society, Fagunwa chose to look back to

50. An on-going research titled "Yoruba writers, past and present" by Bisi Ogunsina, is the basis of this claim.

51. I.B. Thomas, was born in 1896, Fagunwa in 1903 and Okediji in 1929.

52. For period of Yoruba history see Awe, B. 'Yoruba Women in history' in Gangan 1979, p.13.

the traditional Yoruba past. Though Okediji too grew up in the Yoruba traditional environment, the society that produced his writing is basically post-independence, particularly, the first Republic.

Like the three novelists chosen for this study, all the other Yoruba novelists past and present were born during the colonial period. But none of them possesses the significant peculiarities of the chosen three novelists. For instance, Isaac Thomas's only novel, Ìtàn Emi Sègilolá, is the first and only existing novels on the colonial Lagos society. Isaac Thomas is therefore indispensable in any meaningful literary sociology of the colonial Yoruba society from the earliest times. The age and cultural milieu of Fagunwa's first two novels, Ogbóju. Ode Ninú Igbó Irúnmalè and Igbó Olodumare remain significant, among other Yoruba novels. The two novels were written between 1935 and 1942.⁵³ Writing at the time he did, distinguished him as the only second world war time Yoruba novelist, a period replete with profound knowledge of Yoruba traditional life and society. Fagunwa's first two novels thus represent a distinct epoch, they are in essence, irreplaceable in our literary understanding of the Yoruba traditional society.

53. J.O. Awodiran in his Book Fagunwa di Ologbe pp:5-60 states that Ogbojuode Ninu Igbo Irunmale was written in 1935. Bamgbose, A. (1974) puts the writing of Igbo Olodumare at 1942.

Apart from the post-independence historical background of Okediji's writing, many other factors contribute to his uniqueness as a novelist. His career as school master and political activist, the state of political instability in Yorubaland and the throes of the civil war that pervaded the period when he wrote his first two novels, Àjà ló lẹrù and Agbàlagbà Akàn, single him out among other Yoruba novelists.

Thus each of the novelists chosen for this study, more than any others, represents a distinct and significant social, political and historical period. Each period has a definite influence on the society of the novelists. Our study of these novelists would portray the Yoruba society during three notable periods of Yoruba history - the colonial, the traditional, and the post-independence. Furthermore, it will depict the individual novelist's reaction to, and outlook on, the society of those periods. It is hoped that this would be a useful contribution to our knowledge of the relationship between the novel and the society in the Yoruba context.

CHAPTER TWO

THOMAS AND THE COLONIAL LAGOS SOCIETY:
A STUDY OF ITAN EMI SEGILOLA

Structure of the Society

Urbanism, commercialism and capitalism, it has been argued are crucial factors for the growth of the novel.¹ In the case of Europe and America where the rise of the novel coincided with the rise of capitalism, this is most probably true. But to what extent is this true in the Yoruba context? Lagos is the origin of the first Yoruba novel.² To what extent have urbanism and commercialism affected the rise of the Yoruba novel? What kind of society produced the first Yoruba novel?

The first inhabitants of the area now known as Lagos were the Awori.³ These were a subgroup of the Yoruba people who migrated from their original home, Ile-Ife, the cultural homeland of the Yoruba. The first settlement was located on the mainland around Ebute meta and later moved to Ido Island. These original "settlers were soon joined by peoples from

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1. Laurenson, D and Swingewood, A. op.cit., p.202.
 2. Ogunsina, J.A. 1976: The Development of the Yoruba Novel M.Phil. Thesis, p.28
 3. See Baker, P.H. 1970 Urbanization and Political Change: A study of the Politics of Lagos. Doctoral Thesis, University of Lagos.

neighbouring provinces. Prominent among these were the Ijebu and Egbas who made Lagos their centre of trade. In order to secure greater protection from civil unrest which was rampant in the hinterland, the settlers moved to the Island which today constitutes the centre of the city. Olofin the head of the original inhabitants established his village at the western corner known as Isale Eko. Olofin distributed land among sixteen of his children, giving them 'white caps' as insignia of their status. This is the root of the special class of headmen who are today known as the Idejo or "white cap chiefs". It is interesting to note that the descendants of the original Awori settlers today form the heart of the traditional quarter of the city and the core of the urban population. As a result of conquest by Benin, Lagos became a vassal to the Oba of Benin, paying tribute to the Benin Empire for two centuries.⁴ The contact with Benin made the population to become a mixture of Yoruba and Edo with influences from other ethnic groups. The community was basically agrarian consisting of farmers and fishermen. The contact with the Portuguese and the subsequent introduction of slave trade

4. Ibid., p.34.

brought some economic changes. By the early nineteenth century, this trade had had a drastic influence on the character of Lagos, transforming it from a small fishing and farming village to a remarkable commercial centre for the purchase and sale of slaves.⁵ Lagosians acted as the middlemen in the inhuman transaction, buying the slaves from the hinterland tribes and selling them to the Europeans. The Europeans in turn exchanged with textiles, firearms, liquor, knives, cutlasses, hardware, bars of iron, copper and brass etc.

Culturally, of all the Yoruba kingdoms, Lagos has always been the most remote from the mainstream of traditional Yoruba culture. Yet one of the sacred institutions which has survived through the centuries is that of kingship. The religious ideas and ceremonial elements associated with it have been of great cultural value. By the 1840s, apart from his relations with other states, or kingdoms, the Oba of Lagos held a position of supreme power within the town. He had considerable latitude in exercising his royal prerogatives. He could levy fines, sentence a defendant to imprisonment, sell him into slavery, or in serious cases inflict capital

5. Ibid., p.67.

punishment. Persons who immigrated from the interior could also be brought before him for criminal offences, and even after the emigrants had established their own courts, the Oba retained final jurisdiction in disputes involving indigenous Lagosians.⁶

In commercial ventures, the Oba had power to grant trading concessions and protection to merchant communities - the family, the compound, and the town as a whole. The individual was important only in so far as he was a member of the group, and had certain roles and duties to fulfil with regard to his immediate community. The family was a much larger unit, referring to a whole household, often including grandparents, cousins as well as distant relations. The family in this larger sense was the primary legal, social and economic unit under the control of the family head. The family was self-supporting, producing most of the food and clothing in the home, and goods sent to the market for sale were often products of the domestic industry. Farming, fishing, and petty trading were the major occupations. Then came 1851, the year of British intervention in the affairs of Lagos.

6 *ibid* P. 75

The decade which opened with the intervention of the British in Lagos in 1851 and closed with the annexation of Lagos in 1861 has been described as a time of transition from independence to colonial rule.⁷ With the intrusion of the British, the traditional political system of Lagos changed radically. Barely ten years after the conquest of Lagos by the British, the political power and prestige of the traditional rulers of Lagos had collapsed. The Oba no longer had a firm grip on the government of his people. His sources of income had been drastically reduced by the British. By the 1920s, the social and political status of the Oba had diminished considerably. For instance, Oyekan I, Dosumu's successor lived on a paltry sum of £300 per annum.⁸ No longer was he to be called the Oba of Lagos. Rather, he was simply known as Head of the "House of Docemo" and Eşugbayi, Eleko, who reigned after Oyekan I, was simply referred to as "The Eleko".

7. Smith, R. 1974: 'The Lagos consulate, 1851-1861': An outline in Journal of African History Vol. 15, No. 3, pp. 393-416.

8. Baker, H. 1970: op.cit., p. 400

The policy of "Direct Rule" under which Lagos was ruled gave no room for native authorities, or native courts, as was the practice in other parts of British Africa. The entire Lagos colony was placed under the jurisdiction of the Nigerian Supreme Court with executive functions carried out by the District officers acting in lieu of native authorities. Baker described the situation vividly:

Throughout most of the remaining years of the colonial period, the government regarded Lagos Chiefs as political, nonentities, having the official status of private persons in the same way as any other citizens of the town. Recognition was extended to Lagos Chiefs only as lineage or family heads, an "act of courtesy" which it was repeatedly pointed out, had no political significance. Economically, traditional authorities had been reduced to the status of "beggar Chiefs" with no independent income, they relied upon voluntary gifts and fees from followers in the Old Town to supplement their meagre allowance that was predictably suspended whenever the Chiefs became involved in local disputes to the displeasure of the government.⁹

Thus the British intrusion during the second half of the nineteenth century could be seen as a powerful wind of change which had a tremendous impact on the cultural, social and

9. Ibid., p. 402.

political life of the traditional Lagos society.

By 1852, missionaries began to arrive in Lagos; first to arrive were the Anglican Church Missionary Society. With the traders and missionaries came the repatriates, and by 1853, the Sierra Leonians were arriving by every mail. As a result of the changing economic and demographic patterns during the second half of the nineteenth century, Lagos began to emerge as a thriving community. One conspicuous effect of this situation was the production of a multi-cultural society. By 1901, Lagos had become a heterogeneous town of over 40,000 inhabitants - Awori, Edo, Egba, Saro, Imaro and various Europeans as well as other scattered ethnic groups, distributed in relatively segregated districts. Baker, (1970), observed that it was not only the pace and nature of immigration that gave the town a plural character; the emerging patterns of residence, social stratification, and contrasting life-styles in the community also added diversity.¹⁰ By 1886, when the political position of Lagos rose from that of a settlement to that of a colony, it consisted of four distinct sub-communities: the traditional old town of Ìsàlẹ̀ Èkó, Saro Town, the Imaro

10. Baker, H. 1970: op. cit., p.65.

district and the European Section. A brief discussion on each of these communities, will be illuminating.

The old town, popularly known as Isale Eko was situated in the North Western corner of the Island. In the early colonial period, it was larger than the other three districts put together. According to the 1859 estimate, it was five miles in circumference with a population of 30,000 inhabitants.¹¹ Despite the imposition of colonial rule, Isale Eko remained a traditional town dominated by indigenous inhabitants who owned land in the heart of the city. They constituted a landed lower class. They were mostly muslims, comparatively the least progressive, and antipathetic to mission education. They were poorly represented in the schools that were fast growing. They were also relatively untouched by the growing prosperity and commercialization introduced by legitimate trade.

Saro Town, known and referred to as Olowogbowo, situated opposite Isale Eko on the southwestern corner of the island. Olowogbowo was the second major district in Lagos. The name 'Saro Town' indicates the settlement of repatriate from

11. Ibid., p.67.

Sierra Leone. Nearly all the Saro immigrants lived there. The Saro community produced the first professional and intellectual elite of Lagos. Saro Town was a virtually autonomous settlement, it had its own schools, church, police force, jail and court house. The Saro competed with the European merchants in commerce and industry. They were interpreters and administrative assistants to the colonial government, serving as arbitrators between the colonial government and the local chiefs. Even though they were fully conscious of their Yoruba origin, they were socially aloof from the indigenous community and rejected native authority. They were fond of emulating English behaviour and mannerisms. Many Saro children attended British Universities, thus becoming the first generation of African lawyers, doctors, surveyors and journalists in Lagos. Among both Africans and Europeans, the Lagos Saro were regarded as the elite of the society, sophisticated, wealthy and possessing power and prestige.

The Brazilian quarter known as Opopo Imaro, was the third district of the town. It was situated away from the swamps and stood in the centre of the Island around Campos square. It was also called Opopo Aguda. Just as the Saro absorbed many of the cultural traits of their English liberators, so the Imaro repatriates assimilated many of the cultural

characteristics of their captors. Thus they bore Portuguese names, spoke Portuguese language and embraced catholicism. Although as numerous as the Saro, the Imaro were less wealthy and less politically active. It was probably for this reason that they were closer and more acceptable to the indigenous elements. Having arrived in Lagos in straitened circumstances, most of the Imaro began to practise the crafts they had learnt in captivity. These included masonry, carpentry, cabinet making, bricklaying, tailoring, smithing etc. They were in essence, the middle class artisans of Lagos.

The fourth major group in the society, was the European community. It was a heterogenous community and the least in numerical strength as the population was less than one percent of the entire Lagos. The 1911 census revealed a total population of four hundred and eighty-four British, twenty-one French and seventy-three Germans. By 1921, there were a total of nine hundred and ninety-two British, twenty-six French and only three Germans. But despite their meagre numerical strength, they perhaps had the greatest impact on the whole town. They were in three categories - administrators, traders and missionaries. Nearly half of the European were British administrators. Unlike the indigenous and emigrant groups,

the Europeans did not cluster in a single cohesive community, rather, they spread from one end of the Island to the other. Government residential quarters were built for administrators along the Marina and around the race course at the eastern end of the Island. In the twentieth century, European residential settlements were built at Ikoyi. Before this time, most of the administrator's quarters remained close to the natives and the emigrants. Most of the European traders lived above their warehouses along the Marina, while the missionaries lived as close as possible among their congregation.

The European community constituted the upper ruling class and contributed largely to the socio-economic changes that pervaded the society. By the 1870s, Lagos had started to enjoy a prosperous economy, with a high rate of export crops like palm produce, rubber, timber, cotton, coffee, cocoa and maize. Imports included textiles, spirits, tobacco, building materials, salt and other provisions. So bouyant was the economy that by 1896, the ^{year} I.B. Thomas, the author of the first Yoruba novel was born, Lagos was described as an 'ideal colony, self-supporting and self-protecting.'¹²

12. Mabogunje, L. 1961: Lagos, A Study in Urban Geography. Doctoral thesis, p.92.

Various colonial heads introduced diversified physical innovations, into the Lagos metropolis.

The Glover regime (1864-1872), among other things, saw the expansion of the Marina to a sixty-foot wide Broad Street, construction of street lamps, and properly dug wells. Glover encouraged the building of wharves and warehouses to cope with the increasing commerce. Governor Moloney spearheaded and encouraged the planting of trees to give the city a more attractive look. The construction of the railway line encouraged the growth of trade with the hinterland. It also created more job opportunities for various job seekers.

The development of formal education which had begun in the 1850s also greatly influenced the tremendous socio-economic changes in the society. By 1894, there were already thirty-two mission schools in Lagos alone. By 1910, there were one hundred and twenty schools in the Yoruba mission area and by 1930, seventeen of the twenty-six post primary institutions in Nigeria were in Lagos and the West.¹³ The various social changes led to an unprecedented influx of immigrants into

13. Eades, J.S. 1980: Yoruba Today. Cambridge University Press, p.114.

Lagos leading to a remarkable expansion of the urban society.

The population record of Lagos 1901-1931 bears credence to this.¹⁴

POPULATION GROWTH OF LAGOS 1901-1931

Year	Total Population	Intercensal Increase or Decrease	
		Number	Percent
1901	41,847	9,339	29
1911	73,788	31,919	76
1921	99,690	25,924	35
1931	126,108	26,318	27

As shown in the table, the Lagos society witnessed a vigorous population growth between 1920 and 1930 when I.B. Thomas wrote the first Yoruba novel. The tremendous population increase had by Thomas's time changed the society's outlook. It had become cosmopolitan and multicultural. It possessed a virile and flourishing economy, promising professionalism and progressive elitism.

¹⁴. Baker, H. 1970: op. cit., p.62.

These changes in the economic and political order meant an innovation in the structure of the society. It gave room to a new social order - capitalism. The increase in the need for manpower in the administrative and commercial sectors gave rise to salaried posts. Illiterate and half-educated people were appointed as artisans and messengers. These groups of people constituted the proletariat. The economic situation also created another category - teachers, clerks and small scale traders - who constituted the middle class. There were also the highly educated class, the elite, top level businessmen and administrators (mainly Europeans) who constituted the upper and ruling class in the society.

In the area of religion, before the British incursion, the majority of the people were traditional worshippers and muslims. But with the advent of christianity, many became converted. It is paradoxical that even though the majority of the population were traditional worshippers and muslims, the general atmosphere of Lagos society in the later nineteenth and early twentieth centuries seemed almost thoroughly christian. Its administrative government was British and thus christian.¹⁵ Its education was christian oriented,

15. Coleman, J.S. 1958: op. cit., p.108.

hence many of the educated elite were christians. It was the fashion of the times to be a christian. Thus among many of the elite, christian thoughts, christian ideals, christian values, christian concepts, and ideologies were common.

As has been stated above, this change in the cultural and political life of the society, led to a new economic system - capitalism. The capitalist economy brought tremendous changes into the structure of the society. Capitalism made the society extremely money-conscious. A system of personal cash wages whereby each individual earned money for himself gradually evolved. This created a strong tendency towards self interest and individualism. These features of the new economic order went a long way in the weakening of the traditional bonds between kith and kin and in establishing every individual as a separate economic entity in society, whose loyalty is to himself.

One particularly noticeable effect of the new socio-economic system was the prevalence of a greater drive towards monetary gain and material acquisition among all the classes in the society. A new vision was growing in the society. ^{individualism} Communal unity and loyalty gradually began to give way to/ and

selfishness. Pre-colonial Lagos society was in transition, witnessing the incursion of a new economic principle - materialism. I.B. Thomas, was the first Yoruba novelist to react to this new economic order. It was this reaction that gave birth to his first and only novel, Itan Emi Segilola. Who was this I.B. Thomas?

I.B. Thomas: A Biographical Sketch

Isaac Babalola Thomas was born in Lagos on Sunday, 1st March, 1896. He was the first child of Mr. Obediah A. Thomas and Madam Christianah Obakeye Thomas. He was educated at the Christ Church School, Faji, now known as Christ Church Cathedral School, Lagos. First employed as a teacher in the same school, he later became its headmaster from 1919-1921. He became headmaster of African Bethel School, Lagos from 1922-1925. It was in this School that he met Miss Josephine Bamigbola Akanke, whom he married in 1925. He resigned his teaching appointment and joined the Lever Stores as cashier from 1926 to 1927.

Isaac Thomas's interest in literary writing started during his early life as a school teacher. As early as 1919, he had been a regular contributor of interesting Yoruba tales in the bilingual newspaper In Leisure Hours, (Nigbà tí Ọwo bá dilẹ). This interest was motivated by his pupils' admiration

for his story telling class. Some of the stories which he wrote in the newspaper were reproductions in Yoruba of popular English tales. Among these was "Itan Alli Baba ati awon Ogoji Oloṣa". (The story of Alli Baba and the forty thieves).

His useful contributions in the other subsequent newspapers, Èkó Àkéte and Elétí Ofe earned him the commendation, "the trusted correspondent of Èkó Àkéte and Elétí Ofe".¹⁶

He composed poems in memory of eminent Nigerians like the late Revd. J.S. Fanimokun, Principal of C.M.S. Grammar School, Lagos, who died on March 5, 1920. His beautiful acrostic in memory of Revd. S.M. Abiodun of the Christ Church Cathedral appeared in May 28th, 1924 issue of Elétí Ofe. As a result of his constant writings in these Yoruba newspapers, Isaac Thomas soon became a popular story writer, a notable poet and a distinguished commentator on social, political and religious affairs.

Isaac Thomas's increasing interest in journalism led him to resign his job as a cashier with the Lever Stores, and he assumed the post of editor of a new Yoruba newspaper Èkó Igbèhin, on July 15, 1927. He suddenly announced his

16. The Yoruba News June 10, 1924, p.10.

resignation as editor of Èkó Igbèhin in the November 25th issue of the paper, and declared his intention to launch a Yoruba newspaper of his own. Accordingly, a new Yoruba newspaper owned and edited by Mr. I.B. Thomas came out under the title, Akéde Èkó (Lagos Herald) on Saturday, 3rd January, 1928. It thenceforth came out regularly and it had a wide circulation in Nigeria. So extensive was its circulation and popularity that it was described in 1953 as "the oldest and the most popular newspaper printed and published in Lagos and circulated in all nooks and corners in Nigeria".¹⁷ In 1929, Isaac Thomas, launched another newspaper, the Nigerian Evening News. He thus became the editor and founder of "the first evening newspaper ever published in West Africa".¹⁸

I.B. Thomas was a great patriot. He demonstrated his nationalist spirit in many ways. For instance, he was a strong advocate of the use of the Yoruba language as a medium of instruction in the primary school. On many occasions, he called for the use of the Yoruba language in writing. In the

17. I am grateful to Mr. Bolaji Thomas, the author's son who made available to me some of his father's personal papers from which I got this information.

18. See The Nigerian Evening News. June 1, 1929.

local politics of Lagos in the 1920s, Isaac Thomas distinguished himself as a strong supporter of Prince Eşugbayi, the deposed Oba of Lagos, during the latter's legal tussle with the Governor, in Lagos. Isaac Thomas also demonstrated his intense love and admiration for Mr. Herbert Macaulay, the Nigerian political stalwart of the 1930s and the 1940s.

Isaac Thomas was a staunch, conscientious, and dutiful christian. He had implicit confidence in God and a powerful belief in the efficacy of prayer. This strong christian background explains why his first Yoruba book was a "magic-like" prayer book, titled, Olódùmarè. Ìwé Àdúrà Ajébidán. The book came out early in 1927 and sold so fast that a second edition had to be published in October the same year. In 1928, he embarked on the serialization of a realistic story titled, "Ìtàn Emi Sẹgilọla Èlẹyinjúẹgẹ in his Akéde Èkó newspaper. The story appeared regularly for about two years before its publication in book form in July, 1930. Its earlier appearance in the newspaper made the novel instantly popular, giving it a ready audience among many Yoruba educated elite. He also published other interesting and instructive pamphlets mostly in both English and Yoruba languages. The most notable of these was, The Life History of Herbert Macaulay.

I.B. Thomas travelled extensively to many parts of Nigeria in the interest of his Akede Eko newspaper. In appreciation of his many contributions to his country's progress, particularly in the field of journalism and literature, he was awarded the coronation medal for "Public Service in 1953".¹⁹ And in recognition of his role in the development of the Nigerian press, he was unanimously chosen to represent Nigerian press at the Nigerian constitutional conference in London in 1957. He died four years later on August 25, 1961, survived by his wife and three children.

The Novel and the Society

Ìtàn Emi Segilọla is the story of Sẹgilọla Abẹkẹ the protagonist of the novel. She was born in Lagos on September 9, 1882. She is the last of her mother's six children. She is the only surviving child of her parents, for all the others die in infancy. Sẹgilọla is an embodiment of elegance and loveliness. She is greatly loved by her parents, and admired by many men in Lagos. Despite the fact that Sẹgilọla receives a loving care from her parents, she is never indulged.

19. Information from the author's personal papers.

Her elegant beauty wins her the epithet *Ēleyinjuegē* (the one with delicate eye balls). But her loving beauty is also the major cause of her problem. She becomes the darling of many men, a situation that leads to her expulsion from school.

Greatly influenced by her friend *Ayōka*, *Sēgilōla* flouts all parental instructions. She cherishes the company of men and secretly gets involved in amorous dealings with them.

Sēgilōla is a shrewd, tactful, and crafty young girl. These characteristics are used to a great advantage in receiving precious material gifts from men. As her propensity for greed and graft increases, she employs herbal means to assist her in her bargains. So successful is she that she instantly becomes popular with men in highly placed positions.

In her bid to secure herbal assistance, she loses her maiden-head to a herbalist, this leads her to shame and ignominy on her bridal night. She gradually becomes a prostitute. Her matrimonial life was a failure, as it ends in sterility and divorce. *Sēgilōla* forsake and neglects her ageing mother. *Sēgilōla*'s failure in marriage and in life is a major cause of her mother's untimely and sorrowful death. *Sēgilōla* gets more and more involved in indiscriminate sexual dealings with men, a practice that leads her into an incurable

disease. She spends and gets spent in her effort to survive. At forty-eight her grandeur and elegance have diminished. Forsaken and neglected by all her admirers, Sẹgilọla Ẹleyinjuege ends up a social destitute, wallowing in pain, sorrow and regret.

This briefly is the story of Itan Emi Sẹgilọla, the first Yoruba novel which dominated the Yoruba literary scene for many years. It enjoyed a great popularity and wide readership. The novel became the talk of the town and a proud possession of many Yoruba literates. Indeed, it was so well received that non-Yoruba speakers prevailed on its author to translate the novel into the English language for the benefit of the English-speaking audience. This he did in 1931.²⁰ Why did the novel become a people's favourite in the 1930s? Why did it become an invaluable reference point for preachers, teachers and parents for years?

At the time of its publication, Itan Emi Segilọla was in certain respects considered a new form of writing in Yoruba. In content, it was different from many of the Yoruba works that preceded it. For instance, it was unlike Lijadu's Ifá and

20. From January 1931, the author started the serialization of the English edition in Akede Eko. See Akede Eko, January, 1931.

Orúnmilà which contained interesting stories mainly drawn from Ifa literary corpus, with a view to drawing parallels between the traditional worship of Ifa and the new religion, christianity. It differs from the literary writings of A.K. Ajişafẹ, which were more of a homily than a novel.²¹ It is different from the traditional folktales which deal with various natural and supernatural characters, incidents and settings. Itan Emi Sẹgilọla is a realistic portrayal of man in society. This new form of writing suggests in many ways, a kind of advancement on the existing literary tradition.

Its newness lies not so much in adopting the written form as in its hitherto new technique - the epistolary style. This among others, is the first proof of its imported form. The art of letter writing was a new form of communication among the Yoruba in the early decades of the twentieth century. But the surprise becomes more heightened when the book is seen to contain the personal secrets of an individual. Since such a technique has had no parallel in Yoruba literary tradition. Indeed the publication of Thomas's Itàn Emi Sẹgilọla in 1930 ushered in a new type of writing which may

21. For more details on Ajişafẹ's writing, see Ogunsina, J.A. op. cit., pp. 19-20.

be indicative of a new form of social consciousness. The new species of writing was realism, for it represented a far more realistic depiction of social life. It was characterised by peculiar innovations and techniques not found in the earlier writings; the emphasis on the particularity of experience, place, and time, the realistic naming of characters and a deeper psychological awareness of human motivations. His novel depicts man's social and inner life more realistically than ever before. It was the first novel that evinces the material values of an urban commercial society.

Another aspect of the newness is the choice of the protagonist. Why is the protagonist a woman and not a man? Is Thomas's choice of the protagonist a direct influence of the English literary tradition as found in Richardson's Pamela and Clarissa or Daniel Defoe's Moll Flanders?²²

Was Thomas influenced by the Yoruba oral tradition, since instances are not uncommon of female protagonists in the folktales? Similarly, could it be said that the inspiration in the social history arose from Thomas's knowledge of some prominent women /

22. Moll Flanders is a tale of thievery, prostitution and worldly success. Its protagonist was a successful whore.

of Lagos? After all, 'Opó-Olú and Tinubu, both beautiful and wealthy women, were popular figures in the Lagos society of the mid-nineteenth century.²³ Is it due to the fact that Thomas simply prefers a theme that gravitates around a woman? We may never arrive at a conclusive answer. But whatever influenced Thomas's choice, his choice of protagonist was considered innovative. It clearly signifies the close relation between the development of the novel and the freedom of woman. Thus, it produced an instantaneous fascination for his readers.

Another noteworthy factor that made Ìtàn Emi Sẹgilọla a delight to the society in the 1930s was its uniqueness. This uniqueness lies in the fact that it was the first novel in the Yoruba language. The spontaneous reception accorded its arrival has an historical background. From the last decades of the nineteenth century, a growing need for written literature in the "native" language had been gaining prominence. In spite of the conspicuous advantages of European education, some of the educated elite condemned the pre-eminent status of English language and literature in the society.

23. See J.B. Losi 1914: The History of Lagos, African Education Press, Lagos, pp. 79-80.

They therefore made passionate calls for the production of "native literature" in the "native language". One of such calls was contained in a publication from "Veritas" titled "Native Literature and the Native Language". He wrote:

But there is an evil for nothing else can I designate it, which as a little fire, should it be allowed to kindle to a flame, would render the rise of Africa one big sham... This is the habit of disregarding and ignoring and in some cases, totally crying down our native language. That a country should rise with a literature entirely foreign almost assume to me; the form of an impossibility.²⁴

To the progressive elements among the educated elite in the society, Veritas' letter represents the voice of reason. Veritas' pretension characterizes the growing fire of nationalism in the society. The nationalists were strong advocates of the fact that the black race is not inferior to any other race in the world. Thus the publication of Ìtàn Emi Sẹgilọla constitutes a significant literary achievement, and a prompt response to the hopes and aspirations of the Yoruba educated elite.

24. The excerpt which appeared in the Lagos Observer is quoted from Echeruo, M. 1977, op. cit. pp. 114-116.

Thomas and his Society

The society of Thomas's novel is the elitist, commercial Lagos of the 1920s. The characteristic note of the period was change - political, social, cultural and economic. But Thomas's concern is not with societal change in all its totality. His focus is the growing capitalist tendency and its effect on the society. Flourishing trade and increased commercial transactions are among the features of the changing society. The varying effects of the changes are Thomas's main concern. His most important literary device in the novel is characterization. It is characterization, more than anything else, that he employs to depict the structure of the society. His characters illustrate the three broad divisions of the social structure. These are the illiterate low class workers, the middle class clerics, merchants, and lucrative merchants, and the land-owning magnates, who constitute the upper class. Segilola, the protagonist hardly belongs to a definite group. She is used as a reflector of the various social strata of the society. Thomas employs the device of prominence in his creation of Segilola. She is the central figure and the focus of attention. She stands out in full light from a world of other human beings in the novel. Her motivation and history are most fully

lished. She conflicts and changes as the story progresses. She is the one that engages our responses more fully and fully. She is the vehicle by which the most interesting questions are raised. More than any other, she evokes our scorn, sympathy, as well as our revulsion. She is indeed the incarnation of the moral vision and message of the novel. It is the life history of this protagonist that the novel purports to narrate. Thus the plot of the novel has two main divisions. The first part portrays Segilola's premarital life, while the second is an exposure of her post-marital life. The two parts are neatly woven such that the first smoothly leads into the other. The novel's structure has a purposive construct. It purports to be a true story rather than a fictional tale. This purport is further strengthened by the autobiographical style which gives the story a greater capacity for authenticity. The novel is presented as a genuine story of woe, with a pungent language. Thomas employs pathos in a captivating manner to draw attention on the protagonist from the onset. The reader's mind is filled with feelings of apprehension, pity and commiseration. The device of pathos is again given certain prominence.

It occurs at the beginning, and it re-echoes at significant points of the novel, to its conclusion. For instance, after giving a brief account of her early life in the opening chapter, Sęgilọla bursts into remorseful sobbings:

O ęe! igi dá lára emi Sęgilọla
 Ẹleyinjuęęę, lẹrọ temi tó kọjá ọkún
 Ọrọ tẹmi tó kọja arò didá, ọrọ tẹmi
 tó kọjá ọsẹ pipa níwọyí ọjọ aiyé mi (p.6)

What a great pity on me Sęgilọla
 Ẹleyinjuęęę, my own case surpasses
 weeping; my situation is beyond wailing;
 my condition transcends hissing at this
 period of my life.

The use of language here arouses instant sympathy. The semantic repetition of O ęé! (What a pity!) and Igi dá (Alas!) in the first line is important. These two short sentences are identical in meaning, yet, they produce certain escalating effect. Their co-occurrence clearly suggests situation of mounting sorrow and pain of heart. The structural repetition of "ọrọ temi tó kọjá" (my case that is beyond) in the succeeding lines is suggestive of an insoluble problematic situation. The juxtaposition of semantically

related words, ẹkún (tears) arò (sob) and òşé (hissing) is effective, for it clearly expresses a state of poignant grief. This abundant use of repetition not only makes the protagonist's utterances touching, it also produces a striking effect. As the story progresses, the prominence in the use of pathos suggests some emphasis. In effect, ^{it} has a thematic significance on the entire novel. From the onset, it raises a lot of questions on the protagonist. Who is she? What is the cause of her sorrow? How was she drawn into the pathetic situation? Of what significance are these regretful utterances to our understanding of the novel and the society?

On the surface, Segilola's misfortune is as a result of her obstinacy to parental injunctions. She clearly declares this:

Iyá mi kọ mi, emi ni kò gba ẹkọ;
 Iyá mi dùnà tó fún mi lati lè ri
 pé mo ni ibujokò rere nínú ilé ọkọ
 kan laiyé mi, şùgbón emi funra mi
 ni mo ba ọnà mi jẹ mọ ara mi lówọ...
 emi ni a alaigboràn ọmọ lati ode ọrun
 mi wá si aiyé. (p.7)

My mother taught me, it is I who refused instructions; my mother fought enough to ensure that I have a comfortable matrimonial home with a single husband, but it is I myself, that deliberately spoilt my own course in life... I am the disobedient child right from heaven to this world.

But how does Sęgilqla's wilful disobedience relate with the outside world of the home? How does her domestic affair have relevance with the society? Sęgilqla's first experience with her wider community is her primary and secondary education. But the author cuts off this link as Sęgilqla becomes a moral failure and is expelled from school.

A greater and perhaps stronger link with the wider society which the author adopts, is that of marriage. Thomas probably realises the basic functions of marriage as a means adopted by human society to regulate the relationship between the two sexes; as well as the mechanism by means of which the relations of a child to the community is determined. To the Yoruba mind, marriage is a remarkable achievement. It is a means of ensuring the continuity of human existence. The Yoruba traditional ideology stressed above all else premarital chastity and the absolute fidelity of the wife to the husband. This was to a great extent the predominant attitude during Thomas's period of writing, a woman's chastity was of utmost

importance as it was considered an integral aspect of her matrimonial success. A wife's chastity guarantees her a certain dignity and respectability immediately after the bridal night. It is this ideology that Thomas employs to link Səgilqola with the society.

Səgilqola is created in a way that would bring to focus the changing socio-economic conditions in the urban commercial Lagos society. First is Səgilqola's character - sharp, shrewd and wilful; but nevertheless she possesses a fascinating combination of body constitution which greatly recommends women to men. She is physically appealing, a charming figure, young, healthy, fresh, angelic and as she herself declares, one of the most beautiful women ever created. (p.6). With such attributes, Səgilqola is naturally easily exposed to men of various classes in the society. Her ejection from school is the initial cause of her exposure to public life. But her mother's vehement insistence on her getting married constitutes the motor force of the whole novel. The plot hinges on her bid to satisfy her mother's urge, the search for a husband is a crucial motivating factor for action. The bid to get attached to a life-partner exposes Səgilqola to a wide range of socio-economic experiences. It is the variety of experiences of Səgilqola that Thomas uses to portray a glaring

picture of the Lagos society of his time. Sęgilęla's frequent contacts with various people is Thomas's device to evince the social structure of the society.

There are members of the lower class made up of fishermen and crewmen and petty traders, each going about his business in a free atmosphere. Then there are as the story unfolds, shop keepers, clerical assistants engaged in flourishing trade and commercial activities in the society; these constitute the middle class. Sęgilęla's contacts reveal the business magnates, rich landlords, the educated elite made up of doctors, lawyers and engineers all portrayed as enjoying the bloom and the beauty of the glamorous social life. These constitute the upper echelon in the society. Sęgilęla's involvement with the various social groups in the society portrays changes in the cultural setting. There is the introduction of ball room dancing and the performance of modern orchestra with their new styles in music and dance. Among the most popular form of dance is the 'pandero' and 'Gumbe'. The Gumbe dance style was introduced by the liberated slaves who were regarded as the purveyors of modern civilization in the society. These 'modern styles' paint a grand picture of modernity and innovation in the social life of the Lagos society.

Thomas uses marriage as a symbol of socio-cultural change. Marriage is an age-long institution in many human societies. Among the Yoruba, marriage is seen as a strong bond of love, unity and togetherness among families and tribes. Both human and divine sanctions serve as determining factors in the consumation of marriage. Polygyny was the vogue as this was considered the foundation of the populous household as well as the communal society. In keeping with the traditional pattern many of Sęgilęla's suitors propose polygamous form of marriage to her. She turns down such offers, such an offer is conservative, for Sęgilęla no longer belongs to the old tradition. She is clearly a product of the modern society. She abhors the traditional marriage, and opts for the modern form - the 'me and my husband' type popularly known as marriage by ordinance.

Among the most noteworthy changes that characterized the British administration was the introduction of marriage by ordinance. With the establishment of British rule and the growth of Christianity, marriage by ordinance became one of the most sought-after by many Lagos girls. The colonial law based on Christian principles, inter-alia stipulates "the

marriage of one man to one wife to the exclusion of all other".²⁵ It implies virtual permanence of the union between husband and wife, "for better for worse till death do us part". This marriage by ordinance became popular in the 1920s. Many literate Christian women in Lagos saw it as a great advantage on the customary marriage. To such women, this modern form of marriage offers among other things, a more secure and permanent matrimonial home. It was seen as a mark of great esteem, and social standing.

The pomp and grandeur that characterized Sẹgilọla's wedding signify one of the changes brought about by the colonial administration: horse driven cart, white wedding gown, dignifying social reception. It was for this reason that many ladies in the Lagos urban society preferred the 'white wedding' to the traditional type. For Thomas, Sẹgilọla's happy marriage ^{cannot} provide a complete picture of his view of the society as it could lead to the termination of the story in Sẹgilọla's home. Thus Sẹgilọla's marriage ends in shame, sterility and divorce. Divorce is thus introduced to effect continuity in a way that would lead to another

25. See Osoba, O. 1976: 'Some considerations on the impact of the West on Yoruba cultural forms' in Yoruba civilization, p.266.

aspect of cultural change in the society. In the traditional Yoruba society marriage was a union of man and woman which to a great extent was indissoluble save by death. Oguntuyi (1979: 130) confirms this:

By native law and custom, a woman belonged to her husband for life even when death parted them, a woman still belonged to the family of her deceased husband there was no separation... She and her children still remained the property of her lawful husband.

But when the British in 1916 introduced the law of divorce in many parts of Yorubaland, women became conscious of a new kind of freedom. The law of divorce stipulates that a woman could free herself by the refund, in full or in part, of the dowry paid on her by her husband. She was at liberty to marry another man or live on her own without any specific husband. This new law caused untold hardship in the 1920s and the thirties. It was a notable example of the kind of socio-cultural disintegration, which came in the wake of British administration. Oguntuyi (1979: 130) again attests to this:

For a time, divorce caused untold confusion. Many husbands who went to farm in the morning with the intention of coming back for a good meal in the evening returned to be given a piece of paper instead of their meals. The paper was a notice of divorce

stating time of court hearing. The anger engendered on such an occasion led to terrible disorder and murder in certain cases. Divorce destroyed the love which should exist between husband and wife.

Thomas uses Sęgilqla's divorce of Bankqlle to depict breakdown of love and amity between couples. His presentation of Sęgilqla's elopement is an artistic rendering of the perfidy and infidelity of ^{emancipated} women. More importantly, Thomas adopts divorce as a device to expose the heroine to a wider society, to effect a smoother continuity of the story and to achieve a more realistic presentation of the society.

In order to present a wider and deeper view of his ^{the} society, Thomas changes the course of life of protagonist. Having failed dismally as a housewife, Sęgilqla elopes with another man and later becomes a prostitute. This change in Sęgilqla's life style is significant. First, it broadens the scope of the novel and provides a greater opportunity to delve into other aspects of the society. Secondly it depicts Thomas's artistry in character delineation. There is a serious attempt at character development. Sęgilql appears first as a simple, innocent girl; later she grows up into a shrewd, crafty adolescent who is the cynosure of the society.

she finally turns a prostitute. This last change in her life style raises a pertinent question. Why does she become a prostitute?

In its most precise description, prostitution emphasizes two essential elements. First, is the exchange of money or valuable materials in return for sexual activity. Secondly is the relatively indiscriminate availability of sexual transactions to individuals other than spouses or friends. Thus basically, prostitution embodies two major societal interests: sex and money. The motivating force behind Segilola's new life is acquisition of wealth.

The first decade of the twentieth century was significant in the process of modern urbanization and commercialization in Lagos. It was the period of the extension of the railway, the dredging of the channel to the harbour, the construction of the Lagos stream Tramway and provision of many public industrial and commercial enterprises. Of particular importance for the remarkable economic growth of Lagos was the development of the port. All these spurred economic advancement in various directions. The increase in importation of goods attracted numerous wholesalers, retailers and commercial agents. By the 1920s, Lagos had established

itself as a commercial centre for imported consumer products, owing to the high purchasing power of its wage-earning population. It has a high concentration of skilled manpower and consequently an increased population of paid workers. All these brought about material prosperity. The capitalist economy gradually influenced the social structure of the society. It created a greater zest for the pursuit of wealth. Thomas's work is concerned with the portrayal of the effect of this socio-economic change. He is concerned with the theme of social disintegration as an impact of Western capitalism on the traditional Lagos society. His novel is a pointer to the growing concern for money, profit, and greed, in the various classes of the society.

A cursory reading of the novel would readily suggest that prostitution is intended to evince a moral import. The pains and sorrows that characterize the life of Sęgilola is a deliberate attempt to deride prostitution and to serve as admonition to the younger ones. The didactic purpose of the issue of prostitution remains undoubted, for Thomas clearly uses Sęgilola's change to prostitution to establish the fact that unbridled sexuality is absolutely immoral. It is bad because it has a serious corrupting power. Thomas reveals in unmitigating terms that prostitution can ultimately result in

loss of physical beauty, and lead to infirmity and sterility. But this is only a partial assessment of Thomas's purpose. Such an assessment will only reveal Thomas as a moralist. It provides little information about the structure of the society. It certainly limits our knowledge about Thomas's relationship with his society.

From the point of view of sociology of literature, Thomas's use of prostitution transcends mere reflection of sexual immoralities of the Lagos society. Prostitution has a strong link with the socio-economic conditions of the society. Prostitution is basically an economic matter. It is therefore destined to follow ^{economic} laws. It will grow and flourish according to the number of individuals who possess the wherewithal to meet the demands of the business: sex appeal and money. Prostitution is usually reinforced by its affiliations with high society parties, drinking, dancing and entertainment. The Lagos society of the 1920s provided all these facilities. Sẹgilọla testifies to this on page 12:

Lásìkò ìgbà wúndíá, awa kò ní ijó meji lẹhin
 ìlù "Gumbe" ati ìlù "Pandero" tí Ologbe Adelokun
 onílù má n lù. Irú ní èmi Sẹgilọla tí kò n dín
 ní ọbẹ; ẹnikẹni a sì ma gbà fún mi nígbà tí
 emi bá n bẹ ní agbo ijó "Gumbe"... Tàbí ní ọnà
 keji ẹwẹ, tani nínú awọn wúndíá ẹlẹgbẹ mi aiyé
 ìgbàni tinwọn tó lati ba mi ra ijó "Pandero"

níwájú Adelakun Onílù? A! kò sí Oluwarẹ.
 Gbogbo awọn gbajumọ ninwọn si n fi ọwọ
 ílá yẹ mi si lásìkò ìgbà na.

During our heydays, we did not have any other dance music besides "Gumbe" and "Pandero" for which late musician Adelakun was noteworthy. I, Sẹgilọla was like the locust bean in the soup. I was indispensable. Everybody used to hail me whenever I was dancing the Gumbe style in the dancing arena... Secondly, who among my contemporaries in those days could compete with me when dancing the "Pandero" music in the presence of Adelakun the musician? There was no one. Many of the distinguished personalities present often sprayed me with big money at such times.

Thus prostitution is a signification of the growing influence of the capitalist economy in the urban commercial Lagos society. For, by the 1920s, Lagos society was witnessing the rise of a new generation of entrepreneurs who were enjoying affluence, conspicuous consumption, hedonism, and frivolous leisure. Thomas uses Sẹgilọla's multifarious pre-marital and extramarital contacts with men to establish this point. For instance, during Sẹgilọla's encounter with a wealthy Gold Coast merchant, she recounts with zest her sexual dealings with other men:

Àwọn ọkunrin, yálà l'Óyìnbó, l'Ágànyìn
 tàbí lòmọ Ekó tí emi Sẹgilola ti yan lale
 lé ní àdọta ọkunrin láisọ àsọdùn rará.

Various men, whether European, Ghanaian
 or Lagosians whom I Sẹgilola befriended
 were well over fifty men without exaggera-
 tion.

er dealings with these men enriched her and made her a really
 healthy woman within a short time.

Thomas's Itàn Emi Sẹgilola is a portrayal of the rise
 and effects of capitalism in the Lagos society of his time.
 Among such effects are the craze for material acquisition,
 individualism and alienation. Thomas creatively and realis-
 tically weaves this theme around the person and deeds of
 Sẹgilola, the protagonist. The period of her birth and life
 accurately fits into a remarkable socio-economic era. She
 was born in 1882, a period of progressive incursion of
 British colonialism into the Lagos metropolis. The middle to
 the end of the nineteenth century was the beginning of
 conspicuous physical development in Lagos - construction of
 railways, bridges, roads and street lights; factors that
 ushered in modernity and urbanism. The period marked the
 emergence of the Saro community who became Nigeria's first
 westernized elite who paved the way for revolutionizing the

cial, economic and political structure of the town. Sęgilq̄la's birth and life coincide with the time when the effects of capitalist economy were becoming glaringly manifest.

Similarly, her name is symptomatic of socio-economic change, for Sęgilq̄la is not her first name. She changes to Sę. The name Sęgilq̄la, constitutes the epitomé of the effect of change. Rendered in full, the name is "Sęgilq̄la Sęyinjuęęę, ibàdíàrán, ò-ru-nkan-dèdè-wq̄jà. (p.69)

Sęgilq̄la the one with delicate eyeballs, whose bottom befits velvet, one who carries heavy material to the market). The name has an interesting relationship with the market economy - beautiful precious beads, elegant delicate look, velvet clothes, heavy commodity and market. Sęgilq̄la as physically depicted in the novel, is a highly marketable commodity in a vast growing economy. She says of herself:

... emi ję q̄kan ninu awq̄n q̄mq̄binrin aiyé ti
 Èlédà fi ęwà ara ęe lęşşò tí kò n ęe díę;
 ènià pupa fò ni emi n ęe; ęwa ara mi kúná,
 ó si wę pęlú. Ara mi rí múlómúló bí irq̄rí
 olowu-ęgungun; mo síngbq̄nlę lati òkè ara
 mi dé ilę, emi kò sanra jü li ènià
 bë ni èmi kò si gbera kq̄já alá. (p.7)

...I am one of the women in the world, whom the creator endows with unspeakable beauty. I am very light in complexion. My physical beauty is smooth and fine. My flesh is glossy and soft like a succulent pillow. I am tall and stately in body constitution. My figure is moderate, for I am neither too fat nor too thin.

The captivating quality of her beauty is also described:

(p.58).

Lotọ arẹwà obinrin tó tí inú obinrin wá ni
emi Sẹgilọla n ẹ se ani se, ẹwa pupa ara mi
bu iyin on olá lummi tóbẹ gẹ dé ipò pé kò si
ọkunrin kọkunrin to má ẹ alabapade mi lárin
ita mẹta ti okunrin na kò ni sịjú rẹ wò emi
Sẹgilọla lẹmeji tabi ju bẹ lọ...

It is true that I, Sẹgilọla am a beauty among beauties. My light complexioned body heightens my glory and honour, such that no man will meet me at the crossroads without turning back to look at me a second time or even more.

Sẹgilọla adequately meets the greatest physical requirement for prostitution, her profession. Secondly, prostitution is not the original plan for her life. Her mother's intention is to give her sound formal school education. But again, she changes from formal school education to prostitution. Thus from the onset there is an interesting relationship between Sẹgilọla's person and the changing socio-economic conditions

she is created to portray.

The other part of her epithet, *ẹlẹgbẹrún-ọkọ-láyé*, (owner of thousand husbands in the world) suggests a certain behavioural weakness in Sẹgilọla's person. It is an insinuation of avaricious tendencies in the character of Sẹgilọla. This is not surprising when one considers Sẹgilọla's behaviour. The epithet is not a name in the Yoruba sense, rather it is a sobriquet that emanates from the bearer's action or conduct. Thomas depicts Sẹgilọla as a covetous character; this becomes evident right from the period of her expulsion from school. Ever before her first sexual experience with the diviner/herbalist, Sẹgilọla has been known to be sexually innocent. But even though she has had no sexual affair with any man, she cherishes receiving money and precious gifts from men. Before her marriage, she could identify seven suitors and innumerable, unidentifiable lovers among men in the society. Her goal in all the encounters with men is material acquisition rather than sexual pleasure. The epithet then is suggestive of a certain sense of excessiveness and superfluity. This accedes with the capitalist ideology of materialism.

The existence of the large number of suitors and lovers who ungrudgingly satisfy Sęgilęla's financial demands presupposes the state of growing affluence, a situation which culminates in moral decay and squandermania. Sęgilęla begins her dealings with members of the middle class. Her first victim works in a European commercial store where beautiful clothes and luxurious attires are sold. Sęgilęla befriends Sanya not because of love and marriage but because of her strong inclination towards material acquisition. So successful is Sęgilęla's first experience, that within one and a half months of moving with Sanya, she collects a total amount of twenty-five pounds (£50.00) apart from many other valuable and costly presents. The trend continues as Sęgilęla enjoys moving and mixing with men to satisfy her materialistic desires. Her change from one suitor to another confirms the existence of definite social classes in the society. She has nothing to do with the proletariat class. They are portrayed as the true working class; some of them carry Sęgilęla and her man in their canoes on the way to Sekondi in the Gold Coast (Ghana). Her suitors like Sanya, Labęde and Bankęle among others belong to the middle class. Most of her unnamed suitors belong to the upper class. Among these is the remarkably

prosperous man who lives at "Ehin Ogba" street, who among other things promises Sęgilọla a whole house as gift, if she accepts to marry him. Like the others, Sęgilọla feeds fat on the wealthy man only to leave him at last.

The wealthy Gold Coast (Ghana) merchant with whom Sęgilọla elopes is another testimony to the rise of the noveau riche in the new capitalist society. Sęgilọla says of the man: (pp. 66-67).

..mo s'akiyesi, pe onisowo nla ni ale mi
na n se nitoto ni ilu Sekondi yi, ati pe
awon Oja owore re na si bureke lopolopo...
Ale mi yi a si ma fi emi nikan sileni
ilu Sekondi, on a si ma ba awon isere owore
re miran lo si awon ilu agbegbe bi -
Accra, Kumasi, Lome, Cape Coast...

I observed that my lover is indeed a big businessman in Sekondi and that his business is a really flourishing one... This lover of mine often leaves me alone at Sekondi and travels on business trips to other towns like Accra, Kumasi, Lome, Cape Coast etc...

Sęgilọla abundantly enriches herself in her dealings with this man so much that she decides to live alone in Lagos after the burial ceremony of her mother. She recounts with pride her monetary and material gains within one year of her stay in Sekondi:

Láífa ọ̀rò gun lọ tí tí mọ, níwọ̀n ọ̀dun kan
 tí emi Sẹ̀gilọ̀la fi ba àlẹ̀ mi yì wà ni ìlù
 Sẹ̀kẹ̀ndi, ẹ̀ru ti p'ọ̀kọ̀ fún mi tí kò n' sẹ
 díẹ̀, àìníyẹ̀ awọ̀n ohun àlùmọ̀ni ati owó ni
 emi sì n' fi sọ̀wọ̀ lábẹ̀lẹ̀ sí ọ̀rẹ̀ mi Ayọ̀ka fún
 ìpamọ̀. (p. 68).

In a nutshell, within one year that I,
 Sẹ̀gilọ̀la lived with my lover at Sekondi
 I was bountifully enriched, the amount of
 money and precious material possession that
 I secretly sent to my friend Ayọ̀ka for safe
 keeping was inestimable.

Sẹ̀gilọ̀la amasses wealth through an immoral but lucrative
 business. In the capitalist economy, it is the acquisition
 of the wealth that is primary, the source of the wealth is
 of negligible significance.

Capitalism gradually engenders the liberal individualistic
 values of personal liberty, and the rights of man to the
 development of personality. In the Lagos society of
 I.B. Thomas's time, the remarkable growth in the early
 decades of the twentieth century fostered conspicuous
 change. The fluid social structure led to the ethic of
 individualism and individual effort. Thomas does not
 portray this tendency fully, but it is clearly observable
 in the deeds of Sẹ̀gilọ̀la.

From the onset, she has been depicted as a free minded and individualistic character. Since her expulsion from school, she has been left on her own. She has no definite job. She makes her own plans and decisions without hinderance. Her behaviour is in consonance with her generation. For she belongs to an age that advocates the rights and liberty of the individual. Physically, she is an outstanding character - tall, imposing, and exquisitely beautiful. This artistic portrait tends to suggest a kind of **individualism**. The theme of individualism is further strengthened by Segilola's preference for monogamous marriage. It is that type of marriage that suits her high taste and nature. Furthermore, the social changes in the society give room for independent thought and action, she is under no obligation to accept the traditional polygamous marriage. Thus Segilola uses the issue of monogamous marriage to sever relations with men as soon as she has had her fill of their money and material gifts. It is only when Bankole consents to her request that she agrees to marry him. To Bankole and his mother, the idea of "one man, one wife" is repulsive, but Segilola's domineering will represses every opposition. And in her matrimonial home, she employs every force to assert her egoism: (pp. 50 - 51).

Şùgbón nígbàti ó ni iyé ọjọ tó sì ní iye osù
 pẹlu tí mo ti de ilé ọkọ mi tó gbe mi ni iyàwó
 arédè ná; mo wá jẹwọ ara mi gbangba fún iyá ọkọ ati
 ọkọ mi na pẹlu pé iyàwo alárédè tó gba òrùka ni èmi
 kò níí gba àşekáşẹ, onikùmọ kankan, yálà lati ọwọ
 iyá-ọkọ mi ni o, tàbí lati ọwọ ọkọ mi ná
 pàápàá; nitori ná, èmi Şegilọla Eleyinjúẹẹ,
 àní èmi obìnrin tó ti inú awọn obìnrin wá,
 mo wá gbé ojú ẹkùn sójú mi, mo sì aṣfún ọkọ
 mi ná pé kó bá mi şe ikilọ fún iya rẹ lati
 lè wa ọkọ àşekáşẹ rẹ sí itó, nitori pe iyàwó
 alárédè lèmi n şe àti pé emi si ni eni tí o
 ní lati ni aşe ilé ọkọ mi ní ikáwọ kò si n
 şe iyá-ọkọ-kí-iyá-ọkọ kan ni yó pá àşe
 ọdélésinrin kan lé mi lórí.

After I had spent a considerable length of time
 in my husband's house, I asserted my right on
 my mother-in-law and my husband, making them
 realise that I am married to my husband by
 ordinance, since I am not an ordinary wife,
 I cannot and will not accept any undue
 authority either from my mother-in-law or
 my husband himself, henceforth I, Şegilọla
 woman among women, put up an uncompromising
 mien and instructed my husband to warn his
 mother to desist from lording herself on me
 in the affairs of my matrimonial home, this
 is because I am married by ordinance, and as
 such I have absolute authority in my home,
 and no mother-in-law whatsoever, can command
 me unnecessarily.

Seğilola's mother-in-law is severely critical of the 'me and my husband' attitude. The mother-in-law is tenaciously bent on preventing its successful operation in her son's home. But Seğilola remains obdurate and uncompromising and finally succeeds in ejecting her mother-in-law from the home.

The theme of individualism is taken up further in the elopement of Seğilola with the wealthy Gold Coast merchant. Seğilola's condition for accepting the man's hand in marriage is the total expulsion of all his four wives from the matrimonial home. Seğilola wants to be the sole controller of her home, and the centre of her husband's attention. Her usual maxim is: (p.18).

Ìyálé ni n ó şe
 Èmi ò le şe ìyàwó agbòbẹ ka'ná
 Ìyálé ni n ó şe

I'll rather be the senior wife
 I can never be the junior one who
 always warms the soup
 I'll rather be the senior wife.

Seğilola cannot accept any subsidiary position. Her portrait in the novel justifies this view. Her physical and psychological qualities - craftiness, shrewdness, nonchallance and stubbornness: all point to her as a person who would favour

the pursuit of individual, rather than common or collective interests. This unbending individualistic nature in *Segilola* is characteristic of the new socio-economic life of the Lagos society. It has become a society in which loyalty to self is gradually displacing communal loyalty.

Another theme in Thomas's novel is that of alienation. It is depicted as one of the most harrowing effects of the new economic order. Marx defines alienation as the process by which man is turned into a stranger in the world which his own activity has created. He goes further to explain that the social division of labour has the effect of creating vast accumulations of wealth but at the cost of a progressive devaluing of human life. Man is alienated as a 'species being', for he now lives entirely for himself and no longer for the community. Capitalism transforms species man into individual man.²⁶ But alienation can also refer to the process of withdrawal of affection, love, and friendship from where it existed before. Alienation involves estrangement of man from his society. In *Ìtàn Emi Segilola* Thomas depicts

26. Laurenson, D. and Swingewood, op. cit. pp. 212-213.

alienation from the point of view of estrangement of man's affection and love from relations e.g. parents and spouse. He employs some of Sęgilọla's actions to show how man becomes more and more dehumanized and alienated from the society, as a result of the progressive incursion of exchange values.

Sęgilọla is the only surviving child of her ageing mother, but rather than live to care for her and make her happy, she becomes indifferent in her behaviour. Her desire for money and material gains prevents her from making a quick choice of a husband. Her mother threatens to disown her if within six months she fails to make up her mind on the choice of a life partner. Rather than show affection, Sęgilọla *feels unworried* and declares: (p.14).

Okàn mí balẹ̀ fún pe bí iyá mí ná
 tilẹ̀ kọ mí lómọ, nitori pé emi kò
 mú ọkunrin kan wọle wa hàn, gẹgẹ
 bí ẹnì tí o n fẹ mí sọna, èyí kò
 lẹ pa mí ládánù kankan rárá, nitori
 pé ẹwà ara mí tó mí lati fi ẹ̀ ọgo.

I felt assured that if my mother rejects me because I fail to produce a fiancée, I have nothing to lose since my beauty is there for me to glory in.

To Sęgilq̄la, loss of maternal love and affection is no loss, because of the material gains her beauty can provide.

As the story unfolds, Sęgilq̄la's preference for material things gradually dehumanizes her. She secretly plans to elope with another man as she tricks her husband to travel to the herbalist who is helping to solve her problem of infertility. She uses the occasion of her husband's absence to escape. She does not even confide in her mother, but abandons her for ever! This is a glaring depiction of a society in which money and material acquisition have taken precedence over man.

Materialism with its attendant ills does not only change people's relationship to one another, it also changes their attitude to values. Thomas depicts this change of values in one of the adventures of Sęgilq̄la. Money consciousness, flourishing business, distinguished position in society, lucrative profession and the use of herbal power to accumulate wealth are some of the values that the society cherishes. For instance, the crewmen rowing Sęgilq̄la and others to the ship, suddenly abandon their paddles midstream and demand additional charges from the passengers. It is only when their demand is met that they set to work. To the crewmen, money is more important than human lives put in their care.

The crewmen belong to the proletariat class, they are victims of the new socio-economic system in which precious human values have been taken over by material values. Thomas shows that the new ideology of materialism affects not only a section of the society, but the entire society. Thus, Thomas's Itàn Emi Sègilòla is a confirmation of what Goldmann calls 'crisis of values'. Goldmann has argued that crisis of values emerges with the development of a capitalist society where market values dominate human values.²⁷

Thomas's vision is one of pessimism agonizingly portrayed in Sègilòla's helplessness and tragic end. It is not only in content and form that this vision is expressed, it also manifests in his use of language. Language in Itàn Emi Sègilòla like other things in the novel, flows from one source - Sègilòla herself. She does almost all the talking. This is not surprising since the novel is a kind of autobiography issuing out from the heroine's pen. But the striking thing is the way language is used to portray certain things about the society. Certain elements are clearly observable in Thomas's use of language. First, his use of language is

27. Ibid., p.245.

lucid.

For instance the story begins simply:

Ogbeni oniwe irohìn, mo júba o.
 Emi yó ma sope lowo re titi ojo aiyé mi
 yokù bí iwọ bá le gba mi láyè lósòsè ninu
 iwé irohìn re iyebiye ti a n pè ni
Akéde Èkó ki emi Sẹgilọla tí mo fẹ tó
 bí ẹgbẹrún ọkunrín lẹkọ nínú aiyé mi le
 ma ẹ apitàn igbésí aiyé mi ná fún gbogbo
 agbaiye kà nínú iwé irohìn re Akéde Èkó
 (p.1).

Newspaper editor sir, I pay homage.
 I will continue to thank you throughout
 the remaining days of my life, if you
 will permit it that every week in your
 precious newspaper called Akede Eko,
 I Sẹgilọla who courted up to about one
 thousand men as husband in my life may
 narrate the story of my life for the
 whole world to read in your newspaper
Akedé Èkó.

This is the general pattern of language use in the novel -
 direct and clearly intelligible. Like many other Yoruba
 works, the novel is full of apt proverbs, which are aimed at
 making the author's meaning clearer to his audience. For
 instance in a bid to explain the cause of his sorrow (p.24)
 Sẹgilọla states that she is the architect of her misfortune.
 She expresses this in a fitting proverb and says "Atàgò
 kẹyin àparò, ohun tí ojú wa ni ojú ní rí" (when one collects

the bush fowl's eggs from the fowl-coop, whatever one's eye looks for, it finds).

Whatever sad experiences she suffers are caused by herself. And in an attempt to give a reason for deciding to publicize the story of her life she does it proverbially and says: *Eni tí ó ba kókó jìn sí kòtò, ó ye lati kó awon èrò ẹhin lógbón.* (Who soever first falls into a pit, ought to teach his followers a lesson). The simplicity and lucidity in language use reveals his awareness of the nature and structure of the society that constitute his audience. His society is one of diverse cultural backgrounds, whose knowledge of, and proficiency in Yoruba is limited. The use of ^{intelligible} language is thus an effective way to put across his message.

Thomas also uses language to project his view of the society as a victim of incurable pain and irreparable loss. He makes use of words, phrases, nuances and sentences that clearly portray pain, passion, distress and agony. Immediately after expressing the didactic purpose of her story, in the opening chapter, *Sẹgilọla* bursts out: "Ye! o ẹe! ó mà pọ o, ènià kì mà nikan dáro o" (What a great pity! It is far too much. It is not easy to bemoan one's pain alone) and on p.43 she exclaims:

A! igi dá!
 Oṣé ló ní ṣiwájú ẹkún
 Abámọ̀ ló ní gbẹ̀hìn ọ̀rọ̀...

What a great pity
 hissing often precedes weeping
 Regrets come at the end of events.

Interjectory outbursts like these reverberate throughout the novel. Even towards the end (p.75) Sẹgilọla shouts: "Ibosi oró ò ò ò!" (What painful grief!). The expressions paint the picture of a person in severe mental agony and spiritual depression. The picture suggests a feeling of regret and lamentation for wrongful deed. This use of language to create passion affects the reader from the beginning to the end. Even when Sẹgilọla deals with some enjoyable part of her life, she quickly dismisses it as a worthless and wasteful enjoyment since it all ends in sorrow and degradation.

Thomas often makes use of pithy and poetic expressions to illustrate Sẹgilọla's fall from glory to shame. Thus on page 40, her conscience mocks and sings:

Wúndiá lójú
Adélébò nísàlẹ̀

On the face of it a virgin

(But underneath a married/sexually exposed woman)

This is a picture of deceit, insincerity and double dealing. It is a figurative use of language to portray Sẹgilọla as externally pure, inwardly rotten. As the story moves forward, Thomas employs various poetic pieces both from traditional and biblical sources to establish significant points about his view of the society.

A spectacular feature of his language is the use of short and long sentences for effect. An example will suffice:

Lode aiyé mi loni yì, ẹkún àbámọ̀ lemi
Sẹgilọla n sun, yalà lowuro, loṣan, lálẹ̀
tabi ni àbùsùndájí; ẹwa on ọlá ara mi ti
mo ti gbẹkẹlẹ̀ lasiko ìgbà gbajúmọ̀ mi laiye
tí kò fún mi layè lati gba ìkìlọ̀ iyá tàbí
ti ọkọ, ẹwà ná ti fi mi sílẹ̀ lọ léde aiyé
mi loni yì; àìgbà ìkìlọ̀ ọjọ kinni ná si n na
mi ní pàṣán cró lode aiyé mi loni yi ẹmi
Sẹgilọla ti ri ìgbẹ̀hìn ẹ̀rẹ ẹṣẹ̀ àgbèrẹ̀ tàbí
pàṣágà temi loni ná, ṣugbọ̀n kò bá dara púpọ̀
fún olúkúlukù ẹ̀nyin ẹ̀nià tí ẹ̀ n da mi lólá
lati má ka ìtàn ìbanújẹ̀ aiyé mi yì bó bá jẹ̀

wife nyin yó má ɛ temi Sẹgilọla ni jíjí
 ikí; ní ɛnyin ma ba ɛubù sínú ọgbun
 ilàndá ɛ tí emi ní ké ìrora nínú rẹ loni yì.

In this my life of today, I, Sẹgilọla shed tears of regret day and night, or early in the morning; the beauty and honour of my body which I trusted in my heydays, which did not permit me to accept the warning of my parents and husband, have now left me, in this my life today my refusal to accept warning in those days is now lashing me painfully in my life today; I Sẹgilọla have seen the result of my adultery and fornication this day, but it would be good if everyone of you who honour me by reading the story of my sorrowful life can make the example of my life a mirror of warning, so that you do not fall into the pit of anguish inside which I am now groaning today.

As can be seen in the above excerpt, the sentences are often complete with apt words, idioms, metaphors and other figures of speech that make his message clear. In the above excerpt, stylistic devices like repetition, lexical matching and imagery are used to advantage. The phrase "lode aiyé mi yì" (In this life of mine) is repeated three times. The use of repetition here produces an emphatic significance. It focuses attention on the protagonist's situation which is characterized by loss, pain and sorrow. The occurrence of lexical matching "lowurọ, ọsan, àbùsùndájí" (morning, afternoon and early dawn) signifies a recurrence of the painful experience. It is suggestive of a seemingly interminably

onizing condition. Other figurative expressions - metaphor and imagery like "jígí ìkìlò" (mirror of warning), and "Ògbun ànùjé" not only add beauty, colour and weight to the statement, but also give the message a sense of gravity and seriousness.

A distinguishing feature of Itan Emi Segilola's structure is the tragic essence that pervades it. There is a glaring sense of tragic realism in the form of the novel, notably in its characterization, theme and language. All these aspects of the form are inextricably interwoven to depict the tragic essence of the novel. Segilola's life is tragic. Her tragedy looks seemingly interminable. It is worse than death. To Thomas, the death of Segilola will not adequately convey the urgency and poignancy of his message. Thus Segilola does not die but continues her life in seemingly unending suffering. Her tragedy consists in the irreparable loss occasioned by the experiences she undergoes in the course of her life. Her tragedy is caused by the fact that she actively strives to be part of a society that eventually corrupts her. The tragic is embedded in the web of social relationships of which Segilola is the focal point. Segilola is left in a situation of double tragedy. The tragic situation in which we leave her

in the novel, obliterates her past enjoyment^{and} points to a bleak future. All we see about her is the tragic! Her matrimonial joy has been destroyed, her filial relationship is extinguished. Her past constitutes a colossal waste. She is left alone, helpless, childless and penniless! At the close of the novel, Jegilola has no contact with her friends and relations. The novel ends on a deep note of anguish. So successful is Thomas in his portrayal of this agonizing sense of the tragic in the novel, that from the beginning to the end, the reader is engulfed in pity and compassionate thoughts.

Itan Emi Segilola is deceptively a novel of private experience. But it is a portrayal of the socio-cultural degeneration and despair of a society in transition, the early colonial Lagos society in which the world view of communalism is being displaced by materialism and individualism. The novel is a subtle attack on a society which is being emptied of genuine qualitative values through the progressive incursion of materialism. I.B. Thomas is a critical realist. His work constitutes the critical attitude of literature to life; the opposition of the writer to the society his work portrays.

CHAPTER THREE

D.O. FAGUNWA* AND THE TRADITIONAL YORUBA SOCIETY:A STUDY OF HIS FIRST TWO NOVELSFagunwa's Society

The society depicted in the first two novels of D.O. Fagunwa, Ogbójúode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè and Igbó Olodumarè is as stated in p. 71 the traditional Yoruba society of the precolonial and early colonial era although both novels were written in 1930s and 1940s respectively. Unlike Thomas and Okediji, whose novels were set in specific identifiable towns (Lagos and Ibadan respectively), Fagunwa's first two novels, Ogbójúode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè and Igbó Olodumarè indicate no precise setting. This approach gives Fagunwa the opportunity to depict the traditional Yoruba society from the early times to the end of the second world war. This observation is important in the sense that it suggests that the society in these novels is different from the society portrayed in his other novels, notably Irínkèrindò Nínú Igbó Elégbèje and Adìitú Olódùmarè. The period (1930s --1940s) when Fagunwa wrote his first two novels was replete with a sound knowledge of Yoruba traditional life and society unlike the fifties when socio-political changes have influenced Yoruba life and customs tremendously. Since the first two

*We deliberately skip Fagunwa's biography in this work. B-20

novels were written between the early thirties and forties, a knowledge of the society that gave birth to the novels is essential for our understanding of the social significance of the novels.

The Yoruba traditional society from the pre-colonial times to the 1940s was made up of Yoruba speaking peoples in the south-western part of Nigeria, notably the area now known as Ogun, Ondo and Oyo states. Yorubaland stretches from the swamps and lagoons of the coast across the rain forests, rising towards the oil-palm bush and wood land savannah. For the most part, it is a verdant country, watered by many rivers and streams which give it a landscape that varies from swamps and thick forests to uplands and rocky hills in the savannah. They were a populous group with many kings some of who ruled over distinct and independent states while some others were subordinate rulers whose territories consisted of single towns and groups of villages.¹ The Yoruba have been regarded as unique in tropical Africa in terms of the size and number of their towns.² According to the 1953 census,

1. See Smith, R.S. 1969: Kingdoms of the Yorubas Methuen and Co. Ltd., pp. 1-4.

2. Eades, J.S. 1980: The Yoruba Today, Cambridge University Press, p.35.

22% of the Yoruba population lived in towns of over one hundred thousand and 53% in towns of over five thousand inhabitants.

The name Yoruba originally applied to the powerful Oyo alone, for the Oyo was the most popular empire in the early times. Her superior military strength gave her predominance over her neighbours. By the 18th century Old Oyo Empire had reached the meridian of its power. Its strength rested on the ideology of the sovereignty of ^{the} Alaafin the centripetal figure whose name at the best times was sufficient to make his subjects law-abiding. Another factor of its power was the capital's position as a commercial centre. Oyo-Ile the capital linked the coastal trade with those of the cities of the Western Sudan since the fifteenth century. Oyo was actively involved in the seventeenth century slave trade, in return for which it received iron, salt, cutlasses, cloth and mirrors. Items sent northwards included kolanuts, pepper and European salt. From the trans-Saharan trade it received horses, swords, knives, leather, beads and silk.³ The economic situation was basically agrarian. This was more

3. Smith, R.S. op. cit., p.3.

so among the Egbas, Ondo, Oyo, Ijẹsa and Ijebu. Although the Ijebu were hardworking farmers they were better known as energetic and enterprising traders.⁴ By the nineteenth century, they were in control of the trade in firearms in the interior. Their commercial activities and earlier contacts with Europeans made them more prosperous than their neighbours in the interior.⁴ Farming was the mainstay of the economy in many communities in the hinterland, like Ibadan, Oyo and Ondo provinces. The main sources of income were farm crops like yams, maize, cotton, guinea corn, palm produce and kolanuts.

The political system was a feudalistic one which encouraged cheap labour. Consequent upon the internecine wars, powerful and prominent members of the society like Obas, Chiefs and war leaders had access to cheap labour by war captives who were used as slaves and labourers on the farms. Pawns and ^{debtors} served in the extensive farm lands of the rich. Some of the slaves and pawns also served as domestic servants in the large compounds of the rich.

One of the significant features of this traditional society was its dominant monarchical organisation. At the highest level of the hierarchy were the Oba, supported by the

4. Ibid., p.7.

chiefs, household heads and finally the common people. The ideology of sacred kingship was at this period firmly upheld. The sacred character of the Oba is expressed in numerous customs. For instance it is forbidden for any person apart from the Oba to wear his crown. No man must take the Oba's wife or his concubine. It was a taboo for the Oba to see a corpse and on no account must any corpse be carried across the front of his palace. The Oba was granted freedom from manual labour. He might not be seen eating. His bare-foot should not touch the ground. The Oba may take any woman as wife. Indeed, the Oba does not die, he only 'goes away'.⁵ As the Oba, he is the personification of his town, his wealth which is often reflected in the magnificence of his palace and his regalia, establishes the prosperity and rank of the town among its neighbours.⁶

Natural rulers in many Yoruba towns and villages enjoyed an exalted position during the precolonial period. Balogun aptly describes the elevated status of the Oba:

5. Lyoyd, P.C. 1960: "Sacred Kingship and government among the Yoruba" in Africa Vol. 30, No.5., pp. 221-237

6. Ibid.

The Oba was the life of the traditional community. The Oba was the Chief Priest, Chief Executive and fountain of honour and justice. He wielded immense powers commensurate to an envoy of God on earth which it was claimed he was...⁷

This dignifying position of the Oba is clearly observable in many Yoruba communities of the times. This was particularly the case in Oyo which was the seat of the Alaafin who had great powers and authority in the Old Oyo empire. His subjects saw him as their supreme overlord and second in command to the gods. The domineering influences which the Oba had in many towns and kingdoms were not limited to the Alaafin alone. Arifalo describes the great influence enjoyed by the Deji of Akure:

The Deji wielded tremendous influence over the kingdom. He claimed a share of all big game animals killed in any part of the kingdom. If an elephant was killed, he got one of the tusks, if it was a buffalo, a thigh was brought to the palace.⁸

This is a typical example of the exalted position accorded many Yoruba Obas in precolonial times. Fagunwa must have had abundant knowledge of the fame and status of Yoruba Obas at

7. Balogun, K. 1976: 'From Sacred Kingship to Democratic gerontocracy' in Yoruba Civilization University of Ife, pp. 291-324.

8. See Akinjogbin, I.A. and Ekemode, G.O. eds. 1976: op. cit., pp. 154-177.

that time, particularly the overriding influence of the Alaafin of Oyo. It is this among others, that most probably influenced his strong admiration for the institution of Obaship as demonstrated in his novels.

Perhaps among the most significant political changes of the colonial period was the introduction of "Indirect rule" which greatly reduced the powers and importance of traditional rulers.⁹ Between 1914 and 1933, as a result of Lugard's new form of political administration, only four traditional rulers - the Alaafin of Oyo, Ooni of Ife, Alake of Abeokuta, and the Awujale of Ijebu-Ode were recognized as sole native authorities in Yoruba land.¹⁰

It is interesting to note that this period covered Fagunwa's stay at Oyo both as a student in St. Andrew's College, Oyo (1926-1929) and as a Schoolmaster in the College's demonstration school. It was also the period when Captain Ross made progressive efforts to resuscitate the lost glory of the Old Oyo Empire.¹¹ At Captain Ross's discretion, the

9. Balogun, K. 1976: op. cit., p. 307.

10. Ibid., p. 308.

11. Atanda, J.A. 1973: The New Oyo Empire
Ibadan University Press, pp. 45-214.

then Alaafin of Oyo, Oba Siyanbola Ladigbolu, became the head of the new Oyo Province, and consequently, the most important paramount ruler in Oyo Province.¹² Not only was the Alaafin the most highly paid Oba, he also had overriding powers on all the oba in his domain. When he was appointed President of the Provincial court of Appeal and, at his command, the Aséyin of Iséyin, was publicly executed at Iséyin market, it dawned on his subjects that the Alaafin had regained his lost imperial cognomen - "Ikú bàbá yèyé" (Death the great and mighty one).

Since Fagunwa was resident in Oyo at this time, he most probably was aware of the immensity of the Alaafin's power. He noted the grandeur and magnificence of his palace and saw them all as noteworthy features of Yoruba socio-political history. Incidentally, Fagunwa was still in Oyo when, during the regime of Ward-Price as Resident, the Alaafin's power depreciated, leading to the total break-up of the empire between 1931 and 1934.¹³ From this period, it became clear

12. Ibid., p.85.

13. Ibid., pp. 249-282

that Yoruba Ọba were ^{gradually} being divested of their autocratic powers.

As can be seen in his novels, there is no doubt that as a keen observer of incidents and events, Fagunwa nostalgically cherished this aspect of Yoruba political life, namely, the monarchical institution. This feeling most probably explains the resplendent reflection of the Yoruba Ọba in various forms in his novels.¹⁴

Another aspect in the socio-economic life of the pre-colonial times was the Yoruba hunter. The existence of vast forest lands in many parts of Yorubaland encouraged hunting. Many of the surrounding forests were full of wild animals which the hunters killed for security and consumption, as well as for sale. A hunter's ability to kill big game like the elephant and the buffalo was greatly cherished. Such a distinguished feat ^{usually led to} the honorary title of "Ọde aperin" (the elephant killer) on any such hunter. Thus it was one of the ambitions of great hunters of old to attain this eminent position.

14. For instance, in the two novels under study, Fagunwa depicts the Yoruba Ọba in various forms on about ten occasions - six times in Ogboju Ode and four times in Igbo Olodumare.

The European slave trade and the Yoruba wars in the pre-colonial times also contributed to making the hunter prominent in the society. For security, many communities depended mainly on the hunters. Thus throughout the period of the wars and for a considerable time afterwards, the hunters were notable figures in the society. They were often known to be men of immense physical strength, and dauntless courage, who could defend their communities in times of danger. They constituted the local army. The community looked up to them as their source of protection against invading army and marauders.

The hunter was famous not only for his physical energy, he was also known for his herbal power. For this he was feared and revered in the community. Ajisafẹ cites one example in Abeokuta in the precolonial times.

...everybody in that district dreaded the man (Sobiyi Ponlade, the Oloriode of Ijemo)... he was a juju man, and if any one should oppose him or act contrarily to his order, he would be killed by his juju.¹⁵

The hunter did not possess only dangerous medicine, he also had medicine with which he could render preventive and

15. Ajisafẹ, A.K. 1924: History of Abeokuta, pp. 188-189.

lucrative assistance whenever his help was required. The Yoruba oral literary tradition is replete with myths and tales of marvellous feats and awe-inspiring exploits of hunters in battle fields and hunting expeditions.¹⁶ Irele has written on this point:

There is a real sense in which the hunter can be said to be a 'given hero' in the Yoruba imagination, as exemplified not only in numerous folktales, but especially, in the Ijala poetry, in the themes of which are specifically organized in relation to the hunters perception of the world of nature, and which express the particular ideal that he pursues, the unique combination of physical and spiritual energy that is the privilege of man in the universal order, and which the traditional image of the hunter represents in the highest degree.¹⁷

There is no doubt that the Yoruba hunter is a significant character both in the literary and practical life of the Yoruba people. Fagunwa himself must have heard about and observed some of the striking attributes of the hunter: his

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16. Lere Paimc's play Ogbori Elemoso is a relevant example of example of such exploits.
17. Irele, A. 1975: Tradition and the Yoruba writer in ODU, No. 11, pp. 75-100.

redoubtable personality, heroism, intrepidity, and herbal prowess. This background then explains the depiction of the Yoruba hunter with his dashing feats in his first two novels.

Socio-Economic Changes in the Colonial Period:

Perhaps among the most outstanding characteristics of the colonial era in the times of Fagunwa was the conspicuous change of values and ideals in the society. This change was a result of the introduction of christianity, Western education and new economic situation. The effects of the advent of christianity into the hinter land are multifarious. But certain aspects are useful to our literary understanding. For instance the establishment of christianity has brought changes into the Yoruba family life, belief system and traditional politics. It has broadened the people's outlook on life, and has greatly influenced the social and spiritual world-view of many christian adherents.

Ayandele relates a critic's view of the impact of christianity on the society:

...that missionary activity was a disruptive force, rocking traditional society to its very foundations, denouncing ordered monogamy, producing disrespectful presumptuous and detribalized children through the mission schools destroying the high moral principles and orderliness of indigenous society through denunciation of traditional religions, without an adequate replacement and transforming the mental outlook of Nigerians in a way that made them imitate European values slavishly, whilst holding in irrational contempt valuable features of traditional culture.¹⁸

This assessment contains many useful points on the effects of christianity on Yoruba traditional society. It is a critical analysis of the many changes christianity has brought into indigenous Yoruba society.

One factor that has had by far the greatest effect on the social, economic and cultural life of the Yoruba since the colonial times is the introduction of Western education. It broadened the Yoruba scope of life and exposed many Yoruba to foreign cultural ideals. As education spread into the Yoruba hinterland, many members of the community saw it as the only key to the mysteries and prosperity of the colonial times. It was a channel to rapid economic development which created the new bourgeois society and opened up countless opportunities

18. Ayandele, E.A. 1966: The Missionary Impact on Modern Nigeria. Longman, p. 329

or social prestige.

The colonial period of Fagunwa saw the gradual transformation of the society's agrarian economy to one of mixed economy. The recruitment for labour in the various sectors of the new administration led to wage earning, salaried posts and the class of technocrats, commercial traders and wealthy cocoa farmers. This colonial period was characterized by a new economic outlook in the society. It heralded the arrival of a new crop of men, distinguished by their wealth, education, ideas, and travel experiences; all of which have created within the society new values, new tastes and new philosophies of life.

In the 1930s and 1940s when Fagunwa wrote his Ògbójú Ode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè and Igbó Olódùmarè respectively, the new crop of men, the new elite, was just growing in the hinterland. They were few in number and were made up of clerks, teachers and junior administrative officers under the colonial government. As stated above, Western education was the only channel to such salaried posts. Western education was to a great extent, established and controlled in Yorubaland by the christian missionaries. Thus most of the educated elite were christians. Since the British colonial administration was

basically christian oriented, christian values which could serve to maintain the ruling class and promote the smooth running of the colonial machinery were encouraged and taught in education institutions. Among such values are fortitude, perseverance, patience, obedience, hardwork, thrift, respect for authority and godliness.

These values are inherent in the hierarchical traditional Yoruba society. They are aspects of the superstructure to maintain and establish the power of the ruling class and also to stabilize the society. Thus the colonial administration employed these values among others to reinforce its power in the society. Fagunwa was a member of the nascent middle class in the colonial society, one of the privileged few. What is Fagunwa's relationship to this society as seen in the structure of his first two novels, Ògbójú Ode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè and Igbó Olódumarè?

Literary Tradition

Before discussing the structure of the novels some knowledge of the literary tradition in which Fagunwa wrote will be illuminating. The period of Fagunwa's early childhood, (1906-1910) fell within the time when peace was gradually returning into many Yoruba communities. There was freedom from fear of warfare, starvation and slave trade. People were beginning to settle down to their works on the farm and they returned home to enjoy a peaceful atmosphere in the evenings. It was this kind of situation which Delano, (1957: 1) nostalgically described when he wrote :

Lí Ọjọ wọn ọn ni, lí àsikò tiwa ayé
rójú, àlàáfíà wà, óúnjẹ pọ

In these days, in our own time, life was pleasant, there was peace, food was plenty.

Obafemi Awolowo's (1968: 6) description of the society during this period is clear and very convincing:

The society into which I was born was an agrarian and peaceful society. There was peace because under the Pax Britanica there was a total ban on intertribal as well as intratribal war, and civil disturbances of any kind and degree were severely suppressed and ruthlessly punished. There was peace because there was unquestioning obedience

to constituted authority. There was peace because the people lived close to nature, and she in her turn was kind and extremely generous to them. And there was peace because the family life was cooperative, integrated and well regulated...

During these times, Fagunwa, like many Yoruba children, of his time, enjoyed several interesting story telling sessions with his parents. His father Joshua Fagunwa, was a talented storyteller. Not only did Daniel Fagunwa enjoy the stories, he also learnt the art of story-telling from his father. For whenever his father was not around, he usually assumed his father's role of teller of tales, to other younger children in the house.¹⁹ Thus for Fagunwa, the love for story narration and capacity for imaginative thinking all spring from his home background.

The ability to develop the mastery of the art must have waxed stronger when as a pupil teacher, he had several story-telling lessons with his pupils. As a school boy and pupil teacher, Fagunwa must have read works of Ajisafẹ (1921) - Enià Soro and Iwé Igbádùn Aiyé, which contain several tales. There is no doubt that works like Bunyan's Pilgrim's Progress

19. Information received from Madam Maria Adeyemi
See Adesigbin, B. 1977 in Yoruba Gbode Vol. 2,
No.2, p.22.

influenced his writing.

As Bamgbose has rightly observed, Fagunwa was quite familiar with literary works in English. These included both original English literary texts as well as those translated from classical Greek Literature. Fagunwa no doubt made use of St. Andrew's College Library which in his days had a copious collection of such works. Fagunwa most probably read many of such works which stimulated his interest and influenced his kind of writing.

Fagunwa and his Society

A study of the structure of the first two novels of D.O. Fagunwa, reveals that Fagunwa identifies himself with the values of the ^{ruling class} in an undisguised fashion. The content, form, and language of these novels, Ogbójú Ode Nínú Igbó rúnmalè and Igbó Olódùmarè depict Fagunwa's relationship to the colonial ^{ruling class}. The small educated elite of which he is a member, is just beginning to form; it owes its existence and establishment to the colonial government which constituted the ruling class in the society. Thus Fagunwa sees himself both as a representative of the nascent ^{elitist} society as well as a spokesman of the colonial authorities that gave him the privilege position

In many parts of the novels Fagunwa sees himself as teacher. He is out to present the values held in high esteem by the colonial society to the up and coming elite. Fagunwa so much endorses the values that he preaches them with a missionary commitment. The novels are full of sermons. Rather than make didacticism an appendage of the novels, it actually constitutes the mainstay of the entire structure. Fagunwa evidently takes sides in his novels, directly and pungently proclaiming his opinion, which incidentally is that of the ruling class. Fagunwa under his Christian influence does this with such enthusiasm that he does not allow the didactic element to arise from the situation and action themselves. He obligatorily furnishes the reader with a ready made missionary morality.

Fagunwa sees himself as a strong admirer of the colonial ruling class. He is so committed to the christian cause that even though he makes abundant use of Yoruba oral traditional materials, he ensures that his materials are carefully chosen such that they are acceptable to the growing elitist christian audience. For instance, as Bamgbose, (1974:11) has observed in the two novels, there is no single record of incantations recited by any of the hunters. In spite of the massive reference to the use of herbal medicine in the novels, Fagunwa in most cases, merely mentions that an incantation is recited. The reader is not presented with a specimen of Yoruba incantations.

Furthermore, when Akaraogun in Ogbójuode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè is becoming apprehensive of meeting Agbako, in a face-to-face combat, he quickly recites an ogèdè so that Agbako may be cast into the thicket (p. 12). And towards the end of his second journey into Igbó Irúnmalè, Akaraogun attempts to cure his beautiful hostess of a serious attack of headache, by chanting incantations (p. 39). Much as readers would have loved to know such incantations, Fagunwa, unlike many Yoruba modern writers, deprives his readers of this opportunity.²⁰ Fagunwa would not like to offend his elitist christian audience which sees Yoruba incantations as devilish and heathenish.

To Fagunwa the traditional society has been influenced by the colonial administration. The power and prestige of the monarchical institution has been greatly reduced. The stability of the society has been disturbed by foreign influence. Who will bring back the stability? In the traditional society, the hunter was a veritable source of solace. But with the incursion of colonialism, a new leadership was emerging, the educated elite. The educated elite who were beneficiaries of colonial missionary education increased in number and influence in the society. They were being accorded greater regard and recognition in the society. This social group constituted the nascent bourgeois middle class, and identified itself with the ideology of the colonial ruling class. Fagunwa was a member of this middle class. Thus his themes and stories are carefully

20. For instance, Olu Owolabi's novels, Oriade kii sun ta and Eni Olorun ko pa contain adequate specimens of Yoruba incantations.

chosen from the oral literary tradition, so that they will be acceptable to both his colonial missionary audience and the growing elitist class.

Structure of the Novels

The novels are made up of numerous self-contained tales and incidents, strung together without any conspicuous narrative link. The structure of the novels is like that of the folktale. There is a task to be accomplished, the road to this accomplishment is fraught with problems and difficulties. The task as seen in the structure of Ogbójuode for instance, has to do with the peace of the society. The peace of the society is disturbed, there is need for a saviour. The society looks for a saviour who is mandated to find a solution. He encounters tremendous difficulties, in the end he succeeds. But rather than a single straight forward story, it is a concatenation of stories loosely strung together, this accounts for the novels' static, episodic plot. Thus in Ogbojuode, the story is concerned with the hero, Akaraogun, who makes three separate journeys into the forest. Each journey is a story in its own right, and complete without reference to the other, except accidental and occasional references to characters and incidents in the previous journey.

In Ogbójuode, for instance, Agbakò vanishes after the combat with Akara Ogun during the second journey. He surfaces during the journey to Okè Iáńgbódó and is destroyed unceremoniously. Furthermore, each of the journeys consists of a series of episodes.

the team of hunters at Okè Láńgbòdò. (pp. 5-71). It also contains six separate stories narrated by Iragbeje at Okè Láńgbòdò, from pages 75 to 99. Igbó Olódùmarè is made up of thirteen episodes and four separate stories. Many of the episodes in Ogbójúode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè are either verbal encounters with fairies, or physical combats with supernatural characters. On many occasions the story stagnates, an example is Akaraogun's stay in a town of fairies where several attempts were made on the Oba's life. In Igbó Olódùmarè, the story stalls exceedingly at the point Olowoaiye climbs a tree and can no longer come down. The only link between the episodes is the theme of adventure: the hero frees himself from one adventure and after a short while gets involved in another.

Similarly, there is in the form a lack of forward movement particularly in the adventure of the hero. He is a vagrant, wandering from place to place. In Ogbójúode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè, Akaraogun the hero rambles from situation to situation, settles down in a place and moves when forced by circumstances. Thus when the story reaches Iragbeje's house in Ogbójúode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè, it comes to a standstill, and for the next thirty pages (pp. 69-99)

all the hunters sat down listening to stories! Similarly in Igbó Olodumarè from the end of the hero's victory over Ahjànú ibèrù, (the fearsome spirit) on p.41 till the departure from "Baba Onirungbon Yẹukẹ" p.130, no strikingly progressive action takes place. The story stagnates and instead of a forward moving record of action and incidents, all we have, are self contained stories and didactic comments. Why does Fagunwa adopt this form? Is the rambling, episodic form designed to achieve a literary end, that is, to prolong the story so that his literary effort will reach an acceptable length? Or is Fagunwa's goal directed towards achieving a didactic purpose? Barber (1984: 13) upholds both views. She writes:

These formal characteristics could be seen as simply the result of Fagunwa's attempt to use traditional materials - to string together, that is, a lot of stories that were originally independent in attempt to meet the externally-imposed requirement of the length suitable to a book. But Fagunwa had another reason for using this form... He used this form because it was well-suited to his didactic purpose. His strong and consistent aim... is to draw a moral from every encounter and every incident.²¹

21. Barber, K. 1984: Style and Ideology in Fagunwa and Okediji Ife monographs on Literature and Criticism pp. 11-12.

Barber's first suggestion is probably true in view of the fact that by the time of Fagunwa's writing there had been laid down standards on what should constitute an English novel. For instance, Forster (1927) stipulates that a novel should contain 50,000 words.²² Perhaps Fagunwa was aware of the emphasis on the volume of a novel, and strove to attain that standard. But his novels' volume did not reach that mark, yet they were published. Similarly the loose, episodic structure is characteristic of all his novels. These facts suggest that the rationale for the characteristic form goes beyond mere desire to satisfy a technical requirement.

Barber's second suggestion is to a great extent true. For the didactic purpose is one of the major factors that determine the form of his writing. The desire to present his moral ideas pervades the entire structure of the novels. Fagunwa employs every means at his disposal to achieve this end, as borne out in his method of narration and character presentation. His change to the autobiographical technique

22. Forster, E.M. 1927: Aspects of the Novel, Edward Arnold.

in Igbó Olódùmarè is to achieve a moral purpose. Characters are introduced into the novels with the sole aim of presenting Fagunwa's moral message. It is the main purpose of creating the sages in both novels - Iragbeje in Ogbójúode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè and Baba Onirungbon Yẹukẹ in Igbó Olódùmarè. In the former, Iragbeje spends seven days to comment and sermonize on various topics like child care, importance of children to parents, child education, human excesses, pride, humility etc.

In Igbó Olódùmarè, Baba Onirungbon yẹukẹ lectures for three consecutive days on various topics like faithfulness, heroism, selfishness, envy, jealousy, lasciviousness, true love, human insatiable nature, infidelity and perfidy among women. In the same novel, the purpose of the visit to Iku's (Death) house is to open an avenue for more sermons. Thus Iku lectures on various things - his own personal destructive power, causes of human deaths like inadequate personal and environmental hygiene, carelessness when crossing a busy road, the sin of parents and grandparents, profligacy carelessness about injuries and minor ailments, the perfect will of God, hypocrisy, licentiousness, pride, avarice and rebellion.

In each novel the hero's mother appears in miraculous circumstances to moralise on topics like determination, love and co-operation between husband and wife, truthfulness and characteristics of the ideal wife. Themes are on some occasions introduced to provide an opportunity for moralising. Akaraogun is still talking about his father's marital background when he suddenly changes gear and picks up the theme of marriage, a theme that reverberates frequently in both novels. Akaraogun discusses the need for beauty, commonsense and good moral behaviour in a wife. Similarly in Igbó Olódùmarè, the first narrator who merely acts as recorder to the narrator proper, is introduced into the story in the opening chapter, brooding over his father's death. His extensive meditations provide opportunity for him to moralize on the need for children to show gratitude for parental care and accepting the will of God with fortitude and resignation. These examples suggest that to Fagunwa, the moral element is the real substance, the story itself is a mere vehicle for the moral.

As a result of the importance Fagunwa attaches to moral teaching in the novels, there is always the tendency for the story to move away from the immediate narrative

situation to more general themes. In the encounter between Olowoaiye and Eşukekoreode, the fight has barely gone half-way when Olowoaiye starts to blow a whistle commenting on various things about the world. He sings about God the overall creator, the fountain of success and victory, his omnipotence and omniscient attributes. The fight is not raised to the desired climax and ends rather abruptly (pp. 19-20).

In the great combat between Olowoaiye and Anjõnu-Iberu which to a great extent is the most striking episode in Igbó Olódùmarè (pp. 32-41), there is a pause to give the wrestlers some rest. It is during this period that the wives of the two combatants bring food to their husbands. Fagunwa uses the opportunity of this brief pause to reflect on the importance of wifely duty and from there he moves on to various other things:

Báyì' ní àwọ̀n méjèèjì ẹ̀ tì wọ̀n n tọ́jú
 ọ̀kọ̀ wọ̀n, nítọ́rí ìtọ́jú ọ̀kọ̀ ní pàtàkì iṣẹ́
 obinrin si ọ̀kọ̀. Igbà tí inú tọ̀kọ̀taya bá
 dùn ni wọ̀n tó lè gbádùn ọ̀mọ̀ wọ̀n. Sù
 ní baba ati iyá ànfà ní, òmùgọ̀ ẹ̀nià ní
 n wí pé sùru òun pọ̀jù, nítọ́rí sùru kò
 ní òpin. Kí tọ̀kọ̀taya mọ̀ pé, bí sùru tí
 wọ̀n bá mú fún ara wọ̀n lóni ní bá ju tí

àná lọ, awọn yó ni owó, àwọn yó ní ọmọ,
 awọn yó sì ní àlà fià tíí ẹe olúbori owó
 ati ọmọ. Jẹ kí awọn ènià máa rẹ ọ jẹ,
 mú sùru fún wọn, ẹe iwọ mọ nínú ara rẹ
 pé, wọn bẹrẹ iṣubú ni eléyì .ni. Bí
 èniyàn bá rẹ ọ jẹ, tí iwọ si ẹe bí ẹni
 pé iwọ kò tilẹ mọ, iwọ ti gbé eléyíí ní
 sí inú ikòkò gbígbóná, ẹrí ọkàn rẹ yó
 si máa ko iná mọ. Ẹ̀gbọ̀n bí iwọ kò
 bá mú sùúrù tó tí iwọ n bá Olóríbúrukú
 èniyàn bínú pọ, on o kó iwà òmùgò ràn ọ,
 òun á sì mọ pé ohun tí on ẹe dùn ọ, on
 a gbé ẹ̀wù igbéraga wọ sí èjìkà, bẹ̀ ní
 on kò ní irètí ati lọ sí iwájú mọ ní
 tirẹ̀, nígbà tí non bá si kó ibànújẹ bá
 ọ lónì , a ẹe bẹ̀ẹ̀ dí ọ lówọ ilọsíwájú
 ehin ọla. (p.37)

Thus the two of them behaved and they took
 care of their husbands, because care of the
 husband is an important wifely duty. It is
 when husband and wife are happy that they
 can enjoy their children. Patience is the
 father and mother of goodness, it is a
 foolish person that claims he is overpatient,
 because patience has no limit. Let husband
 and wife know that if their patience today
 is more than the one of the previous day,
 then they will have money, they will have
 children and they will have peace which
 supersedes both money and children. Let
 people cheat you, have patience with them,
 after all, you know within yourself, that,
 that is the beginning of their downfall.
 If someone is cheating you and you behave

as if you are not aware of it, you have put that person in a heated pot and his conscience will continue to heat his state of mind more and more. But if your patience is not enough, and you are equally angry with the unlucky person, he will transfer his foolishness unto you, and he will know that what he has done pains you, he then wears a garment of pride on his shoulder, whereas he has no hope of progress, when today he affects you with sorrow, he thereby obstructs your future progress.

The main story has been abandoned. Fagunwa raises various ideas and weaves each idea into his reflections. At first, the focus is on the importance of wifely duty, a point which the author considers indispensable for marital joy, wealth and peace in the home. This leads to the opposite - lack of patience which can be instrumental to sorrow and backwardness in life.

As the reader goes on, he becomes so absorbed in the moral message that he forgets about the combat and its final outcome. Even though Fagunwa's description of the combat is very exciting and dramatic, for him, however the excruciating scene is not as important as the moral message that it is intended to evince. This tendency to move away from the main narrative situation is so common in both novels that it can hardly be called digression. When one

compares the story element of the main narrative with the rate and frequency of moving away from the narrative situation, to moralize, the latter is by far greater. The constancy of this movement away from the narrative situation increases the rambling episodes. Fagunwa chooses this form as it suits the role he intends to serve.

Fagunwa does not only move away from the narrative situations to moralize, he creates episodes to give room for this purpose. In Ògbójúode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalẹ̀ (pp. 17-20) Akaraogun is extricated from Agbako's prison only to enter Ilu Èèmò (Strange City). All the inhabitants of the town except one are deaf, dumb and blind. They operate normal day to day activities, like marketing and holding court sessions. The only normal person Akara Ogun meets is a woman. The woman whose name is Iwàpẹ̀lẹ̀ (pleasant manners) discloses the background of the town:

Iwàpẹ̀lẹ̀ ni orukọ mi, Èèmò sì ni orúkọ
 ilú yíí; ilú iyà ati ẹgbin ni; ilú wọbià
 àti írira; ilú ojú kòkòrò àti olè; ilú
 ìjà àti asọ ilú ikú àti àrùn - ilú ẹlẹ̀şẹ̀
 pátápátá gbàà ni. Ní àkókò kan rí, àwọn
 ará ilú yì. dá ẹşẹ̀ búburú kan - ẹşẹ̀ ná
 burú gidigidi: ...Şùgbón Ẹlẹ̀dàáwọn rí
 wọn láti ọrun wá, nítorí işẹ̀ gbogbo tí

ènla bá n̄ še ni Ọlọrun n̄ ri, èrò gbogbo
tí ó ba si wà nínú ni Ọlọrun mọ. (pp. 17-20)

My name is Iwapẹlẹ and the name of this city is Filth. It is a place of suffering and contempt, a city of greed and contumely, a city of envy and of thievery, a city of fights and wrangles, a city of death and diseases - a veritable city of sinners. Once upon a time, the people of this town committed a most atrocious crime; a very evil deed it was... But their maker saw them from heaven, for all acts of mankind are observed by God and there is nothing hidden from him. (Soyinka's translation pp. 30-31)²³

From the description of the 'city of filth' we have a glimpse of Fagunwa's intention, to condemn sin. He wants readers to know that, a town that is full of various sins will see the wrath of God. Thus Fagunwa's creation of the town is intended to bring out the message that sinners shall not go unpunished.

The way the novels come to an end shows the appropriateness of this form to Fagunwa's didactic purpose. As pointed out earlier, the story telling sessions at Iragbeje and Baba onirungbon Yẹukẹ's houses bring an important characteristics of the books to limelight - giving the

23. Soyinka, W. and Fagunwa, D.O. 1968:
The Forest of A Thousand Daemons
Nelson, pp. 30-31.

novels a kind of structural climax. It is also true from the thematic point of view. By the time the narrative reaches the house of the sages the story becomes immobilised, giving room for a real feast of moralising. The sages enjoy a seemingly limitless opportunity to talk as much as they like. They smuggle in stories (which often were not appropriate) to illustrate their moral themes. The stories are interpolated with straight forward sermons and exhortations. It is at this point that the thematic consummation of the story is attained.

Fagunwa often rounds off with an air of satisfaction, as he consolidates his moral. In Ògbójúṣṣé Nínú

Igbó Irúnmalẹ̀ he states:

Ènyin ọkúnrin ati obínrin ní ilẹ̀ Yorubá
 Ọgbón ọlọgbón kì jẹ́ kí a pe àgbà ní
 wèrè, ẹ́ fi ìtàn inú ìwé yì ẹ́ àríkọgbón.
 Olúkúlùkù yin ni ó ni ìṣoro tíẹ̀ lati bá
 pàdé nínú aiyé, Olúkúlùkù ni ó ní Òkè
 Láńgbèdó tíẹ̀ lati lọ, Olúkúlùkù ni ó sì
 ní ìdínà tíẹ̀ níwájú, bí dídùn tí n bẹ́
 nínú aiyé, bẹ́ ní kíkòrò n bẹ́, bí òní dùn
 ọ̀lẹ̀ kòrò, bí ọ̀lẹ̀ tún kòrò ọ̀tunla lẹ̀ dàbí
 oyin: kọ́kọ́rọ́ aiyé kò sí lẹ́wọ́ ẹ̀nikan...
 (pp. 101-102)

You men and women of Yorubaland, the wisdom of others teaches us not to think an elder a madman - put the story of this book to wise use. Each of you meets with difficulties in the world, each of you has his Mount Langbodo to attain, each of you has obstacles in front of him, for as there is sweet, so there is sour in this world, if today is good, tomorrow may be bitter, if tomorrow is bitter, the day after may be like honey. The key to this world is in the hands of no man.

(Şoyinka translation p. 139)²⁴

The characteristic air of authority and unabashed enthusiasm with which he concludes his novels confirm that Fagunwa deliberately employs the episodic narrative style as a vehicle for his moral ideas.

Fagunwa's Didacticism

The preponderant didactic stance of Fagunwa has been recognized by literary scholars like Beier, and Bamgboşe, among others. Barber (1984: 19-24) focuses on Fagunwa's didacticism. She argues that Fagunwa's didactic intention is the motor force of his writing. To Barber, Fagunwa's style, characterization, theme and language in Ogbójúode

²⁴. Ibid., p. 139.

Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè and Igbo Olódùmarè are "determined and vitiated by his desire to moralise". She writes:

His strong and consistent aim - which gives the stories a kind of artificial unity - is to draw a moral from every encounter and every incident... Fagunwa uses every means at his disposal to present his moral ideas...

Concluding her assessment of Fagunwa's language, she asserts categorically:

The monotony of the language reveals more than anything else, that the real *raison d'être* of the stories is to draw a sermon.

All Barber is saying is that for Fagunwa, didacticism is an end, his style, characterization, and language are means to achieve that end. From the point of view of genetic structuralism, Barber's assertion is a specious one. Her argument is unsatisfactory because it is based on analysis of text alone. Her claim is not holistic because it takes no cognizance of extraneous factors that are closely connected with the artefact. Barber's argument is from the point of view of literary sociology unconvincing because it fails to evince the social significance of Fagunwa's didacticism. Barber's disputation does not provide an adequate answer to an all-important question: of what

value is Fagunwa's unabashed didacticism to our understanding of the society?

An attempt to understand Fagunwa's moral ideas in isolation will only result in what Scholes calls fragmentation of knowledge.²⁵ For, from the point of view of sociology of literature, a writer's work cannot be treated in isolation. As Goldmann rightly maintains, 'all things are both the result and the causes of causes', thus to understand the whole, a knowledge of the parts is essential and it is equally impossible to know the parts without referring to the whole. Thus to understand the rationale for the prominence of didacticism in Fagunwa's work, we must understand his relationship with his society, for as a member of his society, his ideas and attitude do not exist in isolation. They are inevitably conditioned by the social, cultural, and economic background from which he springs. Thus on the creation of the ideas in his novels, he has brought the unique combination of his own personality and environment. A knowledge of his life and environment can therefore shed useful light on the ideas expressed in his works, for certain ideas which he expresses in his works

25. Scholes, R. 1974: *Structuralism in Literature*. Yale University Press. p.1.

can acquire their real meaning for us and can be fully understood, when they are seen as integral parts of his life and mode of behaviour.

From our knowledge of Fagunwa's life, the missionary morality that pervades his works is a signification of certain traits in his own personality. It is our conjecture that certain personality traits in Fagunwa have had significant influence on his role as an artist. Theories of human personality suggest that a person's personal attributes are predictive of his actions. Personality, which is the sum total of the distinctive characteristics of an individual, often reveals that the individual has characteristics in common with other people, and that each individual is distinguished from all others on the basis of his unique combination of these characteristics and the degree to which he manifests them. A person's personality inevitably affects his thought patterns and actions. Fagunwa is not an exception. Fagunwa has been described as a man of impeccable moral character. His son Femi Fagunwa bears testimony:

Father was indeed, a remarkable man. In a nutshell, he was an exceptionally humble, kind, and selfless person - "kind almost to a fault" as someone put it. Though the point at which kindness becomes a fault largely is of a subjective determination. The statement does show that his kindness was probably more than is usually encountered.²⁶

This excerpt provides very useful information about certain attributes of Fagunwa's personality - humility, kindness, and selflessness. An awareness of these characteristics deepens our knowledge about the man himself. His humility suggests modesty and temperance in views or opinions. He was a man of mild temper, a man who was never extremist in his opinions, and he showed some tendency towards submissiveness. His kindness is indicative of certain beneficency, helpfulness, and propriety in nature. It is suggestive of a man given to conformity with established principles, rules or customs. These characteristics are fundamental to our understanding of his relationship with his society.

These personality traits provide clues to our understanding of his role as a artist. He sees himself as an instructor on the moral ideals of his society. As a man in

26. See article on Fagunwa by his son Femi Fagunwa in Sunday Express, December 10, 1965, p.10.

conformity with traditionally acknowledged standards of behaviour, Fagunwa preaches what he believes. Fagunwa was a beneficiary of the christian oriented Western Education, one of the privileged few that constituted the growing elitist class in his society. The inter tribal wars in Yoruba land had ended and the British policy of pacification was gaining prominence. The world view of the war era 'might is right' had been displaced by a new one, "knowledge is power". The traditional world view of communalism, consideration and care for others, humanitarianism, obedience to, and respect for constituted authority were in conformity with those of the christian missionaries. The traditional Yoruba world view of moral excellence was acceptable to the colonial masters because it was a useful means of maintaining the status quo as well as promoting the smooth running of the colonial machinery. Fagunwa endorses this world view and articulates it pungently in his novel. His didacticism is thus an artistic representation of the extent of his conformity with the renewed world view of moral excellence in the society. Thus Fagunwa's didacticism is not an end in itself, rather he sees it as an effective means of promoting orderliness and peace in

the society. As George Orwell (1953) asserts, that 'no work of art is genuinely free from political bias; Fagunwa is not an exception. His didacticism is a means of ensuring socio-political stability of the colonial ruling class.

Depiction of Traditional Values

As previously noted, Fagunwa's posture in his first two novels is two-edged. As much as he sets out to preach the ideology of the colonial ruling class, he tries to present a picture of the Yoruba traditional values to his elitist audience. Thus in the novels, he employs materials from the oral tradition to create characters, situations, and incidents to achieve this secondary goal. Among the values Fagunwa attempts to present are the monarchical institution, Yoruba hunter's heroism, oratory and language. One of the values which Fagunwa seems to cherish most is the Yoruba ideology of sacred kingship. Ogundipe-Leslie (1976: 431), among others, has pointed out the feudal hierarchical society reflected in Ogbójúọ̀de Nínú Igbó Irúnmalẹ̀. She writes:

Through the incidents, the commentaries, or "emblematic" speeches of the creatures, the iwins and vignettes of their social life, the writer obliquely reflects and comments on Yoruba society which is usually the normative monarchic and feudal one which has for us a familiar, institutional structure: the king, his chiefs, the babalawos, the freemen and slaves. These micro Yoruba societies in the world of the creatures, are in fact commentaries on Yoruba social life...²⁷

As Ogundipe-Leslie rightly observes, one of the aspects of Yoruba society that Fagunwa covertly recreates in both novels, is the political organization of precolonial Yoruba society, particularly the role and status of the traditional ruler. In both novels, not less than ten incidents are imaginatively created to illustrate this aspect of the society. What seems probably to have attracted Fagunwa's interest most is the dignity accorded many Yoruba paramount rulers.

During Akaraogun's first journey to Igbó Irúnmalè, he finds himself in the court of Olórí igbó (the head of all fairies). What he regards as an ordinary tree is in essence the abode and palace of the king of fairies. Fagunwa does not give a pictorial view of the palace

²⁷. See Akinjogbin, I.A. and Ekemode eds. op. cit., p.431.

structure, he leaves this till another incident (p.69). But from the short account of the Olórí igbó episode, Fagunwa clearly portrays the importance and dignity of Yoruba Obas and the liveliness and gaiety that pervade Yoruba palaces on social or ceremonial occasions. The portrayal here suggests that Fagunwa transfers the hierarchies in Yoruba social structure into other realms as if they were universal structures. Thus in the fairy world where Akaraogun suddenly finds himself, the supremacy of the Yoruba Oba is reflected. For instance, the name of the head fairy is Olórí igbó, which virtually means father and lord of the wilderness.²⁸

The preliminary dancing and jubilation before Olórí-igbó's arrival is characteristic of day-to-day life in many palaces in Yorubaland. Olórí-igbó's citations by his chanter is a re-creation of the typical performance in Yoruba palaces. Olórí igbo's response to the citation reveals the oba's dignified position. The sound of his voice is distinct and dignifying. It commands perfect silence. It is an illustration of the regard and respect

28. This title is incidentally relevant to the Yoruba Oba, who is sometimes referred to as "Olórí Oko" (head of the farmstead).

accorded Yoruba obas, when addressing the community on important occasions. Furthermore, Oloriigbo sees what his dancing subjects cannot see, until he calls their attention to the heavy dangling object on the tree above. This gives an insight into a peculiar quality of many Yoruba obas. No one is allowed to walk straight to the palace and sit on the throne without the oba's express permission and knowledge. Even though Akaraogun does it inadvertently, his action has been seen as the height of insult, the penalty for which is death. This then is an artistic rendering of the Yoruba world view of the sacredness and supremacy of the Yoruba Oba in traditional society.

The presentation of the Oba of the iwins in Ogbòjú Ode Ninú Igbó Irúnmalè (pp. 27-37) is different from the way Olórí igbó is depicted. The atmosphere is more human. Many incidents that occur during Akaraogun's sojourn among them affirm the supremacy of obaship. The subterranean revolts and insurrections against the king are indications of the depreciating position of the oba. It is a portrayal of the diminishing political status of the traditional ruler in the society in the 1940s.

The creation of Ògòngò baba eye is weird and unnatural. He has a long, strong and sturdy-pair of legs, an elongated wire-like neck and a human head. These features distinguish him from his subject birds. Ojòlá Ibínú in Igbó Olódumare who is the sovereign head of all the snakes of the world, is tremendously huge. He has a great booming voice and a human head. His political set-up includes a police force, and a formidable security system. Fagunwa's portrayal here is a signification of some of the administrative innovations of the colonial era. On the whole, Fagunwa's imaginative recreations paint a picture of the Yoruba conception of the sovereignty of the traditional Oba in Yoruba society.

Another aspect of Yoruba social values which Fagunwa reveals in his novels is the image of the Yoruba hunter. There is no doubt that Fagunwa is fascinated by the role and position of the Yoruba hunter in his time. Irele (1974:82) has most succinctly interpreted the role of the hunter in Fagunwa's works. He says:

The tremendous adventures of Fagunwa's hunters, who go through trials and dangers in which they must justify and affirm their human essence. The very choice of hunter as the central figure in Fagunwa's principal novels and in the human scheme of his narratives is of great importance, for the hunter represents the ideal of manhood in traditional Yoruba society...²⁹

In the first two novels of Fagunwa, the Yoruba hunter is given so much prominence that the two novels can meaningfully be summarized as: "Itàn àwọn ògbójúṣe nínú igbó irúnmalẹ̀ atí nínú Igbó Olódùmarè" (The story of brave hunters' exploits in the forest of a thousand daemons and the forest of God).

Thus Fagunwa consciously weaves into the structure of his first two novels, some salient qualities and attributes of the Yoruba hunter. In many cases, Fagunwa does not give a vivid portrait of his hunter-characters. He leaves the reader to make deductions from the names, activities and utterances of such characters. In Ògbójúṣe Nínú Igbó Irúnmalẹ̀, the hunter is the hero-narrator. His very name, Akaraogun, (Compound of Spells) is symptomatic of his herbal power. He says of himself:

²⁹. Irele, A. op. cit., p.82.

Akàràòògùn ni mi nítótó bí orukọ mi ti
 ri na ni emi papa rí, oşó kò lè jẹ mí,
 àjẹ kò lè pa mi lára, elebòlógùn kò si
 lè ri mi gbé şè. (p.49)

I am indeed Akaraogun, compound of spells;
 even as my name is, so am I. I am no
 morsel for the sorcerer, no witch can harm
 me, no prodigal-with-sacrifice dealer-in-
 charms can find a way to touch me.

(Şoyinka's translation p.71)

On many occasions during the exploit, Akaraogun proves his
 worth as a powerful hunter with redoubtable herbal
 authority.

But it is in Fagunwa's presentation of Kàkó in
Ogbójuode Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè that we have the best example
 of hunter as a doughty man of valour. Fagunwa portrays
 him as a distinguished character both in his physical
 features and in his demonstration of his enormous power
 and courage. Fagunwa's physical description of him is
 short and straight forward:

Kàkó jé arẹwà ẹ̀niá Ó sígbọ̀nlẹ̀, ẹ̀nu
 ẹ̀jìkà rẹ̀ sókè ni ó fi ga ju gbogbo wa
 lẹ... (p.62)

Kàkó is a most handsome man, tall and lanky; he was taller than the rest of us by a head at least.

(Şoyinka's translation p.87)

It is not only in height that Kako surpasses all the others, he distinguishes himself in the tireless energy, fearlessness, and sanguinary temperament with which he accomplishes the tasks before him.

The efficacy of Yoruba traditional medicine is aptly demonstrated. This is illustrated in the presentation of Akaraogun's father, Olowoaiye, in Ogbójúọ̀de Nínú Igbó Irúnmalẹ̀. Akaraogun proudly declares his father's herbal wealth. He says:

Ọ̀dẹ̀ ni baba tí ó bi mí í ẹ̀, Ológun sí
 ni pẹ̀lú. Baba mi ní ẹ̀gbẹ̀rún àdó atọ̀ rẹ̀
 sí jẹ̀ ẹ̀gbẹ̀rin, onde sí jẹ̀ ẹ̀gbẹ̀ta.
 Otàlúgba sígídì ní mbẹ̀ ní ile wà ọ̀sanyìn
 ibẹ̀ kò sí ẹ̀ sí fi ẹ̀nu sọ; à̀njònnú níf' má sọ
 ilé de baba mi bí ọ̀n kò bá sí ní ilé,
 nítorí kò sí ẹ̀ni tí wọ̀ ilé rẹ̀ lẹ̀hìn rẹ̀
 ewọ̀ ní (p.2)

My own father was a hunter, he also was a great one for medicine and spells. He had a thousand powder gourdlets, eight hundred ato and his amulets numbered six hundred. Two hundred and sixty incubi lived in that house and the birds of divination were without number. It was the spirits who guarded the house when he was away, and no one dared enter that house when my father was absent - it was unthinkable.

(Şoyinka's translation p.9)

The description of Olowoaiye's herbal prowess, immediately produces terrible fear. It portrays Olowoaiye as a powerful hunter-herbalist, whose house conjures awe and terror.

The description is no doubt exaggerated, it is an illustration of the abundance of traditional medicine in the precolonial and early colonial Yoruba society.

Fagunwa's depiction of traditional medicine as a social value is not restricted to the terrifying and dangerous agglomeration of evil charms. He broadens out and goes further to show deeper things about the Yoruba hunter. Thus Akaraogun in a categorical affirmation of his father's authority in the use of charms says in Igbó

Olódumarè: (p.5)

Oníṣègùn ni baba tó bí mi ṣe babalawo ni pèlú. Ogùn kún ilé wa dé ẹnu... Ẹni tí ó ni wárápá, baba mi wo wárápá fún un, ẹni ti o ní sòbìyà, baba mi wo sòbìyà rẹ sà, okẹaimọye àwọn adétẹ ni ó si sọ di gbajúmọ nínú ilé wa. Baba mi fi ìyà jẹ sànpònná, ó fi àbùkù kan òkè ilẹ́ ó bá làkùrègbé lórúkọ jẹ inú rirun di èrò ẹhin, orífífọ di ẹni kékeré; ẹ in didùn kò lè sọrọ, jẹdíjẹdí dáke minimini, ibà n rìn tìrònú tìrònú, ìgbẹ ọrìn doríkodò, kúrúnà n sọkún, egbo n posé, ìfọn fa ojú ro. Otútù sì n kánu

My father is a powerful herbalist. He is also a notable diviner, our house is full of various kinds of medicine. And the epileptics were cured by my father, and those who suffered from guinea worm were cured likewise, and thousands of lepers became healthy people in our house. And my father punished smallpox, and attacked malnutrition; he spoiled the reputation of rheumatism, and turned stomach pain into a pauper; and headache became a helpless child, and backache was speechless; cough went into hiding and pneumonia fled; the tiny itching worms kept dead silent and fever was lost in thought; dysentery bent its head, the sore wept and the stomach ulcer was disgusted; the rash wrinkled its brow and the cold cried for help.³⁰
(Uli Beier's translation in Introduction to African Literature (p.190))

30. Beier, U. ed. 1970 Introduction to African Literature. Heinemann Education Publications pp. 190-191

Fagunwa's personification and astonishing humour in this excerpt has been recognized by Beier among others.³¹ But language use is not the goal of this piece. Rather it is a declaration of Olowoaiye's supremacy in the knowledge and application of traditional medicine. It is a pointer to one of the most cherished traditional values in Fagunwa's time - possession and knowledge of traditional medicine for curative purposes. Fagunwa's depiction of this phenomenon is detailed and copious. The description of how Olowoaiye effectively subdues the diseases may be exaggerated, yet it reveals the Yoruba people's belief in the prophylactic and therapeutic qualities of Yoruba traditional medicine.

As already noted, Fagunwa's moral concern supersedes every other objective in his novels. Thus his depiction of the Yoruba hunter is not total. It is a partial reflection of the hunter in Yoruba cultural setting. To a great extent, only a partial view of the hunter is depicted - the hunter's encounter in the jungle. The role and importance of the hunter as a source of security and

³¹. Ibid., p. 190.

protection to his society is almost totally neglected. This partial reflection becomes noticeable when one compares this aspect of Fagunwa's story with Adebayo Faleti's depiction of the Yoruba hunter in Ogun Awitélé.³²

In Ogun Awitélé, Faleti's depiction is very stimulating. It portrays the Yoruba hunter as a doughty warrior, an unerring marksman, and a dependable source of protection in the society. The narrative form in Fagunwa's novels exposes the hunter to rather too many unpleasant experiences. The result is that in many situations in the novel, the hunter proves his worth as a man of action. In other instances, he is left a vagrant, a loafer and/or a helpless character.

Furthermore, Fagunwa uses some other activities of characters in the novels to depict certain values of the traditional Yoruba society. One of such values is sportsmanship. A particularly notable sport which the traditional Yoruba society lauds and extols is wrestling. Not only is wrestling one of the most popular games in the society, it is also a significant aspect in many important traditional festivals.³³

32. Faleti, A. 1965: Ogun Awitélé, O.U.P.

33. Wrestling features prominently during the Olooku and Onimoka festivals in Okuku and Qfa respectively among others.

The ability to wrestle is one of the convincing proofs of masculine power valued in the traditional Yoruba society. Many hunters' tales are replete with cut-throat wrestling encounters with powerful dewilds and spirits during various hunting expeditions. Yoruba traditional wrestling is often an exhilarating sport, action packed, and dramatic. It is usually a crowd puller. Fagunwa's depiction of wrestling in his first two novels is no less so.

Within the episodic structure of the novels, Fagunwa in four instances creatively presents circumstances that inevitably end in forcible display of physical superiority. The duration of the Akaraogun - Agbako and Kako-Agbako wrestlings in Ogbójúḡḡe Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè is short, but the fight is vigorous. The wrestling encounters in Igbó Olódumarè are longer, more energy-sapping and fascinating. In the wrestling encounter between Olowoaiye and Eṣukeke-reode, in Igbó Olódumarè, Fagunwa carefully sets the stage for the duel. First, there is an initial war of words. The furious exchange of words arouses and heightens the temper and anger of both parties. It escalates till it finally issues forth in violent physical confrontation.

Olowoaiye's retort to Eṣukekereode's haughty and insulting statement is worth quoting:

...Eṣukekereode, máse gbàgbé pé eiyẹ ju
 ẹiyẹ ènià ju ènià ọdẹ ju ọdẹ - emi ni mo
 wi fún ọ, emi jù wọn lọ, emi kii ẹ ẹgbẹ
 wọn, ẹgbẹ baba wọn ni emi n ẹ, onigberaga
 ni ọ, iwọ ẹbọra kekere inú ọgán, iwọ Eṣu
 kekere ode, ng kí í ẹ ẹgbẹ iyá nlá iyá
 rẹ, kí lo já mó, ẹiọ rẹ lẹmeje... (p.16)

Esu kekereode, do not forget that bird
 surpasses bird, man excels man, hunter
 outclasses hunter, I tell you I am above
 them. I am not of their class I am of
 their father's grade. You are a haughty
 creature you diminutive spirit from the
 ant-hill, you Eṣukekereode, I am not of
 your great grandmother's class. What
 are you up to? Contempt on you seven
 times...

Olowoaiye must have been fuming with anger as he utters the last words. For Eṣukekereode, it is simply impossible to stomach such vituperations. The violent combat is the answer. Thus the preparatory challenging words before the wrestlings in Igbó Olódùmaré are not only exciting and entertaining, they follow a natural and logical sequence akin to real situations in Yoruba traditional society.

One other important cultural value in Yoruba traditional society is oratory. Most comments on oral tradition in African literature often tend to concentrate on content - the proverbs, stories, histories etc - to the total neglect of the art of oratory itself. Oratory involves the practice of persuasive public speaking that embodies nobility and timelessness in subject matter, the logical arrangement of the ideas, excellence in diction and composition, skill, fervour and forcefulness in delivery.³⁴

Oratory was a highly valued art in traditional Yoruba culture³⁵ and even today, it is a feature of predominantly oral cultures. In Yoruba traditional discourse, how something is said is as important as what is said. The Yoruba cherish public utterances that are pungently and logically presented; such utterances must contain excellent diction - proverbs, aphorisms, maxims, allusions and anecdotes all

34. Oratory has been classified into four major categories. There is the forensic or legal oratory which is practised in the law courts, the deliberative oratory often used in formulating governmental policy. There is the ceremonial oratory, the fourth is the didactic or philosophical oratory. Oratory was a popular art in the ancient Greek society, and in the eighteenth, nineteenth and part of the twentieth century, it was most effectively used in parliamentary assemblies in Britain, America, and Germany. Encyclopaedia Americana 1980 Grolier incorporated U.S.A. p. 789-790.

35. R.A. Freeman Observes that it was a remarkable feature in West African traditional societies. See Finegan 1978, p.44.

delivered with eloquence. Thus in traditional ceremonies and political gatherings, speeches are appraised on style as well as on matter. The Yoruba have a strong respect for the power of the spoken word and an orator who through the effective use of words succeeds in changing his audience's behaviour or strengthening their convictions and attitudes is accorded a high regard in the society. Fagunwa dramatically and convincingly exemplifies this social fact in his first two novels.

The instance of Imọdoye, one of the hunter-heroes to Oke Láńgbòdó is Fagunwa's finest example of an eloquent and witty speaker in Yoruba traditional setting. Thus at a critical moment before the contingent of hunters leaves for Oke Láńgbòdó, Imọdoye, perfectly aware of the charged atmosphere bursts forth and says:

Ènyin ẹlẹgbẹ mi tí ẹ nlọ sí Oke Láńgbòdó,
 ẹ ẹ ẹ ọkan yín gírí, kí ẹ si sẹ bí alágbára.
 Ogo wo ló wà fún ẹni tí nsé afẹ kákiri inú
 aiyé tí kò si ẹ ilú rẹ ní ore olókan!
 Iyì wo ni ó wà fún ọlẹ ènià tí ó tó ti
 akọni ọkunrin? Mo fẹ kí ẹ mo pé, àtàrí
 Ọlẹ kò tó ékán alágbára, bí fári rẹ bá
 dúró ní iṣẹjú kan, iṣẹjú keji ni àṣírí rẹ
 yó tú. È é ha ti ri ti ẹnyin fí fa ojú

rọ? Šòdọkẹ ẹ se tirẹ lárin Ègbá, O ba tirẹ lọ
 Ogedengbe ẹ se tirẹ lárin Ijèsà, ó bá tirẹ .
 lọ. Ogunmọla ẹ se tirẹ lárin Yoruba ó bá
 tirẹ lọ. Njẹ mo bi yín, à ó ẹ tiwa
 tàbí a kò ní í ẹ tiwa (p.57)

My comrades who go now to Mount Langbodo, make your minds resolute and act like men of strength. What glory is there to him who merely lives in glory but does no service for his land? What honour can an indolent man possess that will compare with that of a man of steel? I want you to understand that the skull of a lazy man is not worth the finger nail of a strong man; if his self-display flags for one single moment, the next moment, his emptiness becomes revealed to all. Why then do I see you look gloomy? Šòdọkẹ performed great deeds among the Ègba and departed; Ogedengbe fulfilled his share among the Ijèšas and went his way; Ogunmola did wonders among the Yoruba, and went his way. So now, I ask you, shall we fulfil our own task or shall we not?

(Šoyinka's translation p.81)

Imọdoye's speech is put simply, a masterpiece of Yoruba oratory. The team of hunters to Oke Langbodo is ready to move, public sentiment of weeping and wailing tends to weaken their manliness and dampen their enthusiasm.

Imọdoye senses the fears of his audience and bursts forth in a most exhilarating and invigorating oration. The oration is made up of direct, declarative and interrogative sentences

The first sentence is a call to reactivate the hunter's will and manliness. The next two interrogative sentences, are strong emotional appeals to the hunters' sense of patriotism. The following sentence which is somewhat declarative is pungently assertive. This is quickly fortified by a challenging rhetorical question. The speech is rounded off with powerful historical allusions to distinguished names in Yoruba history. By this, his message penetrates into the heart of his audience. So effective is the rhetoric of the message that by the time he poses the final question, he has succeeded in changing the mind of his audience, he has corrected their wrong position and won them to his own side. Imọdoye effectively employs argument and rhetorical devices, evidence and incontrovertible lines of reasoning, anecdotes and concrete illustrations to achieve his desired goal. Even today, Imọdoye's address is to the Yoruba ear, a celebrated speech. It is a fitting example of Yoruba oratory, which is greatly admired in traditional Yoruba society.

Fagunwa's Language

A lot has been written about Fagunwa's use of language in his novels. Ulli Beier (1967: 189) sees Fagunwa's language as the true flavour of his work. His language constitutes the elements to which the average Yoruba reader responds with delight. Bamgboṣe (1974: 108) considers Fagunwa's language his main claim to greatness as a Yoruba novelist, indeed "he is a master of the Yoruba language". Irele's (1975: 79-80) comment on Fagunwa's language is worth quoting:

...the most striking merit of Fagunwa's art - his way with language. He possessed the Yoruba language to a high degree and employed it with intimate mastery. The tone of his language ... is that of oral narrative which not only gives to his writing an immediate freshness, but reinforced by the use of imagery, contributes to what Wole Soyinka has called Fagunwa's vivid 'sense of event'. The various shades of living speech give full value to the style of the author who draws the most surprising effects from the structure of the language itself... Thus what is significant about his personal use of language is his resourceful exploitation of the communal medium and his ultimate fidelity to its nature, his individual illustration of its peculiar blend of exuberance and gravity.

There is no doubt that Fagunwa's use of language is striking. His language is characterized by certain loftiness and stateliness, often persuasive, emotive and vigorous. (1977) Yai considers comments like the above "over evaluation" and "over emphasis". Barber (1984: 22) sees Fagunwa's language differently. She describes Fagunwa's language as a "purposeless" repetitive and static embroidery. The rhetorical quality of Fagunwa's language which has been widely acclaimed, is severely castigated by Barber. She says:

Another characteristic of Fagunwa's style which seems to derive from his didactic intention is its rhetoric monotony. Sentences are composed of long string of structurally identical clauses the same type of sentences is repeated again and again. The tone never changes, we find the same repetitiousness, the same redundancy of simile, the same elaborate biblical formulations there is no variation...

Barber supports her view with many excerpts from Fagunwa's first two novels. Let us examine one of the excerpts from Igbo Olodumare p.16

Báyí ní 'iwin ná sọ sí baba mi, baba mi ná sí fèsi bí o ti yẹ kí alagbara fèsi fún alágbára, ó wo Eṣu-kekere-ode bí ìgbà tí jàndùkú obinrin bá fi ojú ìbàjẹ wo ẹkọ rẹ; ó wí pé: Ẹnití o fi aṣẹ gbe òjò ó tan ara rẹ jẹ; ẹnti ó duro de rélùwé yó bá ara rẹ ní ọrun alákeji; àgbà tó rí ẹjò tí kò sá ara ikú ló n'ya; ẹranko tí ó ba fi ojú di ọdọ ẹhin àrò ni yó sùn, ẹni tí ó gbójú lé ogún fi ara rẹ fún ọ̀ṣì ta; ẹbọra tí ó ba fi ojú di mi, yó ma ti ọrun dé ọrun ni, èmi ọkùnrin ni mo wí bẹ, òní ni n' o sọ fún ẹyin ẹbọra Igbó Olódùmarè pé nìgbà tí Ẹlédá dá ohun gbogbo ti n' bẹ nínú aiyé tán, ó fi ènià ẹ Olórí gbogbo wọn...

Thus spoke the spirit to my father, and my father replied, as one mighty man ought to reply to another. He looked at Eṣu-kekere-ode like a shrewish wife glowering at her husband, and said: "Anyone who tries to carry rainwater in a sieve is deceiving himself; anyone who stands in the path of a train will find himself in heaven; an elder who sees a snake and doesn't run is hastening the day of his own death; a wild animal that scoffs at the hunter will end up sleeping behind the fire-place (i.e. will be killed and hung up to smoke), anyone who depends on what he hopes to inherit gives himself over to wretchedness; a spirit that is disrespectful to me will certainly wander eternally from heaven to heaven, I, a man, say so, today I shall make it clear to you spirits of Igbo Olodumare that when the creator had created everything in the world, he made human beings the lords of all...

(Barber's translation p.23)

Barber (1984: 24) describes this kind of construction which is characteristic of Fagunwa's use of language as "artificial rhetoric". This assessment of Fagunwa's language is rather unconvincing, it is not based on a definite stylistic principle. It depicts Barber's ignorance of the significant role of orality in Yoruba culture. For as Irele aptly notes, the tone of Fagunwa's language is that of orality in Yoruba discourse. Olowoaiyes' response to Eṣu-kekereode in the above excerpt consists of eight sentences. Six of the sentences are structurally similar. The first five sentences are proverbial expressions which have a definite semantic similarity. The five proverbs as used here do not constitute a purposeless piling of repetitious expressions. Rather, the successive use of proverbs demonstrates a definite structural and semantic cohesion which gives the theme of the utterance an effective prominence. The short, sharp seventh sentence, (Èmi Ọkunrin ni mo wí bẹ̀) (I, a man, say so) gives the utterance a powerful emphatic significance which to the Yoruba ear is a confident and vigorous assertion of the supremacy of man over all other creatures.

But the goal of this study, is not the 'how' of Fagunwa's use of language, but why he uses it the way he uses it. For there is no doubt that Fagunwa uses the Yoruba language with masterful competence. His style is lofty, stately and parsonic. What is his raison d'etre? How does his use of language provide us information about his society? Bamgboṣe (1974: 130) seems to suggest that Fagunwa's use of language is due to his love of words. "He cannot rest until he has said the same thing several times over and in as hyperbolic a language as possible". For Barber, Fagunwa's use of language is determined and vitiated by his desire to moralize. Both views are suggestive of personal factors, they provide little, if any information about how his use of language helps us to understand Fagunwa's society.

Language is a social fact, it is a property of society. Language interacts with every other aspect of human life in society, and its use in a work of art can be fully understood only if it is considered in relation to society. It is the chief means of human communication. Its cultural significance is incontrovertible. William Bright (1968: 22) is probably right when he says:

Language is not merely one of several aspects of culture; it is at the very least, prima inter pares in that it makes possible the development, the elaboration, the transmission, and (particularly, in its written form) the accumulation of culture as a whole.

This significant role of language in culture then confirms the great flaw in the formalist emphasis on the primacy of the text. It strongly confirms the point of view of sociology of literature that no aspect of the literary text can be treated in isolation. Thus a deeper reason of why Fagunwa uses language the way he does would be found in the structure of his society. It is our submission that Fagunwa's use of language transcends personal and moral factors. His use of language is to a great extent a result of social and historical factors.

As pointed out in chapter two, the call for works of literature in indigenous Nigerian languages had started since the second decade of the twentieth century. By the 1930s and 1940s when Fagunwa wrote his first two novels the epochal era of nationalism and liberation struggle had begun. One important weapon of nationalist struggle is the use of indigenous language. The native language played a dominant role in educating the masses on the aims and objectives of nationalist struggles. It was a powerful

form of political propaganda. As Yai⁽¹⁹⁷⁷⁾ rightly observes, Fagunwa's period was one of the establishment of a new bourgeoisie. The thirst for school education had gripped the Yoruba hinterland. Thus a literary work in Yoruba language was sure of eager readership. Fagunwa was most probably aware of this situation and wrote in hitherto unprecedented style that would captivate the interest and attention of his audience.

Perhaps of greater importance was the circumstance behind the writing of Fagunwa's first novel Ogbójúḍe Nínú Igbó Irúnmalè. The novel was written for a literary competition organised by Miss Plummer in 1936 (Bamgbose 1974: 3). If he would win the competition, he had to outclass all others. He most certainly achieved this in his use of language. He used the Yoruba language in a way no one else had done thereby demonstrating the social significance of language. He was mindful of writing in a language that would appeal to the masses, a language that is in conformity with oral narrative form, a language that satisfies the cultural standard. Thus to Fagunwa's society, Fagunwa's first novel was revolutionary in the sense that it had a greater impact on the literary life of the ^{christian elite} than any

existing literary work in any other language. This was made more possible by his use of language than any thing else.

Fagunwa's use of language is a demonstration of his awareness of the social significance of language in the society. His powerful use of language ably confirms his recognition of the fact that "language is power and that language properly used, can be used and has been used to achieve almost any objective." (Chumbow 1985:5). As stated earlier, Fagunwa has a mission - the presentation of the Yoruba world view to his elitist class in consonance with the accepted principles of the colonial ruling class. Fagunwa recognized the fact that what one says is as important as how one says it. Thus his vigorous use of language is in recognition of the fact that word power is one strong element that can be used to achieve social and political stability in the society.

His Theme

Another interesting aspect of Fagunwa's first novels in his theme. Two main reasons have been advanced as Fagunwa's objective: to entertain and to instruct. There is no doubt that the two aims were achieved in the novels being examined. But to what extent do these objectives lead us to an understanding of Fagunwa's society? The entertaining quality of Fagunwa's theme is of little significance from the point of view of literary sociology, because entertainment is a general theme in many works of art. It is not peculiar to Fagunwa and there is nothing spectacular in the novels' ability to amuse his readers. Thus this entertainment aspect of his theme proffers no information about Fagunwa's society and his relationship with that society. The heavy dosage of moralizing in Fagunwa's novels is too glaring to go unnoticed. It is certainly true that Fagunwa is out to deliver a moral message. But the emphasis on the moral theme needs some reexamination. For Fagunwa's moral concern does not provide us with a total view of Fagunwa's relationship with his society.

The popular claim that Fagunwa's main purpose is to moralise, should be seen within the context of the totality of his role as a literary artist in his society. It is true his moralising has strong religious connotations. Fagunwa's concern for his society transcends mere religious concern. His concern for the society is a social concern. His comments in the first two novels are more than moral comments in the sense that they cover almost every stratum of the society - social, economic, and political. His comments cover the range of the family, the social structure and the hierarchical order. To refer to these multifarious comments as merely 'moral' amounts to an under assessment of Fagunwa's relationship with his society.

One of the most significant aspects of Fagunwa's theme is the symbolic meaning attached to his novels. The symbolic and allegorical meaning in the novels of Fagunwa has been very ably treated by Bamgbose (1974:91-100).

He says:

Fagunwa's novels are to be interpreted at more than one level. On the superficial level, they are stories of adventure: A hero sets out on a journey to a forest or in quest of an object. At the deeper level, the journey is an allegory of life's journey with its attendant problems and

difficulties. It is only through an understanding of this deeper level that we can attain the full meaning of the novels.

Fagunwa's novels thus constitute an artistic rendering of the life of man in Yoruba world view. Many of the characters in the novels apart from their superficial functions have symbolic meanings. This symbolism is also present in the setting, and events in the novels. Thus the Akaraogun-Agbako encounter in Ogbojúoḍe Ninú Igbó Irúnmalè is a signification of great misfortune which is often beyond human power and ability, and from which only divine providence can provide remedy. Fagunwa's symbolism is consonant with the Yoruba maxims like "Ojú Ogun ni ilé ayé" (life is a war front) and "Ṛni tí kò gbójú gbóyà kò le jayé pé (He who is not courageous cannot enjoy this world for long). In spite of its importance, the symbolic theme does not convey in full, its social significance, for the symbolic nature of the novels is an important aspect of Fagunwa's social concern for his society. Thus the moral and symbolic themes in his novels deserve a deeper look.

The theme of women, children and marriage is given a wide coverage in the novels under study. Fagunwa's concern here should not be seen merely as a pointer to the importance

the Yoruba attach to marriage, nor a condemnation of polygyny. Fagunwa's concern here has significant social implications, which can be fully understood when seen within the context of his society and his relationship with that society.

Fagunwa's many references to women, children and marriage should not be taken in isolation, for from the point of view of genetic structuralism an element may have relations with other elements. Works of literature must be grasped as 'wholes' in which the various parts function only as elements of a literary and social totality, the parts relate to the whole. This is true because the ideas expressed by a writer are only a partial aspect of the man, the man in turn is only an element in the society. In order to see the core of the meaning in a work of art, it should be seen as a whole. The relationship between the parts and the whole should be closely examined. Thus in the novels, children, marriage, women, men, have an important significance in the hierarchical order of the society. Taken together, they constitute the home or family - the core of the society's existence. Most of Fagunwa's comments on this aspect are symptomatic of the importance

of the home/family in society. To the Yoruba mind, home connotes affection and safety. It expresses the idea of a fixed place of residence. Peace and love in the home presupposes order and stability. To Fagunwa the continuity of the society was important. As a beneficiary of the colonial missionary machinery, he identified himself with the values that served to promote the smooth running and reinforcement of the colonial-missionary authorities. If this would be achieved, it must start with the stability in the home or family as this constitutes the bedrock of progress and stability of the society.

The symbolism in the novels tends to centre on the need for individual courage and fortitude in the race of life, patience in adversity and personal zeal for progress through hardwork. These are attributes essential for order and stability of the society. When members of the society are given to these traits, there would be no room for political agitation and revolutionary activities - a situation which may give rise to what O.B. Yai (1977: 4) aptly calls "social immobilism". This point can be taken further in a critical consideration of Akaraogun's acceptance of the Oba's request to lead a contingent of hunters to Oke-

Láńgbòdó. The incident is expressive of Fagunwa's justification for the need for unquestioned obedience and loyalty to constituted authority in the society. The Yoruba concept of the sanctity and supremacy of the ọba was one of the means of ensuring the stability and continuity of the monarchical order. It was the watchword of the colonial authority in the 1930s and 1940s. The ideology of communal solidarity which was greatly cherished in traditional society is heightened in the novels. This ideology constitutes the weapon of success on the hunters journey to Okè láńgbòdó. It is this same ideology that assists the team of hunters to overcome Ojola-Ibinu in Igbó Olódùmarè. These ideologies for Fagunwa have far-reaching effects for the security, stability and continuity of the society of his time.

Fagunwa's relationship to his society is one of satisfaction and conformity. This conformist attitude is further manifested in the creation of his hero in Igbó Olódùmarè. As Yai (1977: 7) has rightly observed, it is not by accident that the hero in Igbo Olodumare is given the name "Olówóaiye", and his father's name is "Akọwediran". The two names point to a particular socio-economic order. The early 1940s when Fagunwa wrote Igbó Olódùmarè was the

period of the new emerging urban petty bourgeoisie. Whitecollar jobs and salaried posts were becoming a mark of prestige in the Yoruba hinterland. As Yai said, "being an akowe" was highly valued. Fagunwa himself declares in Igbo Olódumare:

Idílé òmòwé kò sí ní ìpò tálákà bí
wòn kò ní owó ni oní, nwòn mbò wa ní
lola.

A family of educated elite is not in the position of the poor, if they are not rich today, they will become rich tomorrow.

Thus the names Olowoaiye and Akowediran constitute an expression of the aspiration of the Yoruba poor peasantry. Fagunwa himself came from a similar humble background and he knew the aspirations of people in such a social group.

Fagunwa's naming of these two heroes is important.

Olowoaiye and Akowediran most certainly belong to the preliterate Yoruba society, yet they are literate. It is a device which indicates that Fagunwa is looking ahead.

The device is suggestive of the imminence of a new leadership made up of the rich and the highly educated.

Olowoaiye's father Akowediran is well educated, but his grandson Ikaraogun is an illiterate hunter. Ogundipe-Leslie (1976:436) recognizes this point and calls it the technique of "narrative distancing". The naming of the characters is a fitting description of the growing elitism and money consciousness in the society. It is in fact as Yai remarks, a pointer to the social distance between the traditional hunter and the elitist, wealth amassing heroes of Fagunwa. Thus there is no doubt that Fagunwa's stance in the novel is expressive of his satisfaction with the colonial oriented socio-economic and political situation of his society. The totality of Fagunwa's relationship with his society can be summed up in the words of Baálẹ̀ Babalọ̀la in Delano's Aiyé Daiyé Oyìnbó: (p. 75)

Aṣabi, o kú o, ìgbà òyìnbó yi ma dára o,
gbogbo ofin tí a se lí ó jẹ daradara fun
awon enia.

Asabi, it is well, (with you) this period
of the white man is very pleasant, all the
rules and regulations are acceptable to
the generality of the people.

In the excerpt, Babalola, a traditional ruler is vehemently opposed to British colonialism. But after some time he submits to colonial supremacy. He is elevated in status. He enjoys the Queen's recognition as he is awarded the Order of the British Empire (O.B.E.) With the salary increment, he becomes one of the upper middle class and is accorded high regard in the society. It is during this period of prestige and plenty that Baale Babalola utters the remarkable comment. Babalola's comment is Delano's reaction to the socio-economic and political situation of the 1940s and 1950s. Incidentally, Delano was a contemporary of Fagunwa. He was born in 1904. He was one of the privileged few elite of the time, a member of the nascent bourgeoisie who benefited from the colonial-missionary era. And like Fagunwa his relationship with his society is glaringly conformist.

Thus as seen in Fagunwa's first two novels, not only does Fagunwa identify himself with the ideologies of the ruling class, he recognizes them as effective means of stabilising the society. Fagunwa's posture in the novels thus confirms Melottis (1977: 5) view that: "Literature is the product of a particular class consciousness, and the expression of a particular class which can play an active role in shaping the consciousness and social aspirations of the people".

CHAPTER FOUR

OKEDIJI AND MODERN YORUBA SOCIETY

Between 1949, when Fagunwa published his second novel, Igbó Olódùmarè and 1969 when Okediji published his novel Ajà ló lerù, remarkable social, political, and economic changes had taken place in Nigeria. It was the period of Nigeria's powerful move towards political emancipation, a phenomenon which has had significant effects on various departments of life in the society. As a member of the society himself, it is most probable that certain aspects of the changes of the period have motivated Okediji's writing. A knowledge of his life and background will then be a fitting starting point for a meaningful study of his work.

Oladejọ Okediji - A biography¹

Oladejọ Okediji was born into the Baálẹ̀ Apáàrà compound in Oyo on 10th October, 1929. He is the offspring of Moses Okediji and Madam Mary Okediji. His father was

1. I am grateful to the University of Ilorin for funding the research on 'Yoruba writers past and present', which made Okediji's biography possible.

a devout, dedicated and dynamic christian. He was one of the earliest christian converts in Oyo. He embraced literacy and soon became a distinguished reader of Yoruba books. He had a strong sense of dedication to missionary work, and was an accomplished preacher during sunday services at the Methodist Church, Oyo.

Ọladejọ Okediji's father had a great love for reading and was fond of buying and preserving available Yoruba books. He made a special basket which he used as his bookshelf. This he hung in the ceiling of his room for safe keeping. Among the books he kept in his miniature library were: ABD Olópe, Ajiṣafẹ's Aiyé Akámarà, Thomas's Ìtàn Emi Sègilọla, Ilosiwájú Èrò Mímó, Orin Sobọ Arobiodu and some of the early Yoruba newspapers like Nígbàtí Owo bá dilẹ (In Leisure Hours) Elétí Ofẹ and Akéde Èkó.

This aspect of the life of Ọladejọ Okediji's father contributed substantially to Ọladejọ Okediji's literary consciousness. From his childhood he had developed a strong love for reading and a powerful urge to acquire and preserve books. As a result of his father's distinguished position in the church, he started school at the age of six, at the Methodist Primary School, Oyo in 1935. He left in standard four in 1941 and proceeded to St. Andrew's College Demonstration School, Oyo, where he

completed his primary school education in 1943. He became a teacher in 1944 and was posted to the Methodist School in Fiditi. He proceeded to Wesley College, Ibadan in 1945, where for the first time in his life, he saw one of his heart's greatest desires - a library. He felt so challenged by the large collection of books that he made sure he read all the works of fiction in the college library in his college days.

His admission to Wesley College in 1945, was at first to the Teachers' Grade Three Certificate course. But at the end of his first year, he was recommended to proceed to the four year course leading to the Teachers' Grade Two Certificate. It was during this course that he met Mr (now) Bishop T. T. Solaru who was Okediji's Yoruba tutor, at the college. After the completion of his Teachers' Grade Two certificate course, he was posted to the Methodist Primary School, Ogèrè in Ogun State. On arrival at Ogèrè, Okediji was deeply preoccupied with how to satisfy his literary desire. One source of satisfaction opened for him at Ipèru about three kilometres from Ogèrè where his friend, Okunola Laşekan was headmaster of a primary school. At that time, Tai Solarin who was then in Britain used to send his newly bought books to the primary school in Ipèru

for safe keeping as the books were meant for his personal library. Thus, Okediji had access to the books and read several of them. This experience deepened his literary interest and created in him, the desire to write. Indeed, he attempted writing a novel in the English language, but it was never published.

In 1951, he was transferred to Itapa-Ekiti in Ondo State. It was at that time, that the Department of Education embarked on a mobile bookshop under the supervision of one Mr. Levi, who often brought the books to Itapa. Okediji availed himself of this opportunity by buying many books on fiction and thus satisfied his literary thirst till 1952 when he left Itapa. 1953 found him at the Methodist school, Owo, and in 1954, he was transferred to the United School, Iju-Ita Ogbolu, in Ondo State. In 1954, when Mr. Levi became Education Officer at Ibadan, the Education Department issued an advertisement inviting all competent Yoruba creative writers to take part in a literary competition in the Yoruba language. Okediji reacted promptly to the advertisement and sent in a manuscript titled "Agbalagba Akan" but he never heard anything on the manuscript till 1960, when he read a public notice in Olokun written by Mr. (now Professor)

S. A. Babalola requesting to know the whereabouts of "Mr. Oladejo Okediji" whose manuscript, titled "Agbàlagbà Akàn" he had read and greatly admired, but never heard anything about since 1954! In response, Okediji wrote to Professor Babalola who gave him every assistance to write another book and saw to its publication. The fruit of Professor Babalola's encouragement and assistance was the publication in 1969, of the first thriller in Yoruba, Ajà ló lerù.

In 1955, Okediji became a tutor at the Oyo Divisional Teachers' College, Iseyin. 1956 found him working in Lagos. This was a period when party politics was taking a new turn in Nigeria. Okediji joined Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe's party, the National Council of Nigeria and Cameroons (N.C.N.C). He contested the local government election and became a councillor for Oyo in 1958. The difficulties and dangers of constant travelling from Lagos to Oyo made him return to Ile-Ife where he was employed as tutor in Yoruba Method and Principles of Education at the Ife Divisional Teachers' College, in 1958. He resigned his appointment as Councillor in 1961. In 1966 he resigned from the teaching profession and became a bookseller/trader and full-time writer. It was during this period

that he wrote Ajà ló lerù. In the process of rewriting and correcting the manuscript, many other new ideas surfaced which led to the publication of his second novel, Agbàlagbà Akàn in 1971. His Ògá Ni Bukola, a children's story book was published in 1973.

In 1972, he became a teacher once again, and taught Yoruba at Ọranmiyan Grammar School, in Ile-Ife. He later became an examiner of Yoruba with the West African Examinations Council. In the same year, 1972, he took part in a writer's workshop organized by Ọla Rotimi at the University of Ife. The result of his experience at the workshop was the publication in 1973 of an interesting Yoruba play, Réré Rún. He later wrote a voluminous Yoruba novel, Atótó Arere which was published in 1981. Another Yoruba play, Sàngó will be published shortly. In the 1975/76 session, he proceeded to the University of Ife, for a Certificate course in Education. He is at present senior Yoruba master at Ọranmiyan Grammar School, Ile-Ife. He is married with five children.

The Modernizing Society in Okediji's times

A notable aspect of the first forty years of Okediji's life and times is that the quality and style of social,

economic, and political life in Nigeria took on many of the characteristics usually associated with modernity. Thus 1929-1969, the period of Okediji's birth and that of his first novel, Ajà ló lerù, was one of social, political and economic transformation in Nigeria. In this period, the generality of Nigerian urban society was exposed to various aspects of modern life. These were conspicuously manifested in the introduction of new technology, innovative building constructions, variegated consumer goods, novelty in the use and response to the mass media, and tremendous increase in the growth of literacy.

Politically, it was the period when Nigeria started paving her way to modern politics. Incidentally it was the period of the Second World War, a phenomenon which in no small way accelerated Nigeria's step to modern political system. It was the period that saw the setting up of modern administrative machinery, and executive and judicial establishments. The period witnessed the advent of parliamentary system of government - the regional Houses of Assembly and House of Chiefs; as well as the Houses of Representatives and the Senate. It was a period of propagation of new political ideas and slogans like "Freedom

for all, life more abundant", "democratic socialism" "pragmatic socialism". In a bid to make their views known to the public, the various political parties that were formed embarked on pamphleteering journalism. Various pamphlets containing the ideas, aims and objectives of political parties were frequently issued. Newspapers were established for political purposes. For instance the Action Group published The Tribune and Ìròhìn Yorùbá and later the Nigeria National Democratic party published Ìmólè Òwúró. All these developments enhanced public enlightenment about various events in the society. The upsurge of newspaper publications provided some incentive for gifted writers in Yoruba to practise their art.²

The introduction of party politics gave room to elaborate hierarchical political structures - professional politicians, party managers, various political titles like party agents, party propagandists, and political thugs. These innovations in the political organization of the country had significant impact on the socio-political and economic life of the Nigerian society. The new political

2. Chief Adegbogega Sobande started writing his Rigimo Obinrin ko se e tu in Iroyin Yoruba in 1949. Lawuyi Ogunniran was editor of Imole Owuro and wrote his poems titled "Emi Atioro Omọ Atiala" in the paper.

situation among other things gradually robbed the Obas of their traditional powers. It greatly reduced the age-long importance of palace messengers and replaced them with the police as key figures in the maintenance of law and order in the society.

It was also a period of remarkable economic change. As noted in chapter two the state of Nigeria's economy in the early times was essentially *agrarian*. The production or processing of food was mainly for domestic use. Farming constituted the main occupation, the farmers were essentially illiterate, traditional in their ways of life, thinking and the kind of farm implements they use. They were on the whole cut off from the outside world. The production of simple handicrafts, and trading activities were mostly confined to traditional modes. But as a result of many factors which became manifest in the period under examination a new economic structure emerged.

Among such factors are the new system of political administration which culminated in the centralization and expansion of bureaucratic activities. There was also the influence of urbanization. Perhaps, the most important is the increase in the establishment of educational institutions. The growth in educational advancement caused many

educated Nigerians to move into positions of responsibility and authority. This new administrative machinery, urbanization, and educational advancement drew many people from the rural to urban centres. The economic situation shifted the labour force from the self-employed to wage earning sector.

It was during this period that cocoa became an important, fast moving, and money yielding cash crop. Later, crude oil was discovered in Nigeria. The discovery of crude oil greatly enhanced the state of economy, creating the term "economic boom". The situation of the nation's economy expanded so fast that by 1969, export volumes and values had increased tremendously. By 1960, commercialization and industrialization in Nigeria had reached such a height that the "Gross Domestic Product" had risen from about 7% in 1950 to 15% in 1960.³ Indeed by 1963, the income per capita which stood at £5 in the pre-Second World War years had risen to £29.6⁴.

As a result, by the 1960s, a greater sense of class consciousness became manifest in the society. The increase

3. Nkemdirim, B. 1975 Social change and political violence in colonial Nigeria.

Arthur, H. Stockwell p. 23

4. Ibid. p.23.

in industrial establishments and business concerns created rapid growth in the number of the working class who are mainly illiterate and half-educated employees (in many establishments). The changing socio-economic and political situation also led to the increase in the numerical strength of the middle and the upper classes in many urban societies. This nascent socio-economic situation brought about an upsurge of the world view of money consciousness. This was particularly the case in many of the increasingly large numbers of urban agglomerations in the Yoruba hinterland. In many of the big cities of Nigeria, a wave of inordinate ambition to accumulate wealth by all means grew in the society. As a result, unscrupulous practices like profiteering, cheating, extortions, smuggling, money doubling, kidnapping etc., all aimed at amassing quick wealth became the vogue. Certain offshoots of Western civilization like gambling, modernized drinking houses, prostitution, obscene literature and films increased tremendously in the society.

Perhaps the most heart-rending of them all was the alarming rate of highway robbery that became rampant in the society. Harrowing reports of unprecedented robbery

filled the pages of many newspapers in the last decade of the period under consideration. For instance, in 1964, dynamite was used to break into a Hospital warden's safe in Ogbómòsò. It was the first report of a real European-style burglary ever committed in Nigeria.⁵ This was followed by gruesome reports of large-scale day-light armed robberies on banks and big commercial establishments. Soon the robbers were reported to have shifted their operation to the highways, halting, assaulting, wounding and killing innocent citizens and making away with substantial amount of money and goods. The situation of insecurity to life and property became so startling that newspaper editorials cried out for improvements in investigation methods and crime prevention devices in the country.

One such outcry, was contained in the January 10, 1965 issue of the Sunday Express; it says:

5. Sunday Express, January 10, 1965 p. 7.

The crime situation in Nigeria is now highly intolerable. Something has to be done to save the country. What is the use of amenities and facilities being provided by politicians when criminals are fast at work preparing to strike. The criminals in our midst must be destroyed now or never.⁶

This in brief was the socio-economic situation that characterized Okediji's society.

Literary tradition and setting

Okediji's reaction is contained in his crime novels - Ajà ló lerù and Agbàlagbà Akàn. Like the novel itself, crime fiction is an alien genre in Yoruba literature. At the time of Okediji's writing therefore, there was no crime novel worthy of that name in Yoruba that could serve him as a guide. But having read a lot of works of fiction in his college days, his main source of inspiration is the English tradition of crime fiction writing. Works like Leslie Charteris's Follow the Saint and Conan Doyle's The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes, provided him with the experience from which he could take off.

He translates this alien tradition into something that depicts a truly Nigerian situation. First, he makes

6. Ibid. p.15

Ibadan and its environs the setting of his two novels. This choice is appropriate for the kind of literary task Okediji has set himself. Consequent upon rapid urbanization, Ibadan has become the largest indigenous city in Black Africa. Its political status as the headquarters of Western Region makes it a strategic point for various administrative, commercial, educational and religious establishments.⁷

The rapid influx of people from the sub-urban and rural areas to Ibadan resulted in a big population with diversified moral peculiarities and cultural characteristics. The physical location of Ibadan with its numerous hamlets and suburbs creates an abundance of areas of operations for men of the under-world. The general planlessness in the siting and construction of many buildings, typical of many traditional Yoruba towns, yields shady and tortuous places of abode which constitute hideouts for many criminals. By the 1960s Ibadan had become more politically important.

7. Ibadan is now the capital of Oyo State.

It had risen from the status of divisional headquarters in the 1950s to administrative centre of the Western Region. By the 1950s the administrative machinery of the Regional Government grew rapidly; further more, government became much more highly centralized in the capital than in the colonial period. As Regional headquarters, Ibadan city witnessed rapid social, economic and political changes in the 1960s. The early fifties saw the expansion of the Secretariat, as well as increase in the number of the senior civil servants who formed the largest proportion of the new educated elite. The new educated elite constituted one of the most important groups in the town, creating the new pattern of life style, behaviour and values appropriate to the modern world into which many Nigerians were being drawn.⁸

Long before it became politically significant, Ibadan had been an important commercial centre. With the construction of the railway, the major expatriate commercial firms and banks had made the town their headquarters. Moreover, Ibadan is one of the main centres for the collection of cocoa and palm kernels. Ibadan allowed

⁸. See Lloyd, P.C. 1967. The City of Ibadan, O.U.P. pp. 3-9.

Lebanese traders to settle and practise their commercial activities. It attracted the establishment of manufacturing and industrial enterprises. Various indigenous craft enterprises and small scale industries also flourished in the city. Furthermore, Ibadan has attracted many new social services. The introduction of the Free Primary Education Scheme in the mid fifties led to the construction of many primary schools. The number of secondary grammar schools in the city increased considerably. The choice of Ibadan as the home of Nigeria's premier university, the building of the university teaching hospital, the Nigerian College of Arts, Science and Technology and myriads of other educational institutions has had significant impact on the social and economic life of the city. For instance, it led to a considerable increase in the growth of the numerical strength of the educated elite. P. C. Lloyd (1967: 129-132) records an average number of four hundred and fifty university graduates between 1956 and 1960; about two hundred lawyers, and not less than twelve private doctors resided in Ibadan in the 1960s.

One significant effect of these social, economic and political developments is population expansion. The

rate of immigration into Ibadan from all parts of Nigeria was astonishing. The 1963 census put the number of non-Yoruba immigrants at thirty thousand (Lloyd 1967:8).

Thus by the early sixties, Ibadan was a populous city with rich, flourishing commercial enterprises and a lively social environment. There was also a conspicuous change in the social structure. Cocoa farming flourished, bringing considerable cash income into the town. The new wealth was also manifested in wage employment, trade and industries. The economic boom led to a greater concern for money and material acquisition in the society.

The mid-sixties witnessed the period of economic depression. There was a sharp reduction in the prices of cocoa, a situation which made life difficult for many cocoa farmers.

The increased number of school leavers with inadequate provision for job opportunities led to unemployment. Many of the applicants came to Ibadan in search of employment; they lived with relatives, or in extreme cases engaged in petty theft (Lloyd, 1967:9).

Thus the structure of the society in the 1960s depicts a fairly developed class structure. At the lowest rung of the ladder were the proletariat class made up of job seekers and and the poor self employed peasants. Next were the farmers,

petty traders, and low-income wage earners which constituted the working class. There were also the white collar workers made up of teachers, nurses, clerical officers and other salary earners who hold subordinate positions in the government service. These constituted the middle class. There were the upper middle class made up of university graduates, professionals, rich cocoa farmers, traders and lawyers. These constituted the petty bourgeoisie. At the top of the ladder were those the Marxists call the 'National Bourgeoisie'. These are made up of politicians wealthy chiefs, and successful businessmen, who invariably constituted the ruling class.

Particularly noteworthy is the fact that the period 1965-1969 was an era of political turbulence, intra-party feud and governmental instability. The 1965 elections generated a great deal of controversy. Violence broke out at Mushin, and it spread to other political strongholds like Ilesha, Ijebu-Ode, Ekiti and Ondo. Looting, arson, killing and frequent pitched battles with the police continued till the middle of January 1966. In many areas it was well organized. The violence gained the name of "Operation "Wẹ̀tì ẹẹ" (Operation wet it) from the way in which the property and persons of political opponents

Ibadan was the nerve centre of these violent political outbursts. It is thus a fitting setting for Okediji's novels.

His novels and the society

The plot of Okediji's novels, Ajà ló lẹ̀rù and Agbàlagbà kàn can be described as a synthesis of thought, action, and counteraction of characters. The development of the stories in both novels reveals a neat progression from one situation to another, such that each situation is characterized by some particular incident. There is always a felt need for urgency and necessity for thought and action to accomplish a definite task. In most cases there is little time to relax and reflect on steps to take to achieve the needed objective.

One significant method which Okediji adopts in the form of both novels is exposure. This is consonant with the Spanish literary tradition of "detection".⁹

⁹. In the Spanish literary tradition, the term "detection" means "taking the roof off", every attempt is made to uncover whatever is hidden in connection with a crime. The situation is like what happens to a building when the entire roof is removed, and it becomes easy to expose what is inside.

See Barzun, J & Taylor, W. H. 1967. A Catalogue of Crime. p. 57.

It is this type of literary tradition that best suits Okediji's intention in the novel. This intention is to expose his society in order to discover the root cause of criminality in it. Thus in both novels, the situation and extent of criminality, the causes of crime, the police force, the criminals, their tactics, and more of operations, and finally, the attitude of the society to the criminals, all are exposed. After the exposure of the society, Okediji seems to ask the question: "what shall we do?" The answer to this question is provided in the personality of the hero who himself is an embodiment of action.

Action is the dominant element in the form of both

novels. The story in both novels begins with the hero in a pleasant, peaceful and harmonious situation. But in order to get the story going, Okediji employs a dynamic motif which destroys the initial peaceful situation. An unexpected incident occurs which disturbs the tranquility of the hero and provokes action on his part. Thus in Ajà ló lerù the story opens simply:

Lápàdé wo iwájú lọ şàkun, ó
 teşè mò kèkè rè Atégùn kan
 rora fé yéé, ó sì dùnmọ Lapade
 tobéè tí ó fi wí jáde pé O
 şeun iwọ èfúufù yìí

Lapade looked straight on the road, he concentrated on his riding. A fresh air blew coolly and calmly, it was very pleasant to Lapade, he enjoyed it so much that he spoke out saying thank you, you this fresh air.

This excerpt paints the picture of the hero in an enjoyable mood. He was on his way home from the farm. He has already caught a glimpse of the town and the joy of going home is filling his heart. As he rides on, certain social facts about the society go through the hero's mind. Then suddenly something happens: "Lójiji ni ó gbọ wéré nínú igbé ó wo ibẹ kò rí nnkankan"

(suddenly he heard a sound in the bush. He looked in that direction but saw nothing). The sudden sound of a movement in the bush disrupts the flow of his thought and causes him to take action. The dynamic motif is much more effective in the opening of his second novel, Agbàlagbà Akàn.

Ó pé tí Lápàdé ti jí ó ti rorín,
 Ó si ti wẹ. Ó wa jókó, ó sì
 fẹhìntì lórí àga aláṣọ kan ní
 pàlọ rè Tímùtìmù aláwọ kan tí
 àwọn onísòṅà fi àwòran orìsírìṣì
 dárà sí lára wà níwájú rẹ, ó
 gbé èsẹ méjèèjì lẹ. Ó dijú, ó
 lẹ aṣọ aran alárábarà kan bayíí
 mọ́ idí kò wẹwù bẹẹ ni kò bọ
 ṣòkòtò. Ọjọ tí a ó bá sọ̀nù,
 gágágá lara ẹnì yá. Ó n jobì
 Ó n mu sigá rè láìyajú. A kíí
 tanná mọ ọ̀nà ọ̀fun. (p. 1).

Lapade had woken up long ago. He had cleaned his teeth and washed. Then he had sat down, and he was reclining in a deck-chair in his parlour. A leather cushion decorated with all kinds of designs lay in front of him, and he rested both his feet on it. His eyes were closed. He wrapped a many coloured velvet cloth around his waist; he had no shirt or trousers on. On the day of one's downfall one starts off feeling

on top of the world. He was eating Kola, he was smoking his cigarette, without opening his eyes. There is no need to light a lamp to see the way down one's throat.

(Barber's translation 1984: 31)

Here is a fine picture of the hero, Lapade in a great state of ease. He is in a state of well being. He later sends for food. His favourite food, Amàlà, is ready on the table. His appetite has reached *its peak*, he rises to wash his hand. Then suddenly, someone knocks at the door! The unexpected knock disturbs the tranquil atmosphere as a stranger enters. The stranger's arrival provokes action and sets the story into vigorous motion.

As the story moves on at various points in the novels, Okediji employs the technique of interior monologue to reveal a lot of things. This technique makes the incidents in the story truly lifelike, as it reveals the inner thoughts of the hero. From his inner thoughts we are let into the secret of the main problem of the police force - lack of men of ability and dedication, absence of an able leader, capable of instilling the much needed sense of direction. In this way, we already have a foretaste of Audu Karimu, the police Inspector, before his arrival on the scene. Some details about

Lapade himself are revealed - his life as a policeman, his abilities, his concern for his farm and the reason for his trip home.

The hero always has a goal. Lapade's decision to leave his job as a police man has a purpose and his trip from one farm to the town at the opening chapter of Ajà ló lerù has a definite reason. Before he reaches home, the stage is set for another target at home. This is revealed in the Yoruba newspaper Aláròyé Ibàdàn. The editorial comment describes the state of criminality in the society. The use of the editorial report in the newspaper is an innovation which brings freshness and variety into the novel's form. It deeply enriches the authenticity and realism of the sequence of events.

In Ajà ló lerù, Lapade's involvement in the crime situation comes about in a natural way. He is passionately urged to help recover a missing young girl. The need and effort to recover the girl, Tòlani, set the hero of the story into action. The hero has to recover the girl, before she comes to any harm. This calls for urgency. The criminals must first be identified, and overpowered. The police must be out-witted, so that they will not be able to disrupt his plans. It is this task that leads to

a series of actions and in the novel.

In both novels, it is particularly interesting that in spite of these actions, the sequence of events and incidents are not a pack of monotonous occurrences. Rather, the succession of events is characterized by variety of incidents, and, situations. Every event brings something new and challenging. In the thick of terrible and frightening incidents, the characters remain human, and the incidents remain realistic.

Exposure of the society

Okediji's first task is to expose his society, particularly the frightening state of criminality in the society. Thus he exposes the tripartite forces in crime perpetration in the society, namely, the criminals, the police, and the people. He reveals, first, the various criminal acts in the society. Among these are stealing, swindling, abduction, kidnapping, burglary, cold blooded murder, car theft, hemp selling and smoking, and organized robbery. Apart from the scenic presentation of the various incidents of criminal acts, Okediji portrays their horrifying effects on the life of the people. For instance, on page 62 of Ajà ló lerù, the Aláròyé Ibadan

comments on the unmitigated wickedness being done to innocent citizens by men of the underworld:

Eniyàn n̄ sonù lṣan gangan ... Olè
 n̄ fi agbàrà gba owó lṣwṣ olówó láàrin
 títi ní ṣsán gbàìgbáí, kò sí ẹnì tí ó
 lè dá wṣn lṣkun, kò sí ẹnì tí i mú wṣn.
 Ilé n̄ jó, a kò mọ ẹnì tí n̄ kun wṣn.
 Ọmọ n̄ sṣnu káàkiiri. Àwṣn jàndùkú n̄
 mu igbó láàrin ojà. Ọmọbinrin kò gbṣṣṣ
 dá rin lójú ṣnà létì ilú, kò sí èyi tí
 awṣn ọlọpáá kápá rẹ ... Wṣn kò rójú tùú
 ọkan kan ...

People get lost in the day time. Thieves
 forcibly steal at noon. There is no one
 to stop or arrest them. Houses are burnt
 and no one knows those who are behind the
 burning. Children get lost every where.
 Thugs smoke hemp in the market place!
 Young girls cannot freely move on the
 streets ... To the police, the situation
 seems a Gordian knot.

The reports show that the society is insecure:

Àwṣn Ọlṣsà náà n̄ fṣfe gbáà, wṣn n̄ dá
 bírà. Wṣn n̄ dána lṣsán án, wṣn n̄
 dánà lóru. Nígba mírán, wṣn a tilè
 máa kòwé sí onilé pé àwṣn n̄ bọ láti
 jà á lolè ní ọjṣ báyií báyií, kó múra
 sílè de àwṣn. Bí wṣn tí n̄ fṣlé, ní
 wṣn n̄ ṣṣpánpá, bí wṣn tí n̄ kó ṣṣṣṣì,
 n̄ wṣn n̄ kó mṣsálásí. Wṣn n̄ kẹrù ní

ilé adájó kóòtù, wọn ní wọ ààfin ọba
 jalè ... Tìbọn Tìbọn ni wọn ní rìn pèlú ...
 Ọrọ ná à kàmòmò gbá à láàrin ilú ọlọba.

(pp. 3-4)

The thieves are really performing wonders. They rob on the highways both day and night. At times, they write landlords of their intention to attack them and urge them to expect their coming. As they burgle individually, so also they burgle jointly. As they steal in churches, so they do in mosques. They rob the homes of high court judges and king's palaces. They are usually armed. The matter is shocking in a community that has a head.

Okediji sets himself three significant questions:

What are the causes of crime in the society? Why does crime thrive in the urban agglomerations? Is there any solution? Thus the complex subject of crime, its causes and possible solutions is the focus of Okediji's concern in Ajà ló lerù and Agbàlagbà Akàn.

In keeping with his technique of exposure, Okediji first attempts an exploration of the rationale behind criminality in the society. Some of the characters in the novels are created to achieve this end. For instance, why does Salami Kemberu decide to burgle Lapade's house? What prompts Jakunmọ Gbekuta to become a hemp farmer and pedlar? What attracts Taiwo to become a kidnapper? What is it

that compels Adegun Adeogun, a respectable member of the community to become divisional head of all criminals? Okediji uses the criminal characters in the novels to find answers to these questions.

Okediji is probably aware of the fact that the problem of crime is no longer a societal or national affair. It has assumed a world-wide dimension. Criminal behaviour is as old as the story of human creation. The first recorded criminal act - the murder of Abel by his brother Cain appears in the first book of Moses, Genesis (Gen. 4:8) and since then it has continued to spread at terrific rate. It takes various forms - from murder to petty theft, from treason to misappropriation of funds. Okediji is most aware that it is not easy to posit a single explanation for such a wide variety of human action. Various theories have been posited about the nature and causes of criminality. Some theories about what constitutes criminal behaviour claim that the criminal code represents the embodiment of God's law and is independent of the will of man. Modern radical Marxist idea asserts that criminal law is simply the instrument by which the ruling class entrenches and

stabilizes its power.¹⁰

Explanations of the causes of crimes are also varied. For instance, there is the individual accountability and responsibility theory which assumes that an individual chooses immoral or criminal conduct of his own free will and is therefore responsible for his actions. Other theories portray the criminal as a helpless pawn of biological, psychological or social forces beyond his reason, understanding, or control. "Traditional" explanations of criminal behaviour have tended to focus upon the individual and on particular attributes of his personality that supposedly cause his criminal behaviour. There is of course the "moralistic" explanation which emphasize the criminal's evil qualities such as greed, envy, corruption, revenge etc., and assume that the individual "gives in" to such feelings of his own free will.¹¹

From Okediji's point of view, criminality in the Yoruba urban society stems from social, economic and political forces. Among such forces are hunger, poverty, unemployment, children delinquency, acrimonious party

10. Mitchell, J. 1976. Man and society. p. 288.

11. Ibid. p. 289.

Ebi lo rán mi wá. Jámbálá ebi,
 ati àíríṣṣé, ati àírílégbé kò
 sí kòbò lówó mi, kò sí ònà ati
 jẹ un, bẹẹ ni mo si gbọdò jẹun.
 Ohun ti o jẹ kí n wa fólé niyẹn.

It is hunger that has sent me (to steal) sharp, biting hunger, joblessness and lack of accommodation. There is not a kobo in my hand and there is no means whereby I can feed, yet it is compulsory for me to eat. That is the cause of my embarking on burglary.

The excerpt establishes three potent causes of criminality in the society - hunger, poverty, and unemployment. Unemployment often leads to hunger and poverty. There is no doubt that Okediji adequately recognizes unemployment and poverty as strong forces in the spread of criminality in the society. He does not give the theme an in-depth discussion, rather he makes it re-echo at every stage in the two novels. He weaves the theme around Tafa's cognomen. Tafa Ajao, Lapade's assistant in the novel often cites himself at significant points in the novel. The cognomen sheds a great deal of light on the implications of poverty which arises from unemployment:

Èmi rée o, èmi Ajàó àro, àyà-jinmọ
gìrìgìrì. Èmi ajámọ láyà bí àìlówólówó
Ajámọláyà bí okun şòkòtò tó já lówùjọ
Itìju ò tó 'tìjú ...

Here am I, I Ajao Aro, the one that
makes a child tremble profusely. I am
he that frightens a child like penury,
the one that terrifies a child like the
strings of a trouser that got snapped in
public. A shameful thing indeed it is!

The way the state of pennilessness is compared to a trouser,
whose string cuts suddenly in public shows clearly that
poverty involves more than it in fact carries with it
loss of self-respect and self identity. It causes anxiety.

Salami Kemberu's identification by Tafa reveals that
Salami is a hardened criminal, an ex-convict, a regular
customer at Agodi Prisons. In his effort to reveal more
of his identity, Tafa discloses that disobedience to
parental injunctions has turned Kemberu into a waif - a
forsaken and neglected child. This point establishes the
fact that children delinquency causes criminal behaviour
in the society. Further forceful probings compel Salami
to make more confessions that are pertinent to our under-
standing of the causes of crime in the society. For
instance in Ajà ló lẹrù (p. 50) Salami confesses:

Níjẹta tí mo jáde l'Agodi, mo bọ sí
 igboro lati wá ẹ́ tí n ó ẹ́. Mo fẹ́
 tètè kúrò nínú irú ìgbésíayé tí n gbé
 mi lọ sẹ̀wọ̀n nígbàgbogbo yìi. Mo ní bí
 mo bá ni iṣẹ́ gidi lẹ́wọ̀ n kò sá lè jalè
 mọ́, n kò sì níí lọ sẹ̀wọ̀n mọ́. Mo bá bèrè
 si i waṣẹ́ kiiri ni jẹta. Mo rin, rin,
 rìn, mo pàarà, pàarà. Mo rin gbogbo ilẹ̀
 yíí já, n kò rí ẹ̀ni gbà mi si iṣẹ́ kankan.

Three days ago, when I left Agodi Prisons,
 I came to the town to look for work that
 I will engage in. It is my wish to leave
 this kind of life that takes me to prison
 frequently. I thought that if I have a
 good job I would no longer steal, I would
 no longer go to prison. I then started to
 search for job, three days ago. I trekked,
 trekked, trekked; I made frantic efforts,
 I walked across this town, but I found no
 one to offer me any job.

From this confession emerges another cause of criminality.
 Lack of adequate provision for the employment of ex-
 convicts is a social problem which virtually gives room
 for criminal activities in the community. Closely
 related to this is the uncomplimentary attitude of members
 of the public to ex-convicts. Salami Kemberu explains
 further.

Bí mo dé bómíràn, wọ̀n a ma a sọ̀rọ̀
 wíyẹ̀wíyẹ̀ pé Salami Kemberu ti wọ̀le 0,
 wọ̀n a si bèrè síí palẹ̀mọ́. Bí Ọ̀ga kan

ba ti n fe gba mi tele, enikan a feti
 kooleti, Oga naa a si so iwé owo re
 silé bí igbà ti ó jóo lówó, a si wa wo
 mi, a yanu silé bi akọ pepeye, a si so
 pé, "kò tí ì sáyè báyií. Bí àyè kankan
 bá si silé, a o ránsé pe o ... ", kò tán
 bí? kí ni kí emi wá máa je?

If I reach another place, they would be talking in whispers that Salami Kemberu has entered, they would start to keep their things. Even if a Manager is interested in giving me a job, someone would whisper to him, he would suddenly drop his appointment paper as if shocked, he would look at me and open his mouth in awe like a duck and say, "there is no vacancy now. Whenever there is any vacant position we will send for you". Is that not the end? What then should I be eating?

Okediji reveals the attitude of the society towards known criminals as one of fear, suspicion, and trepidation. Ex-convicts are seen and treated as outcasts.

Okediji posits other reasons like stealing in order to build up some capital. Kemberu's confession reveals that he intends to steal Lapade's money so that he would use it as capital to start a commercial enterprise. (p.51).

One of the significant marks of the 1960s was acrimonious party politics in Nigeria. Right from the late 1950s, politics in Nigeria had been characterized

by bitterness. By the 1960s, intra-party antagonisms escalated, party slogans and campaign songs were studded with abusive expressions that resulted in public altercations and wranglings. Many able-bodied young men were hired as thugs. Many of the thugs were armed with dangerous weapons. The growing influence of thugs in political campaigns greatly enhanced the growing, selling and smoking of hemp. Hemp smoking was then seen as a potent morale booster to political thugs during campaign meetings. Hemp smoking, alcoholism, and drug addiction became rife in the society. Political thugs indulged in them and the results were the various acts of murder, arson and vandalism.

Thus Okediji sees the acrimonious party-politics of the 1960s where healthy, strong, hemp smoking young men were used as weapons for political ends as a root cause of criminality in the society. The activities of Tafa Ajao clearly portray some of the criminal deeds in which the political thugs were involved:

Níbíkíbi tí wọn bá gbé n ẹ ipàdé ọ̀ṣẹ̀lú,
 Tàfá gbòdò wà láàrin wọn ni. Nínú kó wà
 nìbẹ̀ lati da, ipàdé nàà rú, tàbí kó dúró
 tí wọn lati ba awọn tí ó bá fẹ̀ da ipàdé
 nàà rú jà. Ọun ni igí wọ̀rọ̀kọ̀ tíí da ina

rú. Enikéni ni ó lè bẹ Tafa níṣé
 ijòngbòn. Ti eni tí ó bá sì bẹṣé
 níṣé lóni ín ni i ṣe. Nitorí èyí, ó
 le da ipàdé egbé kan rú lóni ín, kí ó
 sì sin egbé kan náà lọ sóde lola lati
 dáàbò bò wòn. Eni tí ó bá sanwó fún
 Tafa lóni ín ní kàn ni Tafa mò ...

Anywhere a political meeting is holding, Tafa must be there. He is either there to disorganize the meeting or to fight anyone who wants to cause disorder. He is the crooked wood that disorganizes the fire. Anyone can engage Tafa for any assignment that involves trouble. He serves the current employer. Therefore he can cause commotion and disarray in a particular party's meeting today, and be a security force to the same party tomorrow. It is the person who pays Tafa today that he recognizes.

Okediji uses Tafa's life style as a thug to depict the pattern of life of thugs during the period of political turbulence. In some cases, political thugs were bonafide properties of political parties. In the eyes of the society they constituted paid criminals. In the period 1960-1966, they were a menace to the society and a dangerous threat to the peace and security of many Yoruba urban communities. Okediji thus uses Tafa's example to establish the fact that the introduction of thuggery into

the party politics in the 1960s greatly influenced the increase of criminality in the society.

Okediji creatively posits yet another cause of criminality in the society. It is the propensity to become a man of high social standing in the community. The Yoruba cherish the principle of conspicuous social recognition in the community. The Yoruba society is noted for its highly hierarchical and elaborate structure consisting of compound heads, chiefs with the Oba as the supreme head. This hierarchical organization, gives room for anyone who can distinguish himself as a notable personality through his own initiative or capability. A man can assume a distinguished position for himself in the society by his own tenacity of purpose. He can build up a circle of people around himself, such people may be members of his family, friends, distant relatives, hangers on, followers and admirers. Such people would acknowledge him as leader. Such a position requires attributes like wealth, herbal medicine, toughness. This is a common phenomenon because the Yoruba social structure though hierarchical, is not rigid or static. It is a dynamic conglomerate of individuals who usually engage in a competitive struggle to establish and enhance their own

social position. Barber [1979: 80] terms this practice the "Principle of Bigmanship".

By the 1960s the craze for wealth had made the society individualistic with each one struggling single-handedly to attain a high position. This desire to be recognized as a "bigshot" in the community became heightened during the period of Okediji's writing. It was a period when the term V.I.P (Very Important Personality) carried a significant social import, indicating an elevated socio-economic or political status. Many men wanted to become 'Big Men' and struggled in competition with one another to become acknowledged as such. This struggle for social recognition was an indication that the society was deeply competitive and individualistic in outlook.

Okediji recognizes this increasing aspiration to become 'big' in the society. He sees it as one of the causes of crimes in the society. The struggle to be recognized as a 'Big Man' is manifest in some of the criminal characters. Like Oyeniya Seriki, Jakunma Gbekuta, Oloriaye and Adegun Adeogun. All these characters possess wealth, medicine, toughness, boldness and proven ability as leaders, which are some of the

attributes of men of high social standing. They are all recognized as, big men in their various communities. Adegun Adeogun's declaration in Agbàlagbà Akàn bears credence:

Adegun ní, sé ẹ̀ sí mò pé emi kì í ẹ̀
 onípoṭímòṭò! Kí n sa lọ kí n fi aya
 ati ọmọ sílẹ̀ kọ? Alága ẹgbẹ̀ ni mo jẹ
 nínú ijọ mo sí wà nínú ìgbìmọ̀ ilé-ìwé.
 Mò n ẹ̀ baba ìsàlẹ̀ fún ẹgbẹ̀ eléré méjì.
 Emi ni akòwé àgbà ni ...

Adegun says, you know for sure that I am a responsible man in my family! Do you want me to run away and leave my wife and children behind? I am chairman of a society in the church, I am a member of the school board of governors. I am Patron to two musical groups. I am the secretary general in ...

The excerpt portrays Adegun as a distinguished personality in the society. The social, religious and educational positions he occupies are significations of 'bigmanship'. He belongs to a powerful criminal syndicate and this more than anything else constitutes his source of wealth and social recognition. Thus from Okediji's point of view, the causes of criminality in the society are many and varied, but the highest common factor of all is the

desire for money.

A second question which Okediji seems to pose is why crime thrives in the society. There are various reasons why crime thrives in the society, but to Okediji, one is fundamental - a definite flaw in our judicial system. One of the most important aspects of our judicial system on which Okediji focuses attention is the police force.

To Okediji, the police force is weak, ill-equipped and inefficient. The police force is depicted as devoid of adequate man power. There is a dearth of men with a high sense of dedication and commitment. The exodus of men of ability and competence from the police force has been variously caused by poor conditions of service, ill-health, death and finally domestic pressure which forces men like Lapade, to quit the force. In many episodes in the novels, the police is depicted as weak and witless. They get their priorities wrong. Rather than face the distressing situation of crime, they concentrate on trivial traffic offences. Lapade, who is Okediji's mouth-piece on the issue of the police ineptitude states categorically:

Awon Ọlọpàá òhún a si wá fi ètẹ̀ sílẹ̀
wọn a má a pa làpálápá. Wọn a fi
awon igára Ọlọsa tí n fítínà ilú
silẹ̀ wọn a má a lé ẹnì tí ó fi kẹkẹ̀
gbéenìyan káàkiiri ...

(Agbalagba Akan p.4)

The police abandon the cure of leprosy and concentrate on curing ringworm. They leave the robbers that disturb the peace of the community and concern themselves with the arrest of those who lift passengers on bicycles.

The whole picture is one of leaving the substance and running after the shadow. To the Aláròyé Ìbàdàn, (p. 61 of Ajà ló lerù) the police set-up calls for total overhauling. In a column sarcastically captioned: "Ọlọpàá Ìbàdàn bí akòdà ibòmíràn" (The Ibadan police, like court messengers in other places), the paper calls for a change in the headship of the police force. It advises:

... kò sí ohun tí o lè dára tó kí wọn
kúkú gbé gbogbo awon Ọlọpàá ilẹ̀ yìí
kírò, kí wọn ko wón lọ si ilú míràn,
kí olórí wọn Inspektọ̀ Agbà, Audu
Karimu si ni isimi gboṣoṣo pẹ̀lú àitún
padà senu isẹ̀ mọ̀ láíláí.

There is nothing more befitting than to transfer all the police men in this town to another place, and the chief Inspector, Audu Karimu to be given a long leave and retirement.

Deplorable and damaging as the comment seems, Okediji uses it to reveal the feelings of the people about the incapability of the police to tackle the problem of armed robbery in the society.

In particular, Audu Karimu the Chief Inspector of Police is shown as a misfit. Many of his speeches and activities portray him as a leader grossly lacking in initiative and direction. Lapade the hero of the two novels describes Audu as *kùdùúsù*, (a sluggish imbecile).

In Àjà ló lerù p.3, he says further:

kí ló tilẹ̀ ǹ dù tó ǹ rí mú gan an?
 Kò lè dá adiyè mú ká tó wá sọ pé àwọn
 tagbó tagbó.

What is he scrambling for and catching in particular? He cannot catch a fowl not to talk of hemp pedlars.

This humorous play on Audu Karimu's name occurs at the beginning of Àjà ló lerù. But as the story unfolds, several incidents portray Audu Karimu as a mockery of a police chief. For instance, in an episode in a hospital,

in Agbàlagbà Akan (pp. 32-33) Audu Karimu is so confident about his strategy to implicate Lapade, that he rashly enters the hospital and without permission, opens a patient's face and forces him to wake up from a much-needed sleep. The nurse on duty pushes him off in anger so much so that Audu staggers and falls. His action exposes him to scathing comments from the nurse:

Ará ibo ní ọ? Ibo lo ti wá?
 Èni tó ẹẹẹ sun lá tàárò ... ni
 iwọ àfọri yìí wá n jì! Mánú
 èniyàn kì í ẹ ọ ni? Taa ni o
 tilẹ gbàẹ lẹwọ rẹ kí o tó o
 wọ wọ̀dù wa ganan? ...
 Audu dide nilẹ ojú sù tìí.

(pp. 32-33)

Where are you from? Where have you come from? The man who is just sleeping after much effort is the one that you this insane person is waking up by force. How can you be so merciless? Who gave you permission to enter the ward ...? Audu rose up, covered with shame.

The doctor who comes in at this point also castigates him:
 (Agbalagba Akan p. 33).

Irú Ọlọpàá wo ni tírẹ? Ibo ni wọn ti kó irú eléyìí ní isẹ Ọlọpàá? Taa ni kó kakí fún èyi rándan rándan yíí ... kí akíndanidáni kan já wọ ọsípítù kó máa sísọ lórí aláìsàn, kí ẹ má a pé Ọlọpàá ni?

What kind of police officer are you? Where has this man trained as a police officer? Who has given this idiot of a man a police uniform? This ignoramus rushes into the hospital and starts to uncover a patient's face and you still say he is a policeman.

The utterances are no doubt insulting and derogatory. They are however calculated to portray the state of shame and ignominy into which the police has fallen. Audu Karimu is the only distinct police character in the two novels. In many episodes and incidents in the novels, he is a personification of an inept, and impotent police force, lacking in tact, and able leadership to crush the staggering wave of criminality in the society.

Crime and criminal's tactics

In exposing the state of criminality in the society, Okediji does not just narrate the heinous atrocities perpetrated by the criminals. Nor are these same atrocities simply enumerated by the local newspaper,

Aláròyé Ibàdàn. They are scenically presented. The criminal's operations are sensational. For instance, in Agbàlagbà Akàn, in a bid to incriminate Lapade, the criminals acting with despatch and diligence, bring a corpse to his house in the still of the night. With great skill and accuracy, Lapade and Tafa are captured and taken to Oloriaye's palace. In a swift and sharp fashion, Fẹmi's house is razed by the thieves, and she is instantly transported to Oloriaye's palace for slaughtering.

Okediji further reveals that behind these wicked acts are various categories of criminals. First to appear on the scene in Àjà ló lerù is Taiwo who in a devil-may-care attitude drives a car WOT 204, with the intention of crushing Lapade whom he recognizes as an antagonist. Taiwo is injured in the process. He is captured and kept in the custody of Jampako, the keeper of an ancient occult building in the city. The discovery of Jampako's house reveals yet another aspect of criminality, namely, the availability of hide-outs for criminal purposes. Okediji thus reveals that such hide-outs are important breeding grounds for multifarious crimes.

In Àjà lo lerù, it is revealed that Jampako and Tiamiyu own or keep hideout, at Abẹbì and Elékùrọ areas,

of Ibadan. Jampako's hideout is difficult to reach. Okediji describes the circuitous route to the place:

Wọn sòkalẹ̀ ní Abẹ̀bì. Tafa ẹ́áájú,
Lapade si tẹ̀ lé e. Wọn ń lọ. Wọn
ń lọ. Bí wọn ba rin síwájú díẹ̀, wọn
a yà sọtun, bí wọn bá tun lọ díẹ̀ si i,
wọn a tún ya sòsì. Bẹ̀ẹ̀ ni wọn ń rìn fún
nnkan bí ogbòn ìṣẹ́jú ...

They came down at Abẹ̀bì. Tafa led the way and Lapade followed. They moved on, after some distance, they would turn to the right, after some more distance, they would turn to the left. So they walked in a tortuous fashion) for about thirty minutes.

The houses used as hideouts are in many cases ancient, ugly, and frightful in appearance. Okediji's description of Jampako's house is illuminating:

Láìpẹ̀ púpọ̀ mọ̀, wọn dé agbo ilé
nla kan báyií. Ọ̀giri àtijọ̀ ni
wọn fi mo ọ̀ yipọ̀. Wọn kò rẹ̀ ilé
nàà ní sánmòntì; bẹ̀ẹ̀ ni wọn kò fi
òdà kùn ún. Wanke ni Ọ̀giri nàa
fẹ̀yín síta, tí gbogbo rẹ̀ rí
ẹ́ágisàgi, kò si fẹ̀rẹ̀se kan kan lára
Ọ̀giri nàa bi ó ti gùn tó. Ilé aláyipò
àtijọ̀ ni ... Gbogbo yààrá tó wà ninú
ilé nàà kò yọ̀ ilẹ̀kùn sóde ...

Shortly afterwards, they came to a big house. It is fenced round with an ancient wall. It is neither plastered nor painted. The walls are sharp and ugly. There are no windows in the house. It is an ancient building and all the rooms have no doors that lead outside.

Not only are the buildings erected in secluded areas, there are cryptic signs to know whether the occupants are in or not. On their arrival at the Elékùró hideout, there is no easy means of knowing whether any one is in. But Tafa has a clue, he says:

Òpùrọ̀ ni Tiamiyu. Ó sá pamọ̀ ni.
 Bí kò bá sí nílẹ̀, wọ̀n ì bá fi nkan
 dígàgá ẹ̀nu ọ̀nà. Ẹ̀ran-ò-jẹ̀ nikan ni
 wọ̀n pade yìí. Ó wa nílẹ̀ ni ìtumọ̀
 ìyẹn. Àmi tí a fi i mọ̀ nìyẹn. Bí
 kò ba sí nílẹ̀, ìbá sí àgánrántì sílẹ̀
 ni, tí ibà fi nkan dígàgá ọ̀nà.

(p. 6)

Tiamiyu is a liar. He is only hiding. If he were not in, he would have put something across the gate, he only shuts the smaller door, which is a sign that he is in. If he is not in, he would only open the smaller door and put something across the entrance.

Apart from the visual sign of communication, there is the auditory means of information, to indicate that a stranger

is around. Thus before Tafa enters Jampako's house at Abẹ̀bì, he claps three times. He does the same at Tiamiyu's hideout at Elékùrò. Similarly they have a cryptic language, unknown to the outsider. Thus Tafa at the entrance of Tiamiyu's house in the usual Yoruba traditional salutation says: "Àgò onílẹ̀ yíí o. È gááfàrà nílẹ̀ yíí o". He receives no answer. But later, he changes to a queer expression and says: "Mo tẹ̀ndà o, mo toṣoṣo apólójà ..." then a voice comes from inside: "Mo yòndà o. Maa bọ ... (I grant you permission. Come right in.)

The sign for gaining entry to Taiwo's hideout at Ikèrèkú is different. As Taiwo and his gang arrive at the gate, he whistles a sound which is interpreted to mean: "kìtá kítá tán ní bẹ̀ jẹ́jẹ́ ló kù". (The trouble is over, it is now easy all the way). The door opens quietly and some one greets: "È mọ ọ wolẹ o" ... (You are welcome). At the palace of Olóríáyé in Àgbàlagbà Akàn, the sign, four claps and the whistling of some phrase that is interpreted: "Yíyọ ẹ̀kùn tojo kọ" (p. 99) (The tiger's slow gentle movement is no cowardice.)

Okediji's description of this secret communication among criminals is a demonstration of his wealth of knowledge about the tactics and strategies of the men of

the underworld. It is in consonance with Okediji's effort to expose all that is hidden in the crime world. The criminals have an obscure, yet adroit system of operation. First, their hideouts are often difficult to trace and in many cases, are unknown to the law enforcement agencies. Their language is closed to the uninitiated. An air of fear and intimidation surrounds their habitats such that most people would never dare to disclose them to the police. Tiamiyu's statement to Lapade on the day the latter arrives at the criminal's hideout at Elékùrò aptly attests to this:

Nítòrì náà, ibi tí òrò rẹ dé dúró bayíí,
 a gbòdò pa ọ ni, obinrin tó bá fojú kan
 orò, orò a gbe e. Bẹẹ ni tire yíí. Ọ
 tí ri ohun ti èniyàn kíí rí ... Ọ ti já
 ipa wa, bẹẹ èniyàn kíí já ipa wa, kó wà
 láàyè ...

(Ajà ló lẹrù pp. 83-84).

Therefore the verdict on your case is that we just must kill you. When a woman sets her eyes on the orò, the orò carries her away. So is your case. You have seen what must never be seen. You have uncovered our secret, and no one does it and stays alive.

The criminals are perfectly aware of the inefficiency and

inability of the police to uncover the criminal's tactics. Thus Tiamiyu, one of the criminals asserts:

Bó ba ẹ ti àwọn ọlópàá ni, bí
wọn bá ń dọdọ wa sii lọdun mẹwàá,
àyà wa kò lè já.

(Ajà ló lerù p.)

As for the police, if they continue to search for us for the next ten years, we can never be afraid.

Okediji thus uses the exposure of such hideouts to establish the point that with the existence of such sequestered hideouts and the criminals' cryptic signs, the extirpation of crime in the society is a difficult if not an impossible, task.

Criminals and their operations

Okediji reveals the structure of the operations of the men of the under world. The criminals fall into two broad categories. There are the lone rangers, among these was Salami Kemberu who had earlier broken into Lapade's house in the night. Salami's accomplice as revealed by Tafa, is Karimu Alakoba. Lone ranger criminals are easily captured by the police. They are therefore regular

convicts in the prison. The second category is made up of a strong cultic syndicate, under a clearly defined head of operations. The dramatic incident in Tiamiyu's hideout at Elékùrò provides an opportunity for the disclosure of this group. Among members of the identified syndicate are Tiamiyu, Kòla, Dele, Taiwo with Jàkùmò Gbékútà as their head. The base of their operations is situated in a bush at Ìkèrèkú, in the outskirts of Ibadan where Gbékútà owns a large plantation of marijuana.

It is in Agbàlagbà Akàn that we have a deeper knowledge of the organization and management of the criminal syndicate. In many episodes, Okediji discloses that the syndicate has various branches under a supreme head. The capture of Lapade and Tafa, by a team of armed robbers takes Lapade to the palace of Oloriaye the "chief executive of all the robbers in Yoruba land". These branches are at Egbédá, Iwó, Èrunmu, Orígbó etc. Their headquarters is in an unnamed bush in the outskirts of Ibadan, where their overall chief executive lives.

The thieves in many respects, demonstrate a high sense of loyalty to their leader. The performance of their duties and the execution of the leader's instructions are carried out with despatch. For instance, immediately

Lapade reaches Oloriaye's court, he instantly watches the sense of dedication displayed by the members of the gang. Every one of them sets about his duty with a remarkable sense of responsibility. Okediji describes their movement:

Awon Olósà míran n lẹ wọn n bọ
lái fọhun. Lápàdé n fi ojú bá
wọn lẹ, lati mefò ohun ti wọn fẹ
ṣe, lati mọ èrò ti wọn fẹ gbà sí
òun. Ẹ̀gbọ̀n kò ridí ẹ̀gbòkẹ̀gbodo
wọn.

(Agbalagba Akan p. 99)

Some of the thieves moved up and down in silence. Lapade's eyes followed their movement in order to catch a glimpse of their plan. But he had no knowledge of their intentions.

There is no room for hesitation as to Oloriaye's position in the syndicate when Lapade sees him on his arrival on the scene. He is outstandingly tall and slim. His personality is so commanding and intimidating that Lapade's usually indomitable courage is daunted:

Dóógó dúró, Ó tejúmọ̀ Lapade, Lapade
sì fẹ̀rẹ̀ wọ̀lẹ̀. Ó dàbí ẹ̀gbà tí ẹ̀yinjú
Dóógó mejeeji n gbẹ ihò sí àtàrí
Lapade. Bí ọ̀mọ̀dé bá dé ibi ẹ̀rù, ẹ̀rù

a bàá. Jìnnijìnnì bo Lapade ...
 (Àgbàlagbà Akàn p. 100)

Doogo stands erect looking deep into Lapade's eye. Lapade nearly feels like disappearing into the ground. It seems as if Doogo's two eyes are drilling a deep hole into Lapade's head. When a child witnesses a frightful sight, he is surely terrified. Lapade is covered with indescribable fear.

Much more daunting is Oloriaye's speech. His utterances are full of asperity, authority, and firmness and they often end with "mo pá láṣẹ ni o" (I command it). His followers almost in unison usually answer, "àṣẹ, àṣẹ" (so be it). Thus when he pronounces the verdict on Lapade, his word becomes a decree. Perhaps the most significant source of his position is his avowed possession of money and herbal medicine. He himself affirms his wealth:

Mo wá owó dé ibi tí a lè wá a
 dé nílé ayé yìí, mo si ṣòḡgùn
 ju babalawo lọ ... Mo lówó mo
 sì lóògùn. Agbara mi ni iwònyí,
 àwọn ló sì n fún mi ni ìgboyà.
 (p. 106)

I searched for money wherever it
 can be found in this world, and I
 make medicine more than a babalawo

(herbalist-diviner?)
 I possess both money and
 medicine. These are the
 sources of my power. They are
 the basis of my fearlessness.

Furthermore, he enumerates the categories of incantations
 in his possession,

Ọfọ egbé tó dájú ní bẹ, bẹ̀ẹ̀ ni
 ọfọ àfẹ̀ ẹ̀rí, ọfọ gbètugbètu, ọfọ
 kánàko; ọfọ àlupayídà, ọfọ àbo,
 ọfọ àşẹ, ọfọ èpè, tí í jẹ̀ lẹ̀şẹ̀kẹ̀şẹ̀,
 ọfọ àfòşẹ̀, ọfọ amúnimúye tí onitòhún
 yó máa wo bọ̀ọ̀ bí àgùntàn, ọfọ madarikan.
 Mélòó la o ka nínú eyin Adépèlẹ̀?
 (Àgbàlagbà Akàn p.161)

There are various patent incantations
 capable of producing diverse effects,
 like magical transportability,
 invisibility, unquestioned instantaneous
 obedience, short distancing, conjuring,
 immobilization, irrefutable authority,
 curses, efficacious charm, paralysing
 of the faculties of the enemy such that
 the enemy will become stupefied like a
 sheep, invincibility. How many shall
 we count? They are just too numerous
 for mention.

Okediji's enumeration of some of the various types of
 incantations here serves to reveal that one of the most
 trusted and most effective weapons of criminals in the

society is traditional medicine.

Another illuminating aspect of their systems of operation is oath-taking and cultic initiation among criminals. Furthermore, most of them bear extraordinary sobriquets in place of their common names. Thus their chief executive is called "Oloriaye" (head of the universe) their head at Ìkèrèkú is "Jakumo Gbekuta, baba mugbó mugbó" (Diehard Wildcat, head of hemp smokers) some members of Oloriaye's gang bear sobriquets like kúrúnà (crawcraw) "paramóle" (viper) Jambala, Àgbákò, fàrífàrí and pàlóngò. The sobriquets make it difficult for them to be easily identified by name. Some of the sobriquets are descriptive, of the actions or dispositions of the criminals.

The Criminals and the society

In the process of exposure, Okediji reveals that society's conciliatory attitude to the criminals is one of the reasons why they thrive. The society is either forced or cajoled into taking this attitude. One of the weapons used by the criminals is intimidation. Members of the public are coerced into fear. Some kind of apprehension surrounds the mere mention of the names of the criminals. Thus most members of the public dread to

disclose the hideouts of the criminals.

Okediji depicts this kind of situation in Àgbàlagbà Akàn.

A beggar has asked a shoemaker at Ègbédá to direct him to Oyeniyi Seriki's house. Oyeniyi is the accredited head of the thieves of Ègbèda. The shoemaker reacts with unconcealed fright:

Àà bó bá ẹ se Séríkí ló ñ bèèrè, emi ò
mò ọ̀n o. Dákun súnmọ wájú lẹ̀hùn. Jọ̀ọ̀
má bèrè Oyeniyi lẹ̀wọ̀ mi o, mo fỌ̀lọ̀run
Ọba bè ọ̀ o. Seriki! Emi ò mẹni ti i jẹ
bẹ̀ẹ̀ o. Oò ti ẹ si bèèrè rẹ̀ lẹ̀wọ̀ mi o,
şó o gbọ? Işẹ̀ bàtà ni mò wá ẹ l'Ègbédá,
lati bí ọ̀dún méjilá tí mo ti de lẹ̀ yíí,
ngo si dáràn rí bẹ̀ẹ̀ ni n gò yọ̀júràn.
Jẹ̀jẹ̀jẹ̀ mi ni mo ñ lọ ni temi. Àlejò
kì i şòbéeéré. Olodumare! kí ni baba
yíí wá ñ bi mi yíí? Jẹ̀ ng fara re sùn
lóni ó, jẹ̀ n sùn un re ...

(Àgbàlagbà Akàn p. 43)

Please, if it is Seriki that you are asking about, I do not know him. And I beg you, move away from here. Please do not ask of Oyeniyi from me, I beg you in the name of God. Seriki! I do not know who is called by that name. Indeed, you have not asked of him from me, do you hear that? I only come to Ègbédá as a shoemaker, and since about

twelve years when I have been working here, I have never gone beyond my bounds. I go about in my own quiet ways. A stranger does not go beyond his limit. O mighty God! what is this man asking from me? Let me sleep peacefully today.

Even though the utterance is in form of a soliloquy, it is dramatic. It reveals a situation of fear and insecurity, the awe and terror that surround Seriki's name. Perhaps out of sheer compassion for the poor, helpless 'beggar' the shoemaker changes his mind. As he cautiously points to Seriki's house he adds:

Şùgbón má sọ pé emi ni mo tọka
fún ọ o ... kò sí ẹni tí o lè bí
ní gbogbo ilẹ̀ yìí kó nawọ ilé
Seriki fún ọ.

(Agbàlagbà Akan pp.43-44)

But do not say I am the one who has directed you to Seriki's house. If you ask anyone in the whole of this town, no one will show you his house.

Even though members of the public have abundant information about the brains behind criminal activities, they lack the courage to disclose such information to law enforcement agents.

The other aspect of society's conciliatory attitude is shown in the episode at Gbekuta's hideout at Ikereku in Ajà ló lẹ̀rù. Taiwo's mother is in charge of the house. She is let into the secret of their system of communication. (see pp. 258-261 above). She has been made an accomplice in the illegal trade. Thus she asks Lapade:

Ṣe ọmọ lẹ̀yín fẹ̀ rà ni, àbẹ́wé? Ewé ti
wọn ṣẹ̀ṣẹ̀ ja sílẹ̀ ló rí yanturu ni yàrà
un. Mèlòò lẹ̀ ẹ̀ rà? Wọn ò sì ni í
ṣàìrì ọmọ mú bọ 'Bàdàn, bó sọkan ṣoṣo.
E mọ̀ mọ̀ wí fún wọn pé mo bèèrè lówọ̀ yín
o. Tori wọn è ẹ̀ fẹ̀ kẹ́mi o da si nnkankan,
kin wa a larúgbó mọ̀?

(Ajà lo lẹ̀rù p. 105)

Is it a child you want to buy or leaves?
The leaves they have just harvested are
very plenty. You can buy as much as you
like. You can be sure they would not
come from Ibadan without a child, even
if it is only one. But please, do not
tell them that I asked anything from you.
They don't want me to take part in any-
thing. What does an old woman know?

The use of a dialect of Yoruba is intended to show us that this old woman is an illiterate. Her utterances reveal her knowledge of the hemp business and kidnapping. She is most probably constrained to accept her position and

give her support, though she has to pretend to be unaware of the implications of such unlawful business. This kind of pretended ignorance by relations of criminals is one of the powerful reasons why crime thrives in the society.

Okediji reveals the various modes of operation of the criminals in his two novels under analysis. The way he does this shows that the criminals are a formidable establishment. They are organized, secretive, and feared by members of the public. On the other hand, the law enforcement agency, in whose charge is put the security of life and property of the society, is depicted to be no match for the criminals. The headship of the police force, is rotten, and the whole structure is absolutely weak. Unlike the criminals' syndicate, the police force lacks the sense of direction and mission with which to carry out its duty with despatch. This for Okediji, is one of the major reasons why criminality flourishes in the society.

After this exposure of the society, Okediji seems to ask the question: what is to be done? He himself provides the answer in his creation of Lapade, the hero of both novels in whose personality is embodied the action

that constitutes the theme of Okediji's novels.

Characterization and theme

Like other aspects of the form of the novels, Okediji's theme is neither narrated nor stated. It is personified, acted and displayed. The theme of both novels is the efficacy of action and it reverberates in many of the events in the novel. As Thomas Hardy rightly points out:

Characters, however they may differ, express mainly the author, his largeness of heart, or otherwise, his culture, his insight, and very little of any other person.¹³

This is particularly so with Okediji's creation of Lapade and Tafa his assistant. Lapade the hero, is the epitomé of Okediji's concern for his society. Lapade possesses what the police lack - a high sense of responsibility, mission and commitment. Lapade is the compendium of Okediji's panacea to the situation of criminality in the society.

Lapade is Okediji's finest character. His name is

¹³ Berger, M. 1977. Real and Imagined Worlds, Harvard University Press, pp. 119-132.

not obscure. It is a common Yoruba name. The name does not connote any particularly known historical figure. Yet it is interesting that unknown to Okediji himself, that name has a strong affinity with Ibadan cultural history.¹⁴

Unlike the Lapade in *Ọ̀sémíjì*, Okediji's Lapade is not depicted as a handsome or exuberant personality. All we know about him physically emanates from our imaginative

14. The name Lapade originally features in *Ọ̀sé méjì* the fifteenth Odu Ifá which was at the base of the establishment of Ibadan. See Abimbola, W. 1978 *Awon oju odu Mereerindinlogun*, O.U.P. p. 85 and p. 154

assessment of him, when Oloriaye meets him. Oloriaye is so surprised that the man whom his gang has dreaded for so long is not physically imposing after all. He exclaims:

Ṣé Lapade ọ̀hún nì yìí?
 Ènì tí í jẹ́ Lapade ọ̀hún nì kinní
 játíọ̀ yìí? Eleyí lè n pè ní Lapade?
 Àsé kinní Olóríburukú ọ̀hún kò jù
 bá yìí lọ?

(Agbàlagbà Akàn p. 100)

Is this the Lapade you are talking about?
 Is it this diminutive thing you call Lapade?
 Is this the one you call Lapade?
 So the ill-starred person is not more than
 this?

Lapade falls short of Oloriaye's expectation. He is probably expecting a man with a commanding personality. But Lapade does not have to be tall and imposing to be useful. For Okediji, readers are not to be interested in Lapade's physical attraction. It is his moral and mental qualities that are essential. Okediji depicts these abundantly in his novels. For instance, the way Lapade discovers the hidden money in Ajà ló lẹ̀rù, his capture of Taiwo the dare-devil criminal, and how he

successfully wins Tafa over to his own side, confirm that he is an intelligent strategist.

Lapade has a deep concern for human life and property. The trenchant editorial comments of the Aláròyé Ìbàdàn and the passionate appeal by Angelina for help to retrieve the kidnapped Tòlani spur Lapade to action, in Ajà ló lẹ̀rù. The cold-blooded murder of Dele and Kunle, makes him determine to avenge the death of the young men on the cruel robbers. Thus he throws himself into the struggle with zest. Armed with this spirit of humanity, he succeeds in returning Tòlani and Sẹ̀li to their homes and opens the way for the police to arrest the hemp and human sellers at Ikèrèkú. His tenacity of purpose and will lead him to recover the stolen money from Oyeniyi Seriki's syndicate, at Egbédá.

When eventually he is caught in the criminals' web and taken to Oloriaye's court, it seems as if Lapade has come to the end of the road. But Lapade demonstrates the qualities of a man who is never daunted or disheartened by confrontation. In all his encounters with the police and the criminals, he is never rash. He never takes a step which he is likely to regret. Lapade has a tremendous capacity to plan. He rescues Fẹ̀mi and restores her to life.

And when finally he exposes Doogo and Adegun to public ridicule, Lapade distinguishes himself as a champion of morality.

A comparison of the qualities of Lapade and Audu Karimu throws some light on what the society needs to overcome, the problem of criminality in the society. Where Lapade is acclaimed champion, the police chief becomes an object of shame and humiliation. The police chief fails because he is inactive, but Lapade succeeds because he is a man of action. The titles of both novels Ajà ló lẹrù and Àgbàlagbà Akàn carry important messages for the society on the issue of crime. The first, Ajà ló lẹrù (shortened form of the proverb Ajà ló lẹru, irọ ni pẹpẹ n pa (the attic has the power to carry the load the wooden shelf is a liar) is a figurative comparison of the vigour and will of Lapade with the weakness and vulnerability of Audu Karimu. The Ajà (attic) symbolizes Lapade's potency and capacity to withstand the criminals, while the wooden shelf, (pẹpẹ) symbolizes the frailty and ineptitude of the police to combat the increasing wave of crime.

The second title Àgbàlagbà Akàn is derived from Àgbàlagbà Akàn ó kó sí garawa (the elderly crab falls

into the bucket).

In Agbàlagbà Akàn, where Lapade by virtue of his many attributes gallantly overcomes the criminals, outwits the police and saves the victims, the police chief, a debilitated force, crashes in ignominy! It is only men of Lapade's will and calibre that can free the entire society from the menace of criminals.

The language of the novels is the language of the ordinary people in society. It is a mixture of short and long sentences juxtaposed for effect and clarity. Okediji uses proverbs frequently, effectively and innovatively. Barber describes the characteristics of Okediji's language:

If we look in detail at his prose style we find the same qualities of flexibility and variety. His writing is always lively, simple, colloquial and apt. It could be described as heightened speech. It has all the nuances, the changes of tone and tempo, the pithy directness of real speech; but all these qualities are shaped to the requirements of the narrative to arouse anticipation, create tension, suggest a mood - with a skill which is beyond the scope of ordinary speakers.¹⁵

Barber's description is appropriate, for language use in Okediji's novels is vivid and lively. The novel as a whole has a distinct structural unity, almost everything in the

¹⁵ Barber, K., 1979 op.cit. pp. 29-30.

novel - technique, language, actions and interactions of characters as well as the succession of incidents suggests a man on the move.

In conclusion, Okediji's novels carry a realistic, critical and perfectly coherent vision of contemporary Yoruba society. The presentation of ideas, the extent and intensity of criminal activities in both novels show Okediji as a writer who has an intimate knowledge of his age. He is perfectly aware of the fact that the various changes in the structure of the society have affected the world view of the society. He recognizes that the world view of his society has become success-oriented and much more power conscious than before. He realizes that the maxim of his age has changed from "perseverance overcomes everything" to "money overcomes everything". It is an age where the important thing is the acquisition of wealth, not the source of the wealth. His is an age when the status-seeking propensity of the modern man has become heightened.

But rather than accept this world view of wealth-acquisition through criminal means, Okediji assumes an uncompromising posture. For Okediji, crime is a force that should be ruthlessly extirpated. It is a complex

problem that requires a drastic solution. Like the shoemaker in Agbàlagbà Akàn, the time has come for the society to change its mind and attitude to criminals. The simmering state of fear of criminals should give way to fearless attack. The practice of aiding and abetting criminals should change to exposure of criminals. The situation is a challenge to the police force. It requires a high sense of dedication and commitment to the cause of security of human life and property. Okediji sees the need for re-orientation and redefinition of policy in the police force. The police must change its tactics and improve its investigative techniques and methods. Existing vacancies should be filled with men of will-power, sense of mission and determination to serve the nation.

To Okediji, the situation of crime in the society is not insoluble. The solution lies not in patience and perseverance rather, it requires radical action.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we have attempted to demonstrate that the Yoruba novel does not exist in isolation. Every Yoruba novel has a basic relationship with the novelist and a particular society. The study has shown that the Yoruba novelist is a product of a particular social class. The novelist is born into the society, and learns many concepts and ideas in the social, economic and political environments of the society. In creating his art, the unique combination of his personality and social environment influences his purpose and posture. The novelist's art, is a structure of words and ideas, a social fact and property of the society.

Since both the novelist and the novel form are products of a particular society, no meaningful study of the Yoruba novel can be done in isolation of the society that gives it birth. Our study of the sociology of the Yoruba novel thus reinforces the structuralist view that literature is holistic. It is a totality, made up of parts which are in particular relationships to one another. Thus any critical study of the Yoruba novel, and indeed of any work of literature, should not be limited to

the mere analysis of text alone. Rather it should see a work of art in a wider context, as part of the life of the writer, whose life is to a great extent, a part of the life of the society as a whole. Such a study would yield a fuller and richer understanding of the novelist, his art, and his society.

The novelists examined in this study are all members of the nascent bourgeois middle class in a developing capitalist society. As could be seen in the study, their society is not static. It experiences remarkable changes - in cultural outlook, socio-economic order, and world view. Each of the novelists reacts and relates to these changes differently.

Thomas's experiences as a christian, schoolmaster, and journalist deeply affect his stance. His outlook on the changing world view of his society is rather critical. To him the change from communalism to individualism and materialism consequent upon the incursion of capitalism is disastrous and tragic. Thus rather than accept the world view of his society, he assumes a disapproving stance. He uses his novel's structure to weave the individualism and materialism of the society around the character of the protagonist, Segilola, who finally collapses under the

heavy burden of the throes and pains of a changing society. But Segilola is not crushed. She is left in travail as she wallows in endless sorrow. She is a symbol of the interminable tragic consequences of the new socio-economic order. Only does Thomas reject the world view of his society, he also transcends it, to expose its tragic consequences.

The precolonial traditional society which Fagunwa chose as setting in his first two novels was replete with many cherished traditional values. It was an agrarian, and peaceful society. Family life was coporate, integrated and well regulated. Fagunwa cherished some of the traditional values. Among these were the agrarian life, the monarchical institution and the Yoruba hunter. He demonstrated a strong admiration for the Yoruba hunter and depicted him as a man of dauntless courage and proven intrepidity, who represented the ideal of manhood in the precolonial Yoruba society.

But Fagunwa recognizes the fact that no society is ever static. With the advent of the colonialism, the traditional society began to experience changes. The society is affected by foreign influence. The agrarian economy is gradually changing. The socio-political situation is being influenced by the colonial administration.

The powers and prestige of the traditional rulers are being gradually reduced. Traditional values are giving way to foreign influences. The colonial missionary education has produced a new social class the educated christian elite. This new group recognize themselves as beneficiaries of the colonial administration. They identify themselves with the ideology of the colonial ruling class. Moreover, this new social group is beginning to constitute the nascent bourgeois middle class. Not only are they increasing in number and prestige, they are also enjoying greater regard and recognition in the society.

As seen in chapter three, the structure of his first two novels covertly depicts the traditional society as disturbed by foreign influence. The peace of the society has been affected. The society needs a saviour to restore peace and stability. Will this saviour be the traditional Yoruba hunter or the emerging educated elite? A Marxist study of the first two novels of D.O. Fagunwa reveals that Fagunwa takes sides with the colonial christian ruling class. Our study of his novels under discussion shows that Fagunwa unequivocally presents himself as a strong advocate of the colonial administration. He was a beneficiary of the colonial missionary education, rising from humble beginnings to become one of the nascent bour-

Thus in his first two novels, Fagunwa demonstrates his high regard for the colonial missionary machinery. He sees himself both as a representative of the growing elitist class as well as a spokesman of the colonial administration. He is so committed to the christian cause that in the entire structure of his novels, under study, he solidly identifies himself with the aspirations of the colonial administration in its bid to ensure peace and stability in the society. As pointed out in p.154, even though Fagunwa uses Yoruba oral traditional materials in his novels, he ensures that such materials are carefully chosen, such that they are acceptable to the elitist christian audience and the colonial ruling class.

Okediji's perception of the society differs considerably from those of his predecessors. At the time of his writing, the political climate had changed. His was the post-independence era. The changing socio-economic order had become much more pronounced than ever before in the social structure of the society, creating a greater tendency towards a certain competitiveness. The progressive incursion of capitalism tended to have dehumanising consequences on the society. Money and material consciousness became the vogue. The escalating changes in socio-economic and political patterns in the society led to an upsurge of

inordinate ambition for material acquisition. This situation gave way to various unscrupulous practices - profiteering, hemp peddling, kidnapping, unprecedented robbery and gangsterism. But as seen in the novels, Okediji vehemently opposes these criminal means of wealth acquisition. Not only is he inexorably opposed to this fact growing criminal tendency, he rejects and challenges it. He thereby presents a new truth which is in accordance with the reality of modern Yoruba society - war against criminality.

The varying standpoint of these Yoruba novelists to the cause of the society buttresses the point earlier made (p.11) that whether an author realises it or not, every work of art is in a way, ideological, and that literature is an expression of a world view which serves particular social interests.¹ But as this study reveals, it is not binding that writers who are members of the same class will have the same outlook. Various factors of social change and individual personality determine the attitude of each writer to his society.

1. Barber, K. op.cit., p.1.

It is possible for a writer to hold a different position within a class. All the novelists examined in this study had a christian background, they were all school masters, they belonged to the middle class, yet their view on the society differed considerably. Thomas takes a bitterly critical stance, Fagunwa remains solidly conservative while Okediji is relatively radical. The varying postures of the Yoruba novelists examined in this study thus confirm the views of Marxists like Duvignaud, Caudwell and Fischer, among others that, literature is an active force, which is capable of challenging, rejecting, and transcending ideology.

Our experience in this study, shows that there is need for new dimensions in Yoruba literary criticism. As stated earlier, studies based on the primacy of the literary text alone would yield narrow and superficial results. This study affirms that the existing critical studies on Yoruba literary artists need more detailed and sustained reappraisal in such a way that more light would be shed on their social significance and relevance to the society.

It is therefore our view that the application of Marxist critical theory to the works of great poets like Sobo Arobiodu, D.A. Obasa and Afolabi Johnson among others, will proffer a deeper knowledge about the relationship

between the structure of their poems and their society. The adoption of the theory of sociology of literature in the study of early Yoruba writers like A.K. Ajisafe, E.A. Akintan and S.A. Adenle will bring rewarding results. Finally, further sustained studies in the sociology of Yoruba written literature are needed. Such studies will proffer greater insights into the relationships between the Yoruba artist, his art and his society.

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